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Convergence of Objectives? An Evaluation of Social Forestry Interventions in Eastern Bhutan

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(The thoughts of people are not the same,
the feathers of birds are not the same)
Bhutanese proverb

Tim Bodt, Reg. Nr. 790620-077-130, July 2002.

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT
University for Life Sciences

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PICTURES FRONT PAGE (CLOCKWISE FROM LEFT UPPER CORNER):

MEMBERS OF DOZAM CFMG, ZANGKHAR
CHIRPINE FOREST AT THE FAMOUS 26-TURNS OF YADI, MONGAR (AFFECTED BY FIRE, SPRING 2002)
WOMEN AND GIRLS REPRESENTING THEIR HOUSEHOLDS AT DOZAM CFMG MEETING, WAICHUR
CHORTEN BELOW TRASHIGANG DZONG
TRASHIGANG FEO DORJI DRUKPA AND CFMG MEMBERS, PAM
● OZAMCF
TSHURGANG DRAPIHUGITSHUR, SOUTHERN BORDER OF CP AT MANAM
YEZORONGPEK CP, PAM, AFTER DESTRUCTION BY FIRE
WOMEN WITH CHILDREN AT DOZAM CFMG MEETING, SHAPIANGMA

(CENTRE):

TSHOKPEKTANG CP, LANGMACHHU, RIGHT NATURAL FOREST, LEFT PLANTATION

Tim Bodt, Reg. Nr. 790620-077-130, July 2002.
Written under supervision of Dr. Ir. K.F. Wiersum,
Forest and Nature Conservation Policy Group,
Wageningen University, The Netherlands.

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The central aim of this research is 'to evaluate social forestry interventions in eastern Bhutan from the perspective of the local community that is participating in it'. Recognising that this aim is too broad the problem statement was specified to 'considering that a non-convergence in objectives has been observed in many social forestry projects around the world, is such also the case in Bhutan?'. According to Wiersum (1999b) this non-convergence stems from a normative pluriformity in perspectives on forest resources and values, in forest types under community management and in forest management practices. Normative pluriformity occurs *within* as well as *between* actor categories. The non-convergence of objectives is generally considered as one of the major reasons of failure in social forestry interventions. Previous research in Bhutan (Wangchuk, 1995) has also shown that the absence of a common problem perception between the local community and the government is one of the contributors to failure of social forestry programmes. The underlying research served as a follow up on this research.

In Bhutan social forestry interventions have started rather late and as such lessons could be learnt from other countries. The study area of this research is eastern Bhutan. Social forestry interventions here have been facilitated by the third forestry development project that started in 1997. A selection was made of four sites- three Community Plantations and one Community Forest. All sites were severely degraded before plantation. The number of participating households ranged from 19 to 106.

The research questions relate to the objectives of the external actors (government and Third Forestry Development Project, TFDP), which were obtained from the policy documents and interviews with the responsible staff at the national, district and local government as well as the project, and the objectives of the local people. The role of the TFDP was mainly a facilitating one. As such the objectives of the TFDP and the government have been regarded as convergent. The external objectives were basically maintaining and increasing the forest cover on degraded sites, increasing the involvement of local people in forest management, and increasing the livelihood of rural communities.

The local objectives regarding expected output/benefits, management aspects and external inputs were mainly obtained through semi-structured group and key informant interviews. The local people were furthermore asked whether their objectives were met and whether they have been changed during the project implementation. Lastly reasons for success and failure were identified.

The objectives of the local community regarding benefits were mostly to increase the availability of fuelwood and timber and to a lesser extent fodder and shingles. The availability of other forest products and services was considered of lesser importance. Although the nature of the sites could only mean the accrual of benefits on the longer term, the people expressed the hope that forest products would become available within a shorter time span.

The management objectives have been specified in the CFMPs, both for technical as well as organisational aspects of management. In general the objectives of the local people have been sufficiently absorbed in the CFMPs as they expressed their satisfaction with the written rules as well as with their implementation. Grazing and fire protection were, besides plantation, the major management issues. Fire is the main hazard that threatens the social forestry projects in eastern Bhutan. Often the fires are beyond control before they are even

noticed. Grazing within the plantation areas is always restricted by means of social fencing arrangements. This system does not always work though. Minor changes were made in the CFMPs by the CFMG members to adjust for issues that had not been sufficiently recognised before.

In general the local communities are satisfied with the external inputs they receive from government and project. These consist of land, free seedlings, and technical assistance through forestry extension. Only in one site there was dissatisfaction with mainly the extension part.

This research concludes that a non-convergence in objectives between the local people and the government and external facilitators can not be observed in social forestry interventions in eastern Bhutan. Even though the objectives might seem different at first sight, their interdependence makes them more convergent. The only non-convergence was observed in the accrual of benefits. The communities most often gain control over degraded sites, resulting in benefits on the long term only. They however expect at least some benefits at the short term as well. This however has not lead to dissatisfaction. The importance of forestry extension in creating and maintaining a common problem perception between government and local community is also acknowledged. The process has right from the initial phases been participatory and as such the local objectives have been sufficiently absorbed in the management plans.

Not all sites have been completely successful and the main factors affecting success have been identified as technical and site characteristics and the dedication of extension agents. The dedication of extension agents is the most important contributor to a common problem perception between government and local people. Another main factor has been the inconsistency in government policies, which lasted right until the year 2000. Wangchuk (1995) has also identified most of these factors. But he identified the lack of forest extension and consequent lack of congruence in objectives between the government and the local people as a main reason for failure. However in three out of four of the sites visited in this research the forest extension has been shown to have significantly improved and to be of a positive influence.

Lastly it is recommended to upgrade Community Plantations to Community Forests, to improve the seedling provision, to adopt strict criteria for site location and to improve the fencing arrangements, to strengthen the institutional capacity at the national, district and local level, and to conduct further research on indigenous/traditional forest management practices and the influence of further decentralisation on the management of forests.

The preparation leading towards this research as well as the execution and finalisation have been really pleasurable. The general topic, social forestry, was something that had captivated my interest for some time. A number of short papers written for compulsory and elective subjects of my main study field, environmental economics, had already focussed on this topic. To do a full-fledged research in it was very enriching and rewarding, and has tremendously broadened my view, from the more theoretic environmental economics to a very practical, inter-disciplinary application where social skills proved just as valuable as scientific knowledge.

Conducting the fieldwork of this research was a real delight, as was conducting the previous research in Bhutan. Few people have the chance to go to Bhutan, even fewer have the chance to do research there, and even less fewer have the chance to do it twice. Therefore, I consider myself extremely fortunate and truly blessed by God that I have had this chance. My knowledge of the country, its people and environment, culture and traditions, religion and developments have only increased, and the love for it as well.

I hope that the results of this research are acceptable to and useful for all that have put their trust in me. I think that the main conclusion, that the government and local objectives at the root of social forestry interventions in eastern Bhutan are more or less similar and that a major non-convergence as observed elsewhere is not present, is a laudable result of the developments in social forestry in Bhutan in the years since 1995. On the other hand, this research shows that there is no room for complacency. Not every social forestry project is a success story, and every individual project has its strong and weak points. The recommendations are a small gesture towards improvement of things that were noticed as being in need for improvement.

There are many, many people that I should extend my gratitude towards. First and foremost, H.E. Lyonpo Kinzang Dorji, Minister of Agriculture, and Dr. Sangay Wangchuk, Head of the Nature Conservation Division, for so kindly permitting me to conduct my research in Bhutan and for assuring that I would get all the institutional backing and support I required.

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This list is not final, and definitely there are many more people who have contributed to making my research go smoothly and my stay in Bhutan a pleasure. To name them all would make this Preface and Acknowledgements a chapter by itself, and that would be too much. So let me just end here with a 'big'

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Name same kadrin cheyi la-
Thank you very much!

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Cheog	Sub-unit of geog, consisting of 2 to 3 villages or hamlets (Dz.)
Ghimi	Geog representative to the National Assembly (Dz.)
Chuppen	Elected leader of cheog (Dz.)
CF	Community Forestry, defined as in Wiersum (1999)
CFMG	Community Forest Management Group
CFMC	Community Forest Management Committee
CFMU	Community Forest Management Unit
CFMP	Community Forest Management Plan
CP	Community Plantation
CSO	Central Statistical Organisation
DAHO	Dzongkhag Animal Husbandry Officer
DAO	Dzongkhag Agriculture Officer
DzFO	Dzongkhag Forest Officer (dzongkhag, under FED), duty forestry extension
DFO	Divisional Forest Officer (territorial, under FSD), duty forest protection
DEFS	Dzongkhag Forestry Extension Section
DES	Department of Forest Services
DYT	Dzongkhag Yargye Tshogchung, District Development Committee
Dzong	Administrative and monastic centre of a district (Dz.)
Dzongda	Dzongkhag Commissioner (Dz.)
Dzongkha	National language of Bhutan
Dzongkhag	District, Bhutan has 20 districts (Dz.)
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
FEO	Forest Extension Officer, (under FED/dzongkhag), duty forestry extension
FM	Forest Management as defined by Wiersum, (1999)
FMU	Forest Management Unit
FNCR	Forest and Nature Conservation Rules, 2000
FNCA	Forest and Nature Conservation Act, 1995
FSD	Forestry Services Division
FTPP	Forest, Trees and People Programme of the FAO
FYP	Five Year Plan
Geog	Block, subdivision of district, Bhutan has 202 geog (Dz.)
GRI	Government Reserved Forest
GTZ	German Agency for Technical Co-operation
Gung	Household (Dz.)
Gup	Bloc head (Dz.)
GYT	Geog Yargye Tshogpa, Block Development Committee
ICIMOD	International Center for Integrated Mountain Development
ICRAF	International Center for Research on Agroforestry
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
LUPP	Land Use Planning Project
Mangt-ap	Village representative and decision maker
MoA	Ministry of Agriculture
NRTI	Natural Resources Training Institute
PAME	Participatory Assessment, Monitoring and Evaluation (FAO)
PB	Participatory Baseline
PCP	Pilot Community Plantation
PRA	Participatory Rural Appraisal
RGGB	Royal Government of Bhutan
RNR-RC	Renewable Natural Resources- Research Centre
RRA	Rapid Rural Appraisal
SDC	Swiss Development Corporation
SE	Social Forestry, defined as in Wiersum (1999)
Sikshing	Forest land used for leaf litter collection (Dz.)
TEDP	Third Forestry Development Program
Thram	Land/cadastral record (Dz.)
Tsandro	Communal grazing land/pasture (Dz.)
Tshokpa	Village representative/leader (Dz.)
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WB	World Bank

1.1 Country Background and Location

The Kingdom of Bhutan, or Dru Ü, the Land of the Thunder Dragon as it is called by the inhabitants, is a small landlocked country in the Eastern Himalayas in Asia. In the North it is bordered by Chinese-occupied Tibet, in the East by the Indian state of Arunachal Pradesh, in the South by the Indian states of Assam and West Bengal, and in the West by the Indian state of Sikkim. The cultural identity and social organisation of the country are based upon a system of norms and values finding its' origins in a unique absorption of the traditional animist beliefs (referred to as Bön) by the Tantrayana Buddhism introduced from Tibet in the 8th century AD by the Indian Saint Guru Padmasambhava. Greatly influenced by this system the people of Bhutan have always kept a way of life that remains closely connected to the natural environment they live in, resulting in an almost virgin natural environment with one of the highest biodiversities in the world. This system has also preserved a rich cultural and religious heritage (National Environment Secretariat, 1992).

It is this natural and cultural variety that the country has cherished and fiercely defended over the centuries. For long the country remained isolated from developments taking place in other parts of the world. The 20th century however has seen great changes in the political, economical and social situation of the country. Despite the developments that have taken place and that have changed the country so much, a quote from the present King Jigme Singye Wangchuck has been the guideline for all development policies over the years: "We will not sacrifice our Gross National Happiness for a higher Gross National Product".

This is a very courageous stand, especially when taken by an underdeveloped country. In practice this implies that all development activities are only executed if they comply with the preservation of Bhutan's cultural identity, the preservation of the natural environment and the continuation along the path of sustainable development, as described in the environmental document called "The Middle Path". Thus Bhutan has become one of the few countries where a sustainable development has been successfully implemented over the years.

Fig. 1: Geographical location of Bhutan (National Environment Secretariat, 1992).

Bhutan has been a sovereign country at least since the 8th century AD. Internal strifes divided the country for many centuries. The advent of Zhabdrung Ngawang Namgyal in 1616 AD from Tibet unified the country to a large extent and strengthened its position. The urge to protect the nature and culture of the country resulted in a self-imposed isolation for many centuries. Thus the country remained closed to foreign powers, with as only exception the age-old religious, economic and cultural ties with Tibet and the trade with Indian states to the South. In 1865, after a border war, Bhutan established diplomatic relations with British India. This did not lead to a significantly more open international policy. Only after the hostile invasion and take-over of Tibet by the Chinese in 1951 did the Bhutanese realise that opening up was the only way to maintain its sovereignty. As counter balance to big neighbour China, Bhutan strengthened ties with India. Till date the relation between the two countries has remained very close (Department of Education, 1991).

On December 17th, 1907, the first hereditary monarch of Bhutan, Sir Ugyen Wangchuck, ascended the throne. A process of careful internal stabilisation, nation building and development started that continues till date. Until the reign of the third King, Jigme Dorji Wangchuck, the country remained in a situation comparable to that of feudal Europe during the Middle Ages. It can be attributed to this far-sighted ruler, and his son the present King Jigme Singye Wangchuck, that Bhutan started to tread the path of modernisation. They realised that, for Bhutan to maintain its sovereignty, a strong government and strong international ties were needed (Wangchuck, 1997). In 1971 Bhutan became a full member state of the United Nations. Other international organisations were joined as well, and since then Bhutan has played a quiet but at times unique role in the international developments (Tshering, 1999).

In due course of time political reform were put through, such as the establishment of the National Assembly with representatives of the monastic body, the government and the people in 1953. In 1959 a written codifix of laws, the Thrimzhung Chhenmo was introduced (Tshering, 1999). It was followed by a process of decentralisation of the governmental responsibilities towards the districts (*dzongkhag*) and further to village level, the establishment of an independent judicial system, and finally the limitation of the power of the King in favour of the National Assembly and the Council of Ministers in 1998, with the possibility of a vote of confidence being posed in the King. In one of the coming years this process will be further enhanced through the introduction of a written constitution, the preparation of which has been ordered by the King in 2001. The constitution will be a uniquely Bhutanese one, incorporating many cultural and religious elements as well (Kinga, 2002). Although in the western sense of the word Bhutan can not be considered a democracy, in practice it functions more like it than many a democracy elsewhere.

The 781,800 people (World Bank Group, 2000) of Bhutan can be roughly divided in three ethnic groups, the Ngalong (Ngalop), of Tibeto-Mongol origin, in the Western and Central parts of the country, the Sharchokpa of Tibeto-Burman origin in the East and the Lhotshampa (Nepali), of Indo-Aryan origin in the South. In the social field many reforms have taken place since the hereditary monarchy was established. They are an integral part of the Five Year Plans (FYPs). The educational and health systems are undergoing continuous development, being made free of costs to all citizens, raising life expectancy from 47 in the 1960s to 66 in the 1990s and quickly reducing illiteracy, with an adult literacy rate of 46% (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000). An equal distribution of the modernisation across the country is one of the main targets, thus raising the living standards of the entire population and curbing the urbanisation trends (Tshering, 1999, Department of Education, 1991)

Besides the political and social reforms the economy was developed as well. Agriculture, being the main source of income for the majority of the population (around 85%, Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2000), has always had a high priority in the FYPs that were started in 1961. The FYPs provide a five-year layout of the development plans. In the consecutive FYPs (currently the 9th) the agricultural, livestock and natural resource sectors were modernised, a national airport and roads were build connecting Bhutan with the outside world as well as connecting different valleys, providing the infrastructure for accelerated development. Moreover the nation's potential for the generation of hydropower electricity was developed, providing the means for development in other sectors as well as generating income through the export of excess energy to India. Another important source of foreign revenue is the tourism sector. Through the principle of 'low numbers high revenues' the flux of tourists is limited to a mere 6,000 well-off foreigners per year. The manufacturing and industrial sector, which are mainly natural resource-based have remained relatively small. Privatisation policies and the introduction of clean technologies are the ways the development of these sectors is stimulated. In the services sector, the Royal Government is still the largest employer (Ministry of Planning, 1996), with 13,500 civil servants (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2000).

Bhutan has a total GDP of Nu. 18,202 million at 2000 prices, which equalled US\$ 396,990,185/-¹ and a GDP per capita of Nu. 28,606.3/- which is approximately equivalent to US\$ 624/- (Kucnscl, 2000). Bhutan is ranked the 125th position on the Human Development Index (HDI) according to latest data, well ahead of neighbouring countries like India and Bangladesh (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2000). Even though Bhutan is classified as Low Income Food Deficit Country, poverty and hunger are virtually unknown and apart from food grains Bhutan is almost self sufficient (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2000). Notwithstanding all these developments, including a growing GDP of 5.8% in 1998, (Central Statistical Organisation, 1999) and 5.9% in 1999 (Kuensel 2000) and an increasing self-sufficiency, foreign aid remains the main means of closing the gap between government expenditures and revenues (+/- US\$ 53 million, Central Statistical Organisation, 1999). India has by far remained the main contributor to the development process, but other countries and international organisations provide technical and financial support as well.

1.2 Rationale for the Study and Central Aim

After four years of study and a thesis in Environmental Economics at Wageningen University, it was thought that a change of perspective might have a refreshing influence. With a second minor thesis still to be done, the choice fell on Forest- and Nature Conservation Policy, and more specifically Social and Community Forestry. Interest in this topic had been there for a long time, and was strengthened during different courses within the environmental economics program at university which, mainly as optional subject of reports to be written, touched on the subject. The location of study was also quickly determined, as the previous research in Bhutan had left a lasting positive impression of the country and the people. After consultation with the supervisor, Dr. Ir. K.F. Wiersum as well as with counterparts in and from Bhutan, and based upon the knowledge acquired during the Forestry and rural development course, the general topic of the research was decided to become an evaluation of social forestry interventions in Bhutan. Within a relatively short time-span, this broad topic had to be refined to result in a workable problem definition and research questions.

¹ US\$ = Nu.47.50

The central aim of this research is "to evaluate social forestry interventions in Bhutan from the perspective of the local community that is participating in the project". With the help of the outcome of this aim, it is expected that a contribution can be made towards the issue raised in the problem statement.

1.3 Problem statement

As the aim of the research described above is very broad, it had to be transformed into a more practically applicable and specified problem statement. Based on discussions with Dr. Ir. K.F. Wiersum and the available literature this problem statement and consequent research objectives and questions were developed.

In many countries that started SF interventions long before it was commenced in Bhutan, a non-convergence in objectives between the local community and the project/government have been observed (viz. Chapter 2.3).

The problem definition thus has been stated as:

"Considering that a non-convergence in objectives in social forestry interventions has been observed in many projects, is such too the case in Bhutan, i.e., do the objectives that the local communities have differ from those of the project, and to what extent are these local objectives being met?"

1.4 Research Objectives

Since the inception of SF in Bhutan in 1979, the focus has mainly been on seedling distribution for planting in private and communal lands. The government provided the land, technical assistance, free fencing, labour wages and the seedlings. However these projects often failed and a lot of government funds were wasted. The government subsequently blamed the community for negligence (Wangchuk, 1995). Since then the SF activities have changed in focus, with eastern Bhutan a forerunner in more participatory projects. The objective of this research is to see whether these projects really did include local objectives better in the project objectives right from the planning phase. This research will first try to find out what were the initial expectations of the local people. Secondly, to what extent these expectations have been fulfilled. After that the main reasons for the successes and failures in meeting the objectives will be identified, after which recommendations can be made towards guiding other projects. In this evaluation process a participatory approach will be taken, as the people themselves are in the best position to decide what they want to see evaluated. They are the ultimate judges of the changes taking place in their community as a result of the development intervention.

1.5 Research Questions

The following research questions were designed in order to guide the fieldwork. However they were not strictly applied, in the sense that much room was left for local people to express their own opinions (viz. Chapter 3.2 and 3.4).

1. What are the objectives of the national social forestry program? From which more general policies are these derived? What are the objectives of the social forestry component of the Third Forestry Development Project in eastern Bhutan? Has there been any significant change in the objectives of government and project? These objectives are described in Chapter 5.
2. What were the objectives or expectations of the community members when they decided to sign up to the social forestry program regarding (e.g.) inputs (easier access to technical and financial support and information), outputs (increased availability of forest resources), management and responsibility (increased decision-making power over the forest resources)? To what extent have these objectives been met or not? Have their objectives been adjusted during the project time, and if so, in what direction? These local objectives are described in Chapter 6.
 - What were the objectives to join the project regarding the expectations of inputs? Which inputs did the community members expect to receive from the project's side, and which inputs did they expect to have to bring in themselves? Examples of inputs can be: land, tree saplings, labour, financial capital for running (management) expenditures, organisation etc.
 - What were the objectives to join the project regarding the expectations of outputs? Which outputs were the local participants expecting to be able to get from the forest, during which time of the year, and in which quantities? What were their expectations towards contribution to their subsistence living as well as sale of the forest produce?
 - What were the objectives to join the project regarding (management) responsibility? What activities were they expecting they could undertake themselves, and which activities would be undertaken by the project facilitators? Were they satisfied with this power division?
3. In which way have external and local objectives been absorbed in the management plans and implementation of the projects? Is there a non-convergence between local and external objectives which becomes apparent in the implementation of the project? What can be identified as the main factors that influence success and failure in the social forestry interventions in eastern Bhutan? What are the implications and recommendations that can be distilled from this research for running SF projects in Bhutan as well as for new ones? These issues are discussed in Chapter 7.

1.6 Thesis Layout

Chapter 2 will provide the theoretical background to this research. First a general description of Social Forestry as a means to increase participation of local people in forest management activities will be given. After that professional and local forest management will be described. The focus then turns to normative pluriformity of objectives within SF interventions, the resulting non-convergence that has been observed between external and local objectives, the implications that has for the functioning of the projects, and the application of this theoretical background in the Bhutanese context that this research attempts to do. Chapter 3 will provide the research framework and methodology with a description of participatory methods for data collection, the method of selection of the study areas and the methods used at the different study sites. In Chapter 4 the background and context of the research will be given. The chapter includes a description of the (social) forestry sector in Bhutan and the policies and legislation. It then turns attention to the development and status of SF in eastern Bhutan and will provide a descriptive and historical overview of the four research locations. Chapter 5 and 6 will constitute the most important part of the research, with Chapter 5 describing the government and project objectives of SF as answer to research question 1, and Chapter 6 a detailed description of the objectives of the local community as answer to research question 2. Chapter 7 finally will end with conclusions regarding the problem statement of non-convergence, a discussion to what extent the local and external objectives have been integrated in the management plans, and the factors that affect success and failure in the various locations. The report will lastly come up with some recommendations regarding social forestry interventions in Bhutan as a whole and with respect to individual sites.

2.1 Participation in Forest Management: Social Forestry

"The participation of the local community is the key to the conservation and utilisation of forest resources" - His Majesty King Jigme Singye Wangchuk in the Royal Command of January 1979.

Until the early 1970s most forestry projects in developing countries were founded on an industrial paradigm for forestry development, in which the benefits of government resource management were expected to naturally reach the local people. This changed in the mid-1970s when it turned out that this approach did not work. The subsequent focus on the fuelwood shortage resulted mainly in plantations. In the mid-1980s however the shortcomings of this approach also became visible. The social complexity of the rural areas was not sufficiently recognised and thus the benefits did not reach those most in need (MacCall Skutsch, 1983, 1987). Moreover the view that local people were the enemies of the natural forests had developed in response to rapid deforestation (Eckholm, 1976). Lastly many governments realised that the staff requirements for forest protection were becoming too high and expensive (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). Thus many governments realised that there was no other option than to embark on programmes to involve villagers as active partners with the government in the protection, planning, management, utilisation and development of forest resources. The Social Forestry (SF) as it now exists and still develops came into existence (more background information on the development of SF: viz. Arnold, 1999; Bartlett, 1992; Fisher, 1995; Gilmour and King, 1989; Gilmour, 1995; Hobley, 1996; International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development, 1996; Sarin, 1995; Shah, 1996; Wiersum, 1996, 1999a). This development however has not lead to a change from a top-down to a bottom-up approach, but to a more even-sided approach, in which the main partners of development have a more even standing, combining and sharing technical knowledge, scientific systems and outside resources with local knowledge, systems and resources (Messerschmidt et al., 2000).

Social forestry (SF) interventions can be defined as *"forestry policies designed and implemented by professional foresters and development organisations with the aim of stimulating active involvement of local people in small scale diversified forest management activities as a means to improve the livelihood conditions of these people"* (Wiersum, 1999a). In other words, they can be seen as attempts to stimulate community forestry (CF), or *"any management practices executed by local communities not professionally trained in forestry as part of their livelihood strategies"* (Wiersum, 1999a). It can thus also be described as people-oriented forestry or people-driven forestry, dealing with understanding the relationship between the forest ecosystem and human social and cultural systems, taking them fully into account in planning, implementation and management. It includes several varieties of community forestry, designs and techniques for private forestry (including agroforestry); small scale forest enterprises and industries; and institutional forestry (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). The general objectives of SF programmes are to promote an active involvement of local people; addressing their needs to enhance living conditions through efficient utilisation and protection of forest biomass and related resources; to build on indigenous knowledge and traditional practices of forest management; and to use an extension dialogue for two-way learning and teaching, to establish true dialogue and partnership between outsiders and the local population.

2.2 Local and Professional Forest Management

Over the ages, mainly through trial-and-error, local communities have developed a wide variety of locally unique common forest resource management systems (see Messerschmidt et al., 1993). With the increased importance given to scientific, western forest management practices and the nationalisation of many forest resources all around the world, including Bhutan, these local practices have slowly but steadily disappeared (Norbu, 1993). With local communities losing control over their immediate forest resources and professional management practices put in place, many traditional and indigenous management systems have gone lost (Wangchuk, 1998). However after the realisation that professional management practices are not always suitable for SF interventions, and with the failure of many of these practices (such as the planting of exotic species), an increased attention has again been turned to the local management systems.

Forest management traditions are based on traditional (indigenous¹) ecological knowledge, and with Bhutan's strong environmental ethic derived from Buddhism, local knowledge and traditions are worthy of understanding and respect (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). Bhutanese villagers are well aware of the natural resources that their ancestors have traditionally used. However the existence of 'formal' social structures for managing and sustaining them as 'indigenous systems' is less evident- it has not been well studied and documented in Bhutan. Nonetheless, experience (Messerschmidt et al., 2000) has made clear that local people understand the benefits of group tenure and management of the resource, and the value of site enhancement measures. They also recognise the gradual degradation of forest resources in some areas; hence the keen interest in SF practices.

Reasoning in the line of Gilmour (1990), Gilmour and Fisher (1991) and Hobley (1996) the relative abundance and accessibility of forest resources in eastern Bhutan has led to a less obvious and weaker development of indigenous forest management systems. One such practice which is still in existence in some places is that of *ridam*, which assures protection of forest and mountain resources. It follows locally distinct and explicit rules restricting human access to specified forests during certain seasons of the year (for example, Tcmphel et al., 1998). Mostly these periods of 'dam' (restriction, prohibition) coincide with the most vulnerable months for tree and plant growth as well as young wildlife. At the same time it is also during the busiest agricultural season, the harvest season, thus focusing villager attention solely on those activities. The local belief is that when *ridam* is broken, the local deities will cause damage to the agricultural crops. The practice of *ridam* has rapidly degraded after the introduction of the permit system for harvesting of forest products. The fact that people from outside the community could now enter the forest at any time discouraged the locals from following the closure themselves too. Thus in many cases, the threat from outside is an overriding reason for local communities to participate in SF projects. This is shown in examples from Yakpugang and Masang Daza CFs, Mongar (Department of Forest Services, 2001a, 2002, see also Box 1). Perceptions of threat could therefore well be included in the model by Gilmour and Fisher (1991).

Another example of indigenous knowledge can be found in Annex D. The community members of Dozam CF from the hamlet of Shaphangma observed a duality in the growth of seedlings after lemon grass harvesting, in which a set of interrelations between lemon grass harvesting, cattle grazing and seedlings growth was described.

¹ As Fisher, 1989, states it, "traditional implies a degree of antiquity, something old, whereas indigenous implies something originating from within a community, but not necessarily old".

Box 1: CFMP preparation meeting, Masang Daza, Saleng geog, Mongar Dzongkhag: local forest management and protecting a forest under threat (Department of Forestry, 2002).

Under the TFDP funding, budget was available for establishment of another CFMU in Eastern Bhutan. One of the sites selected was Masang Daza village in Saleng geog, Mongar dzongkhag. From 11th till 18th March 2002 the TFDP together with Divisional and Dzongkhag Forest staff conducted a series of community meetings and field visits in order to write and discuss the draft CFMP and make an inventory of the site.

Due to obligations elsewhere and transportation problems the site could only be visited on March 18th, the day that the team returned to Mongar/Khangma. However some discussions were held with Mr. Dhono from TFDP and Mr. Shaha, Mongar FEO. The draft CFMP (Department of Forestry Services) was also obtained, but being a draft version not yet approved by the Director of Forests it is deemed unfit to refer to any of the information in the draft.

The name Masang (deity) Daza, applying to both the forest area as well as the village located nearby, is derived from the deity that previously inhabited the broad-leaved forest. It was believed that whoever accessed the forest would be taken by the deity, thus enforcing a total access ban. Sometime the last century, the previous reincarnation of Geduen Lama (now in Bumthang Ura) built a chorten in the vicinity of the forest in order to subdue the deity (possibly upon villager request and in response to a greater demand for products from the forest). However, open access to the forest and its products was still out of the question, as this would result in hailstones and heavy rainfall seriously damaging the area. The traditional belief of the presence of the deity has thus ensured a sustainable utilisation of the forest till date. The village elders however expressed fear that with the changing times and outside encroachment this traditional system might be rendered defunct, endangering the provision of the daily necessities from the forest to the villagers.

Considering the enthusiasm of the local people in protecting their forest resources from future degradation by insiders and especially outsiders, it would be very rewarding for them if the forest were handed over to them under the FNCR (2000). They expressed special fears that their forest resources might be affected in the future due to resettlement of people in the government reserved forest. Their hope is that, by changing the status of the forest into a community forest, the resources will be protected well into the future from encroachment by outsiders, with or without permission of the government. Not only do they thus display a long-term vision of protection and sustaining the forest they depend on, but also a great trust in that the government will not change the rules and the status of the CF in the future. Another striking feature was the fact that a number of female villagers were the fiercest in expressing the need for protection, claiming that they were the ones most directly involved with the forest.

Fig. 2: Participatory forest mapping during Masang Daza CFMG meeting.

Professional Forest Management (PFM) pertains to management of forest resources by people, often in government service or as part of a project, who have undergone (more or less) professional training to do so. The aim of those trainings and PFM itself most commonly relates to silvicultural aspects of forestry. The main objectives here are forest conservation and/or extraction of timber and other forest products for commercial purposes. Thus it becomes obvious that within the framework of SF, PFM itself is not conducive for reaching the SF objectives, mainly the objectives of assuring a sustainable supply of timber and non-timber forest products for local people and increasing the participation in forest management activities.

It therefore has become widely accepted that for SF the roles of professional forest managers have to change from 'protectors' to 'facilitators' (Messerschmidt et al., 2000; Vergera, 1984). Modern forestry strives to achieve the so-called 'consultant forester/facilitator model' which represents a great change from previous top-down forestry development approaches and it reflects an important recent development role reversal also noted in agriculture and animal husbandry (Chambers, 1983, 1985, 1993). This model has also been chosen in Bhutan, where the Department of Forestry Services provides a facilitating role through the Forestry Extension Division.

In many cases the SF projects in eastern Bhutan have built on the indigenous knowledge and traditional practices (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). It has been attempted to build local institutional structures on the foundations of existing systems, and thus be truly innovative. However, the extent, nature and purposes of indigenous systems of resource management are not well understood nor documented yet. Research in this field is therefore a priority.

2.3 Normative Pluriformity and Non-convergence in Local and External Objectives

As with every plan or project, SF interventions have their *objectives* and their *actors*. These objectives can be distinguished between the two main actor groups, i.e. the *policy objectives* for stimulating community forestry and the *local objectives* of the community which is expected to execute the related management practices. The policy objectives are often predetermined by the government and development agencies. They often include bringing a halt to deforestation and protection/increase in the forest cover by stimulating effective forest management (Fisher, 1995; Gilmour, 1995). Arnold (1991) also mentions that each of the actor categories in social forestry has different perceptions and aspirations in respect to the needs for forest management. Among the many lessons learnt from the early community forestry initiatives was that households and external planners did not share a common vision of needs and priorities (Wiersum 1999b; MacCall Skutsch, 1983; Kartasubrata and Wiersum, 1993; Gilmour and King, 1989). The objective of community forestry was often the (government and other external agencies') aim of preservation of forests rather than serving as a strategy for not only reaching these conservation objectives but also providing direct and indirect benefits for communities that would support rural development. It was not that there was a lack of concern for well being of rural communities, but that the primary focus was on environmental concerns (Arnold, 1998). It was often erroneously assumed that the problem perception of the government and project were similar to that of the local people (Rao, 1992) which in turn led to a poor fit between the needs of the community and the nature of the services proposed by the government and project (Korten, 1983). There was an externally derived imposition of objectives, priorities and definition of needs that often did not reflect the needs of communities and the local realities. The question

is, whether the values, perspectives and practical knowledge embedded in professional forest management can be made compatible with those of local communities. This is a key issue that Messerschmidt et al. (2000) also would like to see addressed.

To answer this question, Wiersum (1999b) has analysed the origins of these different perspectives on (sustainable) forest management. Firstly, both professional foresters and local communities have different perspectives on forest resources and attach different values to the forest functions. Secondly, there are a broad variety of forest types under community management, ranging on an evolutionary continuum from natural forest to tree plantations, a fact often not recognised by professional foresters. And lastly, there is a wide variety in indigenous as well as professional forest management practices. This results in a normative pluriformity in perceptions, ideas, objectives and expectations towards forest management and thus social forestry interventions.

Sarin (1995) also remarks that even *within* local communities, individual actors have different objectives depending on their socio-economic and cultural status. These different objectives are the result of social diversity, or the inevitable variation that exists within human society in the form of roles, values, status and economic stratification, and their culturally-defined expectations (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). So whilst professional foresters working in a SF project have objectives different than those of the local community, also within the community the objectives might also differ. Therefore, there is no single clear-cut aim or objective. The recognition of this social diversity and the resulting objectives has been proven globally to be of vital importance of success (Messerschmidt et al., 2000, Ingles and Gilmour, 1989).

2.4 Implications of Non-convergence

The lack in congruence between policy objectives and local objectives of SF interventions has been observed in most SF projects in different parts of the world. Whereas the SF interventions in India had initially as main policy objective to protect forests, it was later increasingly recognised that forests greatly contributed to the livelihoods of forest-dependant people. Their local objectives of better and more equitable access to the forest resources were increasingly incorporated in the SF programs. In many cases however, it was noted that the most disadvantaged societal groups did not see many improvements in their position (Wiersum, 1996b; Skutsch, 1987). Shamu (2000) recognises this as a weak point in the Indian Joint Forest Management program. He attributes it to various factors, most notable 'a lack of attention for the local socio-economic and cultural value system', 'an inadequacy in meaningful people's participation' and 'a donor- and target-driven rather than a need-driven and need-oriented approach'. Rastogi (1999) also states that "the pluralist values, perceptions, objectives and interests must be acknowledged, now that people's participation has become a *sine quo non*".

Similar experiences have been reported from Nepal (Bartlett, 1991, 1992; Bartlett and Nurse, 1991, 1992; Bartlett et al., 1993; Malla, 1996; Beuving, 1998; Soussan et al., 1991). Malla (1996) for example attributes the limited positive impact of CF in Nepal on the livelihoods of the rural people to a too strong focus on the environmental objectives of the project and policy makers, rather than the developmental objectives of the rural people. Melkama and Bisht (2000) have expressed an increased need for attention to local people's perceptions. Uphoff (1986) states that apart from their physical characteristics, how resources are perceived by their users is an important consideration. Gregersen, Draper and Elz (1989) agree that the success of SF interventions often depends on the desires and perceptions of the local people. Ingles and Gilmour (1989) report that in a CF project in the Middle Hills of

Nepal the members of the user group are not a homogenous group. They have different objectives in forest management as well as differing interests in participating in the process. The differing objectives the user groups had regarding the forest management made the negotiating process more difficult.

2.5 Application in Bhutan

In Bhutan, detailed research into these different perspectives on SF has, due to the quite recent inception of the projects, not yet taken place. However it can be expected that, as in other parts of the world, there will be differences in objectives between the participants in the project at the one end, and the government and other outside agencies at the other. SF interventions have often been initiated and led by the DFS of the government and external donor and development organisations. Many of the projects have had the aims of these external initiators to a large extent overriding those of the local people. This however does not imply that these local people did not have expectations regarding improvement of their situation, otherwise they would not have joined in the first place. To reveal these objectives of the local people is one of the research action fields identified during a workshop on social forestry, in 1992 (Department of Forestry, 1993).

In the early years after the inception of SF in Bhutan in 1979, the projects mainly focussed on seedling distribution for planting in private and communal lands. The government provided everything from land and seedlings to technical assistance, free fencing and even labour wages. These projects often failed and cost the government a lot of money. The government blamed the community for negligence. However, on hindsight the failure can be explained by many factors, mainly boiling down to a lack of congruence between the objectives of the government and those of the local people. Wangchuk (1995) did his research against this background of less commitment by local communities in protecting and maintaining community woodlots, and aimed at identifying the factors affecting local participation in CF.

A number of factors were identified, ranging from local level socio-economic circumstances to political commitment at government level. However, as fundamental to supportive local action to a government initiated development programme it was concluded that there should be a shared problem perception between government at one hand and the local community at the other, as well as a shared problem perception among the community members themselves. The fact that community forestry programmes were not very successful indicates that *"there exists a gap of mutual understanding between the government and the local people. In other words, there may have been a lack of understanding on the part of the government about the people's needs, problems and perceptions in relation to forest products. What the government wanted to achieve with CF programmes may not have been in accordance with the local perception"* (Wangchuk, 1995:3).

As problems he identified first and foremost the fact that forestry extension has not been successful in creating a mutual understanding between the government and the local people. Most farmers were not aware of the objectives of CF, the government policies, rules and regulations, and thus saw the CF as just another government plantation. A second problem he observed was the heterogeneity of some communities, resulting in failure since they could not work together, and the homogeneity of other communities together with a strong leadership leading to success. A third problem was the absence of a clearly perceived need for or shortage of forest products. As fourth problem he states the lack of economic benefits and as last the distance to the village (long distance meaning less protection).

He concludes that homogeneity of the community, participatory surveys (learning about needs and problems of local people as they see and perceive them) and forestry extension (making local people aware of new forestry practices that may address their forest-related needs and problems) could contribute to creation and maintenance of a common problem perception among the involved parties. In order to enhance local participation in community forestry, there is a need for outside planners and foresters to become aware of how local people define community forestry and share in their needs and expectations. To this end it is recommended that a common problem perception at different levels is institutionalised to strengthen the bond of mutual understanding between government and local community.

This research will more or less follow up on the research done by Wangchuk in 1995. It aims at seeing to what extent the gap between government/project and local objectives has been closed and whether the situation has improved compared to 1995.

Chapter 3

Research Framework and Methodology

3.1 Assumptions and Framework

A number of assumptions lie at the basis of this research. These assumptions are (adapted from Wangchuk, 1995):

- Both community and government have a certain problem perception: what is the problem, its extent, seriousness, and how can it be solved?
- These perceptions for forestry related problems would lead to certain objectives for SF interventions: how can SF contribute to solving the problem, and what do they want to achieve with SF?
- If the government and the community share a common problem perception, they will also have corresponding objectives for SF.
- If the government and local people have the same problem perception and objectives for SF, the subsequent actions they take will lead to co-operation and success.
- Wherever the problem perception and consequent objectives for SF between government and community differ too much, the actions from either or both sides will conflict and lead to a failure of the project.

The problem perception and objectives for the social forestry intervention from the external side (government/project) are explained in Chapter 5. The problem perception and objectives of the local community are described in Chapter 6. In Chapter 7 an analysis is made whether these two groups of objectives are similar to such an extent that there is a common problem perception and common objectives for social forestry. This in turn would lead to co-operation during the implementation of the technical and organisational forest management activities and thus to success.

3.2 Participatory Approaches

For long, direct involvement of the local target groups in SF interventions for stimulating CF was not common practice (Oltheter, 1995). Their participation remained limited to the planning phase, after which the operational aspect often turned out to be a surprise with unexpected results. Now however participation is seen as a prerequisite for sustainable development, and in the words of Oltheter a shift has taken place from "we want them to take part in what we do" to "we want to support them in achieving their goals". Davis-Case (1989) already referred to this shift. In all project phases the use of participatory methods and tools is advocated, with as goals the empowerment of local disadvantaged groups, the integration of local knowledge systems into project design, the development of a two-way learning process between the project and local people, and achieving political commitment and support.

The first major steps in this direction were taken in 1985 when the FAO published its' Forestry Paper No. 60 on the monitoring and evaluation of participatory forestry projects. Not only the environment/protective objectives of the outside agencies, but also the rural development objectives of the local people were taken into account in the evaluation process. The term Participatory Monitoring and Evaluation (PME) was coined for a method to chart the progress of project implementation towards the achievement of objectives, to assess the relevance, efficiency and effectiveness of the projects and its impact on the environment and the participants, and to serve as a lesson and guidance for planning future projects.

The PAME (Participatory Assessment, Monitoring and Evaluation) approach was born in 1989 and first described in detail in Community Forestry Note No. 2 by Davis-Case (1989). It is "a combination of a concept, backed by participatory methods and tools for information gathering, and encourages, supports and strengthens communities' existing abilities to identify their own needs and objectives and then monitor and evaluate to adjust these within the project time frame". It is a "combination between outsider and insider knowledge". The primary focus is on the information need of the communities, whereas the information need of the project only has a secondary position. The work by Davis-Case (1989) differentiates between Community Problem Analysis (CPA), Participatory Baselines (PB), Participatory Monitoring and ongoing evaluation (PMoe) and Participatory Evaluation Events (PEE).

Within the PAME framework some of the tools advocated for use in PRA¹ and RRA² are being used. Oltheter (1995) and Chambers (1992) also advocate the use of mix of tools derived from the RRA-PRA continuum. Whereas RRA is useful for initial data collection and a first assessment of general opportunities and constraints as well as to establish a working relationship between the community and the project, PRA can be used for complimentary information collection and participatory assessment. More on methods of monitoring and evaluation of community forestry projects can be found in Bhattarai and Campbell (1982, 1984), Dembner (1986), Melkania and Bisht (2000), Prasad (2000), Soussan et al. (1991) and Smith, (1996). More on the theory and tools of participatory techniques in general and applied to community forestry can be found in Jackson and Ingles (1995, 1998), Molnar (1989), Davis-Case (1989, 1990), Messerschmidt (1995), Food and Agriculture Organisation (1985), Bartlett and Nurse (1991), Bruce (1989), Chambers (1992), Oltheter (1995), and Thompson (1994). Examples of application of these tools in Bhutan can be found in Gyeltshen et al.

¹ Oltheter (1995): "a process-oriented method that enables local people to conduct their own analysis".

² Molnar (1989): "a creative, structured use of a particular set of investigative tools for assessing a situation, topic, problem or sector on the short term".

(1994), Maier (1996), Basnet et al. (1995a, b), Norbu (1992), Messerschmidt et al. (2000) and Wangdi et al. (1996).

In this research the basic principles of PAME were applied during the fieldwork. Experiences from previous researches executed wholly or in part with the use of participatory tools for evaluating social forestry interventions teach a number of lessons and precautions in their application and suitability for different purposes. In their application a few things have to be determined.

Firstly, it has to be determined which kind of data will be collected. For the practical application a conscious choice has to be made whether to use predetermined evaluation criteria and consecutive questions or whether to construct a number of general questions as guidelines to the interviews. Prasad (2000) states that taking many criteria calls for assigning weights, which makes the evaluation process unnecessarily difficult. Smith (1996) applies a number of evaluation criteria taken from MacConnell (1992) in evaluating the performance of different forest management systems in Java. Soussan et al. (1991), in their evaluation of a community forestry project in Nepal based on the projects' objectives, compare the actual implementation of the project from an institutional point of view to the projects guiding principles. They mention a number of evaluation questions on which they base their criteria for evaluation. These criteria are meant to judge whether the used approach is effective, sustainable and will lead to improvements in the quality of lives of the local people.

The second issue pertains to how these data are going to be collected and from whom (the methodology). As method of data collection Smith (1996) used a literature review to get the initial data, after which the more specific data were obtained from participation, observation and semi-structured open-ended interviewing. These research techniques however did not only focus on the evaluation criteria, but other issues were discussed as well. As such there was found to be a discrepancy between the chosen evaluation criteria in the research method and the research techniques. As evaluation methodology Soussan et al. (1991) used existing literature, discussion with the involved staff and officials at various levels of the project, and the results of an extensive programme of rapid appraisal fieldwork. This last RA consisted of individual and group interviews of households, interviews with key informants, and an assessment of the community forest area. Although the authors call it a 'participatory community forest appraisal', the attached form to be used in the appraisal has a very formal nature, and seems to be more of a checklist, the questions of which all have to be answered and that's it. The same can be said of the question list by Beuving (1998). The method Beuving (1998) applied was mostly open-ended conversations that were not recorded to get a broad overview and semi-structured interviews and open-ended conversations with a topic list as backup to get more detailed information. These last interviews were recorded. Key respondents were purposely selected based on a person's position, specialised activities, presence during the period of fieldwork and general interest and willingness to participate. General respondents were selected on basis of social position. Awang (1997) used an interactive research approach, in which data collection and analysis were done in the setting and in which knowledge is used and people were involved in the exploration of ideas, rather than doing research on people. Open discussions in an informal setting were the starting point, with more structured interviews among randomly sampled participants and key informants towards the end.

Thirdly there is the question of social and technical factors such as the relation with the respondents, the timing of the interview and the presence of a translator/interpreter. Smith (1996) realised that his lack of knowledge of the local language was an important shortcoming as now he relied on external translators, often from the government, which might

have biased the responses. Some of his practical guidelines (viz. also Casley and Kumar, 1987, 1988) when conducting this type of interview were: to make initial contact in an informal manner, use understandable formulation, keep a neutral attitude, and record the interview. An interesting outcome was, that though the interview method had that liberty, the questions neither their sequence were often changed. Beuving (1998) also encountered problems in Nepal when relying on external translators, because they were not able to probe in detail into the answers of the respondents.

From these previous experiences a few things were learnt. In the research no evaluation criteria were used to keep the evaluation as simple and participatory as possible. A number of general research questions were developed which were used as guiding lines during the semi-structured, open-ended group, individual and key informant interviews. These interviews were recorded and reviewed later since especially during group interviews important remarks tended to get lost in the discussion. Information obtained from the available literature and from key informant interviews with project and government extension staff was used during the interviews as well. Another lesson from the reviewed researches was that it is beneficial if the researcher knows the local language. In this case, the author having an intermediate command of both Dzongkha, the national language, as well as the predominant language in eastern Bhutan, Sharchokpakha, was a clear advantage. Then the timing of the fieldwork is also important. When farmers are interviewed, they have to be present and available for that purpose. Conducting the research in winter, or the agricultural slack season, has been a deliberate choice as to assure maximum co-operation. Moreover, the winter holidays will mean that a great number of students will have returned to their villages thus increasing the number of possible respondents, who also have a command of English to facilitate interviewing and possible translation work. Lastly, the author's previous visit to Bhutan has resulted in a better knowledge of local customs and traditions, which made acceptance by the local community easier. This also resulted in easier access to respondents.

3.3 Selection of the Study Areas

Upon arrival in Bhutan, it was found that the number of sites in eastern Bhutan where social forestry interventions had been implemented was rather limited. Until the end of 2000, the approved and implemented sites in the six eastern dzongkhag of Lhuentse, Mongar, Trashigang, Trashi Yangtse, Pema Gatsel and Samdrup Jongkhar numbered only 6, one in Lhuentse, one in Mongar, two in Trashigang, and two in Trashi Yangtse. The thesis research focussed on four of the six dzongkhag that receive technical, financial and logistical assistance by the Third Forestry Development Project (TFDP) under a Nu. 234.810 million fund by WB/SDC running from 1997-2002. This project has its head office located at the RNR-RC at Khangma in Trashigang Dzongkhag, eastern Bhutan. The TFDP has adopted a multiple use management of forests; has a social forestry component including the financing of NTFPs and related livelihoods; and involves the rural community in managing the forests and improving the farm output in tree planting on private lands (Banerjee et al., 1997).

The four dzongkhag in question are Lhuentse, Mongar, Trashigang and Trashi Yangtse. Two of the six eastern dzongkhag, namely Pema Gatsel and Samdrup Jongkhar, have been excluded due to the currently tense situation in southeastern Bhutan as a result of the continued presence of Indian militants.

Given the fact that four sites would be chosen, one each in one of the four eastern dzongkhag, it was clear that Tsokpektang in Jhucntse and Dozam in Mongar would qualify being the only sites in these dzongkhag. Sites started after 2000 were not considered. Furthermore, in order to maintain consistency in the legal tenure status of the land on which the CP or CF was established, it was decided to choose those on government reserved forest only. This is the most frequently occurring legal tenure status of land on which CF/CP is started. It is a well-known fact (Bruce, 1989; Fortmann and Bruce, 1988; Fortmann and Ridell, 1985; Raintree, 1987; for examples from Bhutan, Gongthung and Khamdang, viz. Messerschmidt et al., 2000) that the legal status of the land will influence many aspects, especially the institutional ones, of a CP project. As such the Tholong Pangthang and Shangshang Phola sites did not qualify. Moreover, the Tholong Pangthang site is located at an altitude of approximately 2,400 masl, much higher than the other sites, and therefore it has a different vegetation type (*P. bhutanica/walllichii* instead of *P. roxburghii*) and thus also different plantation requirements. This meant that for Trashy Yangtse the Tsurgangpek CP would be chosen, and for Trashigang the Yezorongpek CP.

Other factors, such as site accessibility, were not taken into account. Whereas Pam could be reached in 20 minutes by motorbike, Tangmachhu took 1 ½ hour by four-wheel drive vehicle, Drametse 4 hours by truck, and Manam took 2 hours by truck and 5 hours by walk (all from dzongkhag headquarters).

Fig. 4: Map of Bhutan with location of study areas.

3.4 Used Methodology in the Study Areas

In the literature on PAME, RRA and PRA (viz. Chambers, 1983, 1992; Bruce, 1989; Molnar, 1989; Davis-Case, 1990; Thompson, 1994; Otheter, 1995; Messerschmidt, 1995) a range of tools is mentioned to be used in participatory methods of data collection. For this research, interviews of key (people with special knowledge on the subject), individual, and (focus) group (homo-/ heterogeneous groups of people) respondents, most participatively through semi-structured interviews, were used most often and effectively. However, direct observation at the site level and use of secondary data sources (existing literature) was used

as well. Probing, cross-checking/ triangulation of the information from different sources was not used as an independent tool, but took place as data quality assurance. The majority of the information was obtained from secondary sources as well as informal group discussion and key informant interviews. Also keeping in mind that the goal of this research was to elicit the local objectives and perceptions and a fully participatory approach was to be taken, it was decided that no evaluation criteria would be formulated beforehand. The interviews would be conducted using a number of questions as guidelines, and the respondents' own opinions and views. This list with questions, based upon information from the CFMPs, was kept at hand as guidance, but for the rest the interviews were open-ended in nature. The following choice of tools and their application was applied in the field:

A general description of the village surroundings and the community forest was done by observation and village walks together with village members. The history of the SF project was obtained from the project facilitators and CFMPs as well as from group discussions with the local community. The external objectives were asked to the project facilitators, extension staff and forest department staff. Consequently, it was asked whether the project objectives have remained the same during the project or had been adjusted in response to several factors, most importantly emerging dissatisfaction among the participants.

The objectives resulting from group and individual discussions as the outcome of research question 1 were also ranked according to the priorities as given by the community members. In the group discussions, the issue list served as a guide to make sure that no important issues were missed, but at the same time that the discussion did not deviate too much from the required responses. As such the group discussions had the character of open-ended interviews.

When a divergence in objectives for certain clearly definable actor groups was distinguished, these actor groups were separately interviewed during focus groups interviews. Though no society is homogenous, compared to many countries especially Nepal and India the rural areas of Bhutan have, at least at the household level, a less clear social stratification. Regarding inter-community heterogeneity has to be noted, that it has been observed that in day-to-day affairs, and especially at the household level, Bhutanese society is largely egalitarian (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). The example of Tshokpektang CP in Tangmachhu (viz. Ch. 6) shows that in many places there is strong social cohesion and solidarity. In Tama village, Zhemgang dzongkhag however the planning of a CF within the Mangdecbhu FMU was discontinued after there turned out to be a lack of co-operation among the villagers (Pckelder and Topper, 1998). As a result, during the fieldwork it was not noted that the objectives of certain distinguishable groups of households were notably different. As last respondent group, key informants were interviewed, both at the village as well as the block and district level.

During all interviews (except in Manam), forest extension staff was also present, even though it has been noted (e.g. Beuving, 1998) that their presence can result in untrue or at least politically desirable answers and opinions. This did however turn out not to be the case in Bhutan, since serious attempts were made to assure the local community that the research is done *independently* from the government and the project. Moreover, the forest extension staff all had a long-standing relation (of 3 to 5 years) with the community, and therefore they were really frank and open towards each other. Project and government headquarter staff, who are often respected and feared and do not have such a personal relationship, were never present during the data collection.

3.4.1 Dozam Community Forest, Drametse

Contact was made with Mr. Rinchen Wangdi, DzFO Mongar and with his previous experience working under the TFDP and conducting many RRAs and PRAs in eastern Bhutan in preparation of CFMPs this interview provided a lot of information. Consequently he referred to Mr. Tshering Choeda, FEO in Drametse geog, who has been actively involved in the Dozam CF. In Drametse the fieldwork was linked up with Mr. Tshering Choeda's CFMP review meetings with the CFMG members. Having run for 4 years the CFMP had to be reviewed. The executive committee members were instructed to gather representatives from all households. The meetings lasted every day from 9 a.m. till 5 p.m. Point by point the CFMP was discussed and the members were asked to comment on whether to change or keep it as it is. After that chance was given to express other comments and ideas regarding the new CFMP. Finally and on basis of the opinions expressed during the group discussion questions relating to the research were asked in general as well as to specific household representatives.

There were a total of three meetings, one at Shaphangma, where out of 29 households 25 had send their representatives, 9 males and 14 females. At the Zangkhar/Wungkhar/Phantshomo meeting 29 out of 42 households had send their representatives, 7 males and 22 females. From Wungkhar village only one representatives had shown up. The secretary of the CFMG and the Drametse mangi-ap were also present. At the Bikhar/Thramlu/Waichur meeting 24 out of 36 households had send their representatives, out of which 3 were underage. The secretary of the CFMG was again present.

The decisions made during these meetings would later be discussed in a general meeting. On basis of the consensus/conclusions reached in this meeting the new CFMP would be written. However at the time of departure from Bhutan the results from this meeting had not yet been forwarded to the FED, Thimphu, and could thus not be included in the report.

Fig. 5: CFMG members of Zangkhar, Wungkhar and Phantshomo, (04/04/2002).

3.4.2 Yezorongpek Community Plantation, Pam

Fig. 6: FEO Dorji Drukpa and CPMP members (08/03/2002).

After informing the DzFO Mr. Sithar Dorji, he directed to Mr. Dorji Drukpa, Trashigang FEO. Having a long experience and involvement in social forestry activities in Trashigang dzongkhag, informal discussion with him already provided valuable information. Subsequently he organised a group meeting in Lamngakpa hamlet at which the chairman and secretary of the CFMG as well as 9 household representatives consisting of both males as well as females were present. The group meeting itself produced the desired results and since no differences in opinion between the present members were observed it was deemed unnecessary to conduct any further interviews. After the plantation was destroyed by forest fire on April 1st some additional informal interviews with CFMG members were conducted to see what were their opinions as to how to proceed from there.

3.4.3 Tshurgangpek Community Plantation, Manam

The first information was retrieved from the CFMP provided by TFDP Khangma. In Yangtse itself a general discussion was held with the Yangtse DzFO Mr. Sonam Gyeltshen. However being new in office and not having visited the site he did not have much information to share. A second discussion with him was held in presence of the chairman of the CFMG cum mangi-ap Mr. Sonam Jamtsho as well as the Toetsho chhimi. He agreed to go to Manam together and provide the necessary assistance during the three-day fieldwork. As translator Mr. Ugyen Samdrup, pass-out from the Trashi Yangtse Institute for Zorig Chusum (traditional arts and crafts) came along who is fluent in Sharchokpakha and has intermediate level command of the local language (Bramilo).

A key informant interview was held with the chairman. For triangulation of the provided information two more informal interviews were held with female CFMG members, among them a widow with a two-member household, the other Mrs. Yeshey Choden. Due to the death of a Manam villager no further interviews could be held as the community had gone to the deceased person's house for attending the last rites. Lastly a field visit was made to the CP.

Fig. 7: CPMG Chairman, family and female CPMG members (03/03/2002).

3.4.4 Tshokpektang Community Plantation, Tangmachhu

In absence of the DzFO Mr. Nima Dorji, direct contact was established with the FEO, Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, who moreover has a much longer experience in SF activities in the dzongkhag. A key informant interview with him (29/03/02) generated a list of detailed questions to be asked to the CPMG members. In presence of Mr. Nakphel Drukpa and a new FEO Mr. Tshering Dorji whose native language is Choecha Ngacha kha (the language spoken in Tangmachhu) a group interview was conducted at the private/community nursery location (30/03/02). In this interview the chairman and secretary of the CPMG were present as well as both male and female household members. Beside the previously designed question list room was left for additional comments and questions. Although the chairman and the secretary dominated (but not controlled) the discussion, it did not seem that other members disagreed with their opinions. When asked separately later on they agreed on all the points mentioned. After the interview a site visit was made together with the chairman.

Fig.8: FEO Nakphel Drukpa and FEO Tshering Dorji (left) with CPMP members, (30/03/2002).

3.5 Limitations of the Study

This study has as geographical limitation the four eastern Bhutanese dzongkhag of Lhuentse, Mongar, Trashigang and Trashi Yangtse. Community Forestry and Community Plantation sites in western Bhutan were not visited. Due to time and logistical constraints not all sites could be included in the research and a choice was made for the four different sites mentioned above. In total 2 months were spent in eastern Bhutan, of which 3 weeks were spent in the villages (ranging from 2 to 9 days per site), 2 weeks total on travelling, and the remaining 3 weeks on establishing contacts, collecting and reviewing literature and preparing the field visits. This includes visits to a number of other sites, such as Masang Daza CF in Mongar and Joensham Lamdroksa CP in Trashigang (both in the planning phase).

Inter-community heterogeneity such as described in Chapter 2.3 was not included in the research although wherever it did appear specifically it has been mentioned. However the main focus has been on the objectives of the local community and the government/project.

It also has to be noted that the research did not focus on the question to what extent the 'official' objectives as they appeared from the documents and the discussions with the staff were also the objectives at the field level. In other words, it was not examined whether when forestry or project staffs for example discuss with the community or write the CFMPs they are lead by these official objectives or whether they acted in other (such as their own) interest as well.

Chapter 4

Research Background and Context

4.1 (Social) Forestry in Bhutan; Policies and Legislation

Around 70% of Bhutan is currently under forest cover, with 13% of this under management. Wood and wood products account for 11.9% of the total exports in 1994, and forestry for 9.2% of GDP in 1995 (Bhatia, 2000). Forests also contribute to 5% of government revenues through royalties and sales revenues (Wee, 1991). Bhutan's forests are among the most important remains of natural eastern Himalayan forests. They are characterised by exceptional biological diversity and considered one of the world's ten most important biodiversity hotspots (Food and Agricultural Organisation, 2000). Forest in Bhutan is state owned, but rural people have traditional user rights for grazing, collection of fuelwood and non-timber forest products, and thus the forests are an important resource base for rural communities. Forests provide 90% of rural domestic fuel as well as timber for construction. The Divisional Forest Office controls timber marketing and allocation of permits. Bhutan's per household firewood consumption is among the highest in the world and for rural household consumption free of charge. Grazing cattle on government land is allowed but subject to restriction where the government deems necessary (McSessersmidt et al., 2000). Forests also play a major role in food security, forming a backup when transportation problems reduce food availability, people do not have enough money to buy food, and when there is crop failure (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2000). An estimated 164 plant products are collected from the forest (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 1996).

Centralised forest management through Forest Departments is a relatively new experience for Bhutan, compared to India and other countries - just over 30 years. Traditionally, communities managed their surrounding forests in more or less sustainable ways themselves. The Department of Forests (DoF) was only established in 1952. Till 1994 it was known as DoF, from 1994-2000 it became the Forestry Services Division (FSD), and from 2000 onwards it is known as the Department of Forest Services (DFS). The Bhutan Forest Act (Department of Forests, 1969) was a landmark in the history of natural resources access, utilisation and management in Bhutan. Overnight, communities ceded their rights and ownership of trees and forest to the state. Forest in Bhutan that is not on privately owned land became per definition state property and was defined as "Government Reserved Forest (GRF)" (Dz.: 'Zhung wā nātshā'). Forestry activities on private land fell under social forestry (Dz.: 'Mi'de nātshā'). Though Bhutan was never colonised by foreign powers, the policy and legislation in India which influenced the drafting of the Act in 1969. The policy of the former colonial powers was to immediately nationalise the forest resources to make as much revenue for their governments and to meet their expanding raw material requirement. The local people were marginalised and they were perceived and considered as problems to forest management (Department of Forests, 1974). In Bhutan, while the forest bureaucracy is just over 30 years, there is, unfortunately, also a strongly developed tendency in the local culture to think that the forest is best managed by the central government, and that the government, in anyway, takes care of all the needs of the local people. While the government sees to the needs of the local people, it has not thought seriously how it can facilitate local people to take more responsibility and seize opportunities in managing the nearby and surrounding forests.

Non-convergence of Objectives in Social Forestry in Eastern Bhutan

Social forestry interventions have been implemented in many parts of the world during the last two decades, and in the South Asian region India and Nepal have been frontrunners in this respect (Hobley, 1996; Bartlett, 1991, 1992). In Bhutan however policy makers apparently felt the need and urgency for social forestry programmes relatively late, presumably due to the unique situation that characterises this kingdom (Bhatia, 2000). Despite population growth and rapid socio-economic development during the past three decades, the natural environment in the Kingdom of Bhutan has remained largely unaffected. Deep reverence for nature imbedded in the Buddhist belief of the majority of the population created an intense awareness of the infallible relationship between man and his natural environment. Moreover geographical conditions did not allow for expansion of the agricultural area beyond 8%. And lastly, the development policies of the Royal Government of Bhutan have always been consciously directed towards reconciling socio-economic development with the preservation of culture, traditions and the natural bounty.

In 1979 His Majesty the King issued a Royal Degree on Social Forestry, in which it was stated that the limited forestry staff cannot adequately manage and control the local use of forests and that the participation of local communities is the key to the conservation and utilisation of forest resources. It commands the revision of the forest policy and the preparation of a scheme for the promotion of social forestry in and around villages, in order to involve local people in the planting of trees on private and communal lands.

In 1989 the Social Forestry and Extension Section (SFES) was established under DoF with a mandate to develop national forestry extension programmes, prepare rules and train extension staff for their implementation, and to test them in the field. In 1997 SFES became the Social Forestry and Afforestation Section (SFAS), and in 2001 it was upgraded to the Forest Extension Division (FED) under the DFS. In 1990 the Interim Social Forestry Rules were issued by the DoF (Department of Forests, 1990). In 1992 the Draft National Forest Policy with conservation of nature as main priority is written (Department of Forests, 1992). In 1993, at the start of the 7th Five Year Plan (FYP), the social forestry extension was decentralised to the dzongkhag level, which underscores the importance and need for close participation of local communities in forest management. Direct forestry extension activities became the responsibility of the Dzongkhag Forestry Extension Section (DFES) and its local staff the Dzongkhag Forestry Officer (DzFO) and Forest Extension Officers (FEOs). The Social Forestry Rules were revised as well.

Whilst not changing the legal property rights of the GRF and private forestland, the Forest and Nature Conservation Act of 1995 (Ministry of Agriculture, 1995) introduced a new concept in Bhutanese forestry. Due to the recent introduction of CF, the FNCA has only one section dedicated to community forestry (Dzongkha: 'Drong'deī nātshā'). Section 17 (a) to (c) states that the Ministry of Agriculture may make rules for the establishment of community forests on GRF. It then continues that these rules may provide for the transfer of ownership of the forest produce in the community forest to appropriate groups of inhabitants of communities adjoining the forest. This group shall manage the forests for sustainable use in accordance with the rules and the approved management plan. Section 18 describes the rules for protection of the community forestry and penalties for offences committed against the rules.

However several factors contributed to the need for more specific community forestry rules and regulations. Firstly, the continued development of the forestry sector in Bhutan with increased funding and manpower as well as better educated and specialised national staff. Secondly, the example of the relative successes booked with community forestry projects in neighbouring Nepal and India. And lastly, the realisation that despite the best intentions,

population trends and development of the rural areas do affect the forests, especially at the local level. Whilst nation-wide policies for forest protection were established at an early stage of development and commercial forest harvesting was regulated by the state quite soon, at the local level extraction of forest produce continued as usual. With changing times and increased foreign influence and living standards in the urban centres, the morals and attitudes of the rural people started to alter and traditional values that had preserved the natural environment started to erode. Despite strict national legislation on forest conversion and wildlife protection, the remoteness of most rural areas made it impossible to effectively enforce these rules. The FNCR authorised the issuance of the Social Forestry Rules for private and community forestry. The revised Social Forestry Rules were issued in 1996 (Forestry Services Division, 1996). These developments finally resulted in the Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of 2000 (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000). In these new rules Chapter 4 (Social Forestry Rules 2000) is completely designated for social and community forestry. Whereas the earlier definitions of private forest and GRF as well as social and community forestry remained unaltered, Part B on community forests saw a considerable extension. The sections include the institutional arrangements relating to the establishment of Community Forests on GRF by a Community Forest Management Group (CFMG).

Bhutan has also undergone the development phases in SF that have been described from all around the world (see Wiersum, 1996). The main difference is that, due to the relatively late inception of the national SF programme and the cautious approach, the phases occurred later and in a shorter span of time than elsewhere. Before 1989 when the Social Forestry and Extension Section was established the focus was mainly on government plantations on government land whereby the community provided paid labour. The experimental phase was characterised by the establishment of community woodlots/plantations in western Bhutan in order to relieve fuelwood and timber shortages. This phase lasted roughly from 1989 till 1993. The consolidation phase was ignited after the revised Social Forestry Rules of 1990 started to be implemented, with increased attention for decentralisation and people's participation in forestry. Still the larger part of the sites were plantations, and the focus lies mainly in eastern Bhutan where the TFDP was active. This phase started around 1993 and approximately ended in 2000. From that year onwards the Social Forestry Rules and part of the Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of 2000 gave a new impetus to social forestry by allowing for the inclusion of natural forests. This phase is also mainly concentrated in Eastern Bhutan and continues till date. SF interventions are thus relatively new to Bhutan, especially when compared to other countries in the region such as India and Nepal. This gives Bhutan the unique opportunity to learn from success and failures of its neighbours and to create an approach most appropriate to its own local socio-cultural, economic and environmental contexts and needs (Messerschmidt et al., 2000).

The national SF program in Bhutan consists of three elements:

- *Community Forestry (CF)* which aims at enabling traditional user groups in forest management activities on government land including commons
- *Private Forestry (PF)*, also called *Agroforestry* or *Farm Forestry* which promotes tree planting and forest or woodlot activities by individuals on their private lands, as well as the creation of private nurseries and seedling distribution
- *School Social Forestry (SSF)* which is a type of institutional forestry focussing on education and developing awareness among the youth.

4.2 Social Forestry in Eastern Bhutan

The entire social forestry sector in eastern Bhutan (viz. the organigram in Appendix B) falls under the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) of the Royal Government. Two departments within this ministry are involved, namely the Department of Forestry Services (DFS) and the Department of Research and Development Services (DRDS). DRDS is mainly involved through the Renewable Natural Resources-Research Center (RNR-RC) at Khangma. They conduct research and provide the outcome in the form of information to the DzFO and FEO at dzongkhag level, the FEO in the geog RNR-Extension Centers, the SFEC, and the territorial staff. Another important RNR-RC is the one in Yusipang, Thimphu, which carries the national mandate for forestry extension and research. Information coming from the field is also processed in the RNR-RCs. The Department of Forestry Services is represented in the organigram by three divisions, namely the Forest Extension Division (FED), the Forestry Protection and Utilisation Division (FPUD) and the Forest Resources Development Division (FRDD). All these Divisions have their headquarters in Thimphu. The FRDD operates mainly on the national level and through the SFSU provides technical assistance, mainly in the field of vegetation surveys and site demarcation, to the DFO and the SFEC at the local level. The territorial DFOs in Mongar and Trashigang represent the FPUD at the local level. They and their staff are mainly providing technical assistance to the SFEC and the dzongkhag and geog level FEOs, especially in the planning phase of the project. This technical assistance mostly consists of vegetation surveys, forest condition surveys, site demarcation and in the monitoring phase to see to a correct implementation of the agreements made in the CF/CPMP.

The main actors at local level from within the DFS come from the FED. Within the FED it is the Social Forestry and Extension Section (SFES) located in Thimphu which is the main section that deals with social forestry. They create awareness, design, introduce, monitor and support social forestry interventions at the national level. Their main implementers at the local level are the DzFOs and the FEOs at the dzongkhag headquarters and the FEOs in the geog RNR-Extension Centres. They formally come under the respective dzongkhag administration of the Ministry of Home Affairs, but receive their technical assistance from the FED and are thus represented as part of the FED here. Not all geog have a geog RNR-Extension Centre, and in those geog that don't these tasks are taken over by the FEOs at dzongkhag level. The DzFO has mainly a co-ordinating task in the process, whereas the actual fieldwork is done by the FEOs. They work closely together with the SFEC of the TFDP and are the main local-level representations of the government in the social forestry sector dealing with the community itself. Lastly the Project Facilitation Office under which the TFDP comes has a special position within the MoA since it is of a temporary nature. SF interventions have been mainly based in the eastern dzongkhag, and the TFDP is one, if not the main, facilitator for these interventions. They are mainly focussed on the CF and PF compartments of the national SF program (Wee et al., 1991). The SF component has been executed by the Social Forestry and Extension Cell (SFEC) of the Project Facilitation Office (PFO) in Khangma. However, during the project implementation, the afforestation and reforestation component also came partly under the SF programme as most community forestry projects were technically plantations. The SFEC has information and technical linkages to the SFSU, the RNR-RC and the DFOs and with a two-way technical and information stream with the DzFOs and FEOs and the local community.

Under the TDFP, two types of community-based forest management are being developed in association with the DzFO and DFO staff. These are:

- Community Forest (CF, or Community Forest Management Unit, CFMU)
- Community Plantation (CP, or Pilot Community Plantation, PCP)

Initially the SF programme was designed to plan and implement an untargeted number of Community Forestry Management Units (CFMUs), in response to local awareness and promotion campaigns (World Bank, 1993). However, following the project's mid-term review a target of one per dzongkhag (six total) was set (Evans et al., 1996; Desmond, 1996). Later this number was again reduced to a more realistic three on pilot basis (Keil et al., 1998). These have by now become Dozam CF (Mongar), Gayzor CF (Pema Gatsel) and Yakpugang CF (Mongar), with a fourth one (Masang Daza CF in Mongar) currently under discussion for approval. During that same mid-term review it was decided to start with Community Plantations (CPs) for reforestation (on degraded land) or afforestation (on barren lands). Beside the introduction of a participatory form of afforestation/reforestation, the CP approach also aimed at stemming and preventing soil erosion (Keil et al., 1998; Messerschmidt et al., 2000). The development of CPs has been fairly good, but that of CFs has been slow (Evans et al., 1996). Both CF and CP are to be managed through the executive committees selected to represent the local users organised into Community Forestry Management Groups (CFMGs). The major characteristics of and differences between CF and CP are as follows:

CF has as resource base natural forest for sustainable management, and/or degraded forest for reforestation, and/or barren land for afforestation. The size is expected to be ~ 2.5 ha per household times a minimum number of 10 households. The management responsibility is in the hands of the CFMG with an executive committee and a detailed plan (CFMP). The management is entrusted to the local community over all the forest resources within its boundaries. The CFMG shares the benefits and resources as well as income from fees and fines etc. This income will be used for a group fund for public works and/or for use as a revolving loan fund. The natural forest is improved by protection and sustainable management, whereas degraded and barren areas are improved by direct seeding or planted up with seedlings, and natural regeneration is protected.

CP has as resource base degraded land for reforestation and/or barren land for afforestation. The size is small and variable with an overall goal of 600 to 700 ha across the whole TDFP area. The management is in hands of a CFMG with a detailed plan. The CFMG shares the benefits and resources as well as income from fees and fines etc. This income will be used for a group fund for public works and/or for use as a revolving loan fund. Degraded and barren areas are improved by direct seeding or planted up with seedlings. Measures are also to be taken to improve the natural forest, and to protect the natural regeneration.

The feature differentiating CF from CP is that a substantial percentage of the local management area in CF is natural forest (typically up to 50%), whereas in CP the site has only degraded or barren forestland.

4.3 History and Description of Study Areas

Eastern Bhutan consists of the six dzongkhag of Mongar, Lhuentse, Trashigang, Trashigang, Pema Gatsel and Samdrup Jongkhar. The total area is 11,382 km², around 30% of Bhutan (LUPP, 1997). It is an isolated part of Bhutan, and from the capital Thimphu it takes a two days drive by car or three days by public transport to reach Trashigang (if road condition permits). Physically, it is more closely connected to Assam and Arunachal Pradesh districts of India. Geographically it is rather different from the rest of the country, ranging from the sub tropical foothills in Pema Gatsel and Samdrup Jongkhar and the lower valleys of Mongar, through the temperate inner Himalayan hills of Mongar and Trashigang and lower parts of Lhuentse and Yangtse, to the greater Himalayan alpine zone in north-eastern Trashigang and northern Lhuentse and Yangtse. The landscape of the interior region is characterised by deep V-shaped valleys.

Average population density is 35 people per square kilometre¹, and one third of the total population of Bhutan lives here (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). Average household size is estimated to be seven and population increase 2.7% per year (slightly higher than the national average). The population consists mainly of sedentary agropastoralists (approximately 85% of the population) who have built their homesteads and carved out their fields in the rugged landscape. Farming is conducted on irrigated wetland (chhuzhing), rain-fed dryland (kanzhing), and by shifting cultivation (tseri and pangzhing). Main crops are maize, upland rice, potato, chilli, millet, wheat, buckwheat, soybean and a variety of vegetables and fruits, mainly for domestic consumption. Potato and orange have recently become important export crops. Agroforestry is an ageless activity of the farmers, with crops mixed with trees and shrubs as well as grazing in a variety of ways and for a variety of purposes. A special example is that of sokshing, government reserved forest, which has been legally registered to a private rights-holder, from which leaf litter is collected to make farmyard compost and manure. Grazing land is mostly in or near the government reserved forest and called tsamdros, communal grazing land (12% of total area). Livestock (total estimated 264,000 heads) is grazed in tsamdros at higher altitudes in summer and in the winter the cattle is grazed at lower altitudes in the fallow agricultural fields and nearby forests (Wee et al., 1991). Cattle are kept for milk, cheese and butter as well as meat. The arable land amounts to 17.

The area has six main ecological zones: alpine, cool temperate, wet temperate, dry subtropical, humid subtropical, and wet subtropical, depending on altitude (200 to 5,800 masl), rainfall (1,000 to 5,000 mm per year), soil, aspect of the slope and other factors. Mountain forests are a predominant feature of the landscape of eastern Bhutan. An estimated 68% of the total area is currently under forest cover, ranging from 87% in Mongar to 53% in Pema Gatsel. There are nine major forest types in eastern Bhutan (Ministry of Agriculture, 1998; Grierson and Long, 1983), namely tropical lowland and lowland hardwood forest, chir pine forest, evergreen oak forest, cool moist broad leaf forest, broad-leaf/conifer mixed forest, blue pine forest, mixed conifer forest and fir forest.

The forests in eastern Bhutan form an integral part of the farming system, and both agriculture and livestock rearing depend on them. However natural degradation is increasing due to the high population and livestock density. Thus in some locations the shortages of and inaccessibility to forest resources is becoming more and more apparent. It is here that public interest in SF activities is highest. The CF and CP sites visited in this research, and indeed many of the CP sites in eastern Bhutan, are located in chir pine forest. Chir pine (*Pinus*

¹ However when a more realistic average number of people per square kilometre of arable land is taken (considering the large inhabitable and non-arable area), the figure ranges from 180/km² for Samdrup Jongkhar to 290/km² for Mongar (Dick and Yonzon, 1996).

roxburghii) in open stands is found in the deep, dry inner valleys of Mongar, Trashigang, Trashi Yangtse and Lhuentse at altitudes of 900-1,800 masl. These valleys have a long winter and early spring dry season when burning is frequent. *P. roxburghii* are fairly resistant to burning after reaching shoulder height, but the underlying brush, grass and accumulated pine needles and mainly the dry lemon grass with high oil content are highly inflammable. Main use of the forest relates to timber extraction, grazing, resin tapping, fuelwood cutting and lemon grass harvesting. In Dozam CF, Drametse, the upper part of the CF consists of evergreen oak forest, but the majority of the site is chir pine forest.

4.3.1 Dozam CF, Mongar

Dozam CF was the first CF implemented in Bhutan. It is located in Drametse Tsho 'Om geog, in Mongar dzongkhag. It was established under the TFDP as a comparative CF experiment, consisting of mainly degraded and barren land, as opposed to Gochadrang CF that would consist mainly of natural forest. Dozam CF covers 300 ha, of which 100 ha are under cultivation and settlement. The site is located on a steep (average slope of 67%) southwards facing slope ranging between 800m at the lower south side near the national highway to 2,000m at the northern ridgetop near Drametse village. The site is demarcated by the Khairmaithung ridge (from Zangkhar through Phantshomo till Yayung) to the north and east, by the national highway between Mongar and Trashigang to the south, and the Shinardrang seasonal stream to the west. Since the site is in the rainshadow it is dry and hence has poor vegetation. The predominant vegetation consists of chir pine and lemon grass, but the site is depleted due to timber and fuelwood extraction. In some steep, moist gullies there is limited natural regeneration. The use was limited to free grazing of cattle, lemon grass harvesting for oil extraction and compost, lopping of kharabtangshing (*Lyonia ovalifolia*) for fuelwood, and harvesting of phinshing (*Aesandra butyracea*) seeds for essential oil extraction (Forestry Services Division, 1997a). Use is made by the people of the villages/hamlets surrounding the area, namely Gop, Waichur, Zangkhar, Yayung, Shaphangma and Wunkhar, and of the three villages inside the area, Bkhar, Phantshomo and Tbramlu.

Fig. 9: Dozam Community Forest with the location of three internal and one external village.

The identification of the site started in May 1995 when an RRA (Basnet et al., 1995a) was conducted. In April 1996 the site was selected and demarcated, the users were identified, the CFMG committee was selected, a PRA was conducted and the application was completed. The number of users was initially established at 109 households from 7 villages. The planning stage started in June 1996 by drafting of the CFMP and completion of the forest inventory. In August 1997 the CFMG approved the final CFMP. In July 1997 the implementation stage started, with the official handing over of management responsibilities in September 1997. Annual CFMG meetings have been held as well. From 1996 till 2002 a total of 98,261 seedlings was planted, covering approximately 106 acres or 42 ha. The target was to plant 136,250 seedlings on 50 ha in 5 years (106 households times 5 years times 250 seedlings per year). The target was not met mainly due to a lack of seedlings in some years. In addition there was broadcast sowing of 0.5 kg of chir pine seeds in 1998-1999. Lemon grass oil production units are licensed by the CFMG, and the license fees were deposited into the CFMG fund. Annual CFMG meetings were held to assess progress, resolve issues, review member activities, elect executive committee members, receive guidance from DFES staff etc.

4.3.2 Yezorongpek CP, Trashigang

After an awareness campaign on CF by the Trashigang dzongkhag forestry extension staff the villagers applied for the establishment of a CP. The interested number was 47 out of a total of 51 households. Although no RRA or PRA was conducted to gather information on the community and the site, the FEO Mr. Dorji Drukpa and staff held several group meetings in preparation of the CFMP. The different objectives, rules and regulations were composed and discussed during these meetings with community representatives and the draft version of the CFMP was discussed with the whole community for approval and necessary adjustments (personal communication with Mr. Dorji Drukpa, 08/02/02). The Director of Forest approved the management plan in March 2000 and the certificate was issued on June 11th 2000.

The site has a total area of 9.32 ha and was originally established on GRF. Its boundaries are demarcated by the feeder road to Rangjukhar in the east, the old foot trail to Trashigang Dzong in the west, Lamngakpa hamlet to the south, and Chamkhar Duwang, Kheti hamlet and the land of Mr. Ngotong to the north. The site was severely degraded without any natural forest stands or other vegetation except some shrubs. Use of the area by Pam community was limited to grazing land for local cattle and collection of *Phyllanthus emblica* fruits for domestic use (Forestry Services Division, 1999a). The CFMP was written after a partial RRA and site reconnaissance.

4.3.3 Tshurgangpek CP, Trashi Yangtse

Tshurgangpek CP is located on the slope to the west of Manam village below the footpath coming from Khinyel. The slope faces south-east and until plantation had always been degraded with as only vegetation lemon grass and several other grass species, shrubs like Phrokpalagashing (*Butea buteiformis*) and Omla (*Phyllanthus emblica*) trees. Use of the site was limited to cattle grazing by the people of Manam and Thangdrang as well as people from the villages of Chemkhar and Maidung. The site boundaries are demarcated by Rakti Manitsawa chorten to the north, Tshurgang Draphugitsur ridge denoted by a single tree and large rock to the south along the Tshurgangrong stream, Mergola Brakyar rock outcrop to the east and Phinshing Tshawamar tree to the west with a total area of 13 acres or 5.30 hectares (Forestry Services Division, 1998). The CFMP was written after a partial RRA and field reconnaissance.

Fig. 10: Mergola Brakyar, the rock outcrop demarcating the eastern border of the CP site.

The Yangtse DzFO conducted an awareness campaign on CF/CP in his dzongkhag and the community of Manam and Thangdrang responded positively on the idea of establishing a CP. The whole community of 27 households enrolled as member. The exact site was selected and demarcated and the CFMP was written and put up for approval. Yangtse Dzongda recommended the CFMP on 30/10/1998 and approval by the DFO was given on 11/12/1998. The certificate was granted by the new Yangtse Dzongda on 27/10/1999 on basis of the FNCA (1995) and Community Forestry Rules of 1993 (draft). No RRA or PRA was conducted. In three years time i.e. from 1998-2000 the area of 13 ha was completely planted. A fire in April 2000 however destroyed the whole site. After that no replanting was done.

4.3.4 Tshokpektang CP, Lhuentse

The DzFO of Lhuentse informed the people of Tangmachhu of the existence of a CF/CP programme and they expressed their interest to participate. In 1995 a RRA was conducted in Tangmachhu village to see to what extent the village was eligible for establishment of a CP. The results of the RRA (Basnet et al, 1995b) were encouraging and the TFDP decided to start a pilot CP in Tangmachhu with 19 member households. After the FE● Mr. Gem Tshering had drafted a CFMP in close co-operation with the community it was approved on June 3rd 1998 and the certificate was issued on May 27th 1999. Starting from 1998, by 2001 the whole site was planted with chir pine, eucalyptus and Melia and Cupressus spp. In end of October 1999 a community nursery was established (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29/03/02).

Before establishment of the CP the site was severely degraded with only a few small sized pine trees and dispersed kharabtangshing and perennial herbs (Forestry Services Division, 1997b). After nationalisation of the forest in 1969 some regeneration took place but still the site remained barren. Site use was restricted to grazing land for local cattle, grass collection for bedding and lopping of pine and coppicing of kharabtangshing for fuelwood. The total area of the CP is 8 ha. The CFMP was written after partial RRA with field reconnaissance. The north boundary is formed by sokshing land, the south by a steep and inaccessible ridge, the west by a stream and the east by a ridge.

5.1 Objectives of the National Social Forestry Program

The objectives of Bhutan's SF program are largely derived from greater objectives of the countries' development policy. The overarching goal of all policies in Bhutan is ensuring the future independence, sovereignty and security of the nation-state. The achievement of this goal is guided by the principles of the maintenance of the unique Bhutanese identity, the maintenance of unity and harmony, ensuring stability, the promotion of self-reliance, the concept of sustainability and lastly flexibility and the capacity to adapt to change (Planning Commission Secretariat, 1999). The central development concept is, in contrast to the more widely used Gross National Product, the concept of *Gross National Happiness*. Realising that happiness is the ultimate desire of all human beings and all else is just a means of achieving this happiness, the development path of Bhutan can be seen as a process to maximise happiness, rather than economic growth. The main development objectives are defined as human development, culture and heritage, balanced and equitable development, governance and environmentally sustainable development.

The objectives for the SF program naturally flow from the combination between a number of these objectives. Firstly, that of balanced and equitable development, which aims at giving development opportunities to all groups in society, including those in the rural areas, remote and inaccessible locations, and vulnerable and disadvantaged groups (Planning Commission Secretariat, 1999:77). Secondly, the management of development must be progressively adapted in response to new needs and requirements, and thus take account of the devolution of new powers to the dzongkhag and gcog levels. Moreover it should be aimed at strengthening the management capacities of local communities, making them 'owners' of the development process (Planning Commission Secretariat, 1999:79, 82, 83). Lastly, the development process should be environmentally sustainable in all aspects. Specifically, the approach to forest regeneration should display a greater sensitivity to the maintenance of biodiversity (Planning Commission Secretariat, 1999:89). Combining the three objectives, one finds an attempt to facilitate, enable and empower all groups of rural/local communities to develop themselves in all aspects and at the same time maintain the ecological base that sustains them.

In the various official documents that have been released over the years containing rules and regulations on the SF program, most goals and objectives have not dramatically changed (viz. e.g. Forestry Services Department, 1996; Maier, 1996). The goals have been described as:

- To maintain biological diversity and ecological functions of the land (protection function);
- To maintain or improve the sustainable supply of forest products in order to contribute positively to the self-sufficiency and the economies in the rural areas (production function);
- To improve and strengthen rural institutions which are interested in the sustainable use of the forests and to ensure equitable decision making processes, implementation and the equitable distribution of forest benefits (social and economic function).

From these goals the following objectives were derived:

- To transfer the responsibilities for management, implementation, development and utilisation to local users;

- To strengthen the technical, institutional and organisational skills and the capacity of the local users;
- To assist the forest users in developing forest based home and cottage industries.

The national SF programme is divided in three components of community forestry, private forestry (including agroforestry) and school forestry. This research focuses on the community forestry component.

5.2 Objectives of the Third Forestry Development Project

The overall objective of the TFDP (viz. chapter 3.3) is to support the RGoB's efforts to develop an approach for sustainable protection, management and use of its forest resources in line with national development plans (Woe et al., 1991). The goals have been described as:

- To protect Bhutan's rich biodiversity heritage and ensure a sustainable supply of forest products for the rural population, urban centres and local forest industries;
- To involve local people in the management of forest areas near villages;
- To integrate trees into farming systems;
- To rehabilitate degraded government forest land; and
- To ensure an effective policy development and sector planning capacity.

And as objectives it aims at establishing, in eastern Bhutan, the mechanisms for:

1. Sustainable forest management for selected government forest areas;
2. The involvement of local people in the rehabilitation of degraded forest areas and their subsequent management;
3. The integration of trees into farming systems thus improving the viability of the local economy;
4. The introduction of a criteria-based approach to afforestation and reforestation; and
5. Strengthening the government's capacity for effective and efficient implementation of the above development programmes.

These objectives are to be executed by means of four components, namely:

- Forest management, for objective 1;
- Social forestry, for objective 2 and 3;
- Afforestation and reforestation, for objective 4; and
- Institutional strengthening, for objective 5.

Since the TFDP has a purely advisory and facilitating role towards the royal government's social forestry sector its objectives are similar to those of the government. Whereas the government wants to transfer the management, implementation, development and utilisation responsibility of the forest resources to the local people and strengthen their technical, institutional and organisational skills, the project's objectives are to assist the government in these respects. Consultations with TFDP staff affirmed this. Although the linkages between the TFDP and the Forestry Department at the national level are not very strong, it was mainly at the local level in eastern Bhutan that the relationship has become very close. As such, the government and the TFDP have been considered as a single entity or stakeholder group in the process, rather than two separate groups with different, conflicting objectives and interests, as has been observed in other social forestry projects (viz. chapter 2.4 and e.g. Wiersum 1999b).

5.3 The Role of Extension Agents

In between the government and the local people in Bhutan there is, as in most nations, a number of intermediaries. These intermediaries in Bhutan are for example the *gup*, *chim* and *mangi-ap*. Within the Ministry of Agriculture the extension agents assume the main intermediary role. There are agricultural, animal husbandry and forestry extension agents based in all the *dzongkhag* headquarters as well as in (almost) all the *geog*. At the *dzongkhag* level the extension agent is called *Dzongkhag Forestry Officer (DzFO)* and he is assisted in the *geog* by his assistants. Both are most commonly called *Forest Extension Officers (FEOs)* or *Forest Rangers*. It is important to note the difference between the *DzFOs* and *FEOs*, and the *Divisional Forest Officer (DFO)* and the *Forest Guards*. The *DzFOs* and *FEOs* come under the *Forestry Extension Division* and operate from within the *dzongkhag* administration, and their main task is extension. The *DFO* and *Forest Guards* operate directly under the *Department of Forest Services*, are located in a special office and are mainly focused on forest protection (issue of permits, chocking and fining). In the study area all the *Dzongkhag* have a *DzFO*, but the *DFOs* are located in *Mongar* (for *Mongar* and *Lhuentse*) and *Trashigang* (for *Trashigang* and *Trashi Yangtse*). *FEOs* are usually trained at the *Natural Resources Training Institute's Forestry course* at *Lobcysa*, whereas the *divisional forest guards* are usually pass-outs from the *Taba Forestry Institute*. *DzFO* and *DFO* usually have a background of in-country training at the *NRTI* or its predecessor combined with working experience and additional education abroad, which may vary from *Diploma* to *MSc* qualifications.

Within the framework of the TFDP another type of intermediary is involved in social forestry namely those from the *Social Forestry and Extension Cell (SFEC)*. In practice most TFDP staff is directly or indirectly involved in social forestry activities including those from the *Private Forestry and Afforestation Cells*. The *SFEC* has mostly an advisory role towards the forestry staff from the government side. Although there has been a national staff present over the project running period, there have been external consultants from the Australian consultancy agency *Fortech* as well. They provide the local government forestry staff (i.e. the *DzFO* and *FEO* at *dzongkhag* level, the *FEOs* in the *geog*, and the *DFO* and his staff) with training on participatory techniques and assist in their implementation in the field. They also provide necessary equipment such as drawing boards and pens for participatory planning.

A simplified overview of the main organisational (viz. also 4.2), technical and information linkages in the social forestry sector in eastern Bhutan are given in Annex B. Not all the actors involved and not all the linkages could be indicated in the organigram, but the most important ones have been depicted. It has to be kept in mind that there is a major information stream running through the whole system, back from the lower echelons to the higher ones and among the higher ones. Since the approach of the research was at the local level, the focus in the chart has been on the lower echelons. It can be seen that the local community is very much at the centre of the processes. The organisational linkages have also been presented in chapter 4.2. For *Social Forestry* the *DzFO* and the *FEOs* and the *TFDP* staff are the main intermediaries between the local people and the government. The four-stage process leading to the establishment and implementation of a *CF/CP* site as well as the main actors is given in Box 2:

Box 2: Stages in the CF process (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000; Messerschmidt et al., 2000)

Identification involves the selection of a commonly used forest area and the group of users. In most cases, FEOs as part of their job disseminate information on the possibilities of community forestry among the people in the villages. In other cases the local people hear about it from other sources. In response to that, it is the village community itself, which will make an application for assistance in the establishment of a community forest. In some cases, especially in the early stages of social forestry development in eastern Bhutan and in the case of community forestry with additional purposes such as watershed management, the extension agent works pro-active and identifies an area himself after which consultations with the local people takes place. After a community and the forest it uses have been identified a report is written including a broad overview of the socio-economic situation of the community, the forest conditions, the interaction between them, site demarcation and condition, site mapping, forest use, forest product availability and trends. RRA tools are commonly used during the data collection.

The actors in this stage are mainly the local community and the FEO at dzongkhag and geog level. Smaller roles are there for the territorial forest guards, and the staff of the SFEC of the TFDP.

Planning involves the organisation of the users, the preparation of the plan, and the submission of the plan for authorisation. Firstly the national community forestry programme goals and procedures are explained to the community members. Then the CFMG members are selected. A very important step includes a participatory approach to writing the CFMP. This includes an overview of the current forest situation, the management objectives of the local community members, the existing communal organisations and forest management systems, the constitution and bylaws, and the utilisation and protection rules. It also includes a more detailed assessment of the forest resources such as the forest product requirements, inventories on the current availability, and determination of the forest management objectives and operations.

The FEO and SFEC staff now compile a draft CFMP absorbing all the above mentioned information and including a plan of the activities and inputs required. During subsequent meetings with all the member households the draft plan is discussed over and over until the local community has no further comments and additions to the plan. This process may take several months. When the community has approved of the final plan, it is sent for approval to the DzFO, DFO and Dzongda who then recommend it for approval to the Director of Forests in Thimphu. Any of them might send the plan back with comments and requests for modification. After that the certificate is handed over to the community in an official ceremony in presence of the dzongkhag officials.

The CFMG executive committee members and the CFMG in consultation and co-operation with the FEO at dzongkhag and geog level and the SFEC staff conduct the actual planning process. The RNR-RC and SFSU sometimes contribute information. In the more technical/silvicultural aspects of the fieldwork and forest assessment the territorial forest guards are consulted. The DzFO and DFO review the plan and judge it according to the government objectives. The Dzongda, being the highest local level authority, approves the plan upon advice to do so by the DFO and recommends it to the Director of Forests, who has the final say in it. Before actually ending up at the Director's desk, the plan is scrutinised by the national forest extension staff of the FED as well.

Implementation involves the on-going process and execution of the management as described in and in accordance with the rules in the CFMP. It also includes monitoring of this process. The main actors are the CFMG members who execute the activities. The extension agent (FEO at dzongkhag and geog level) helps in the implementation (by providing technical and administrative assistance, monitor the activities, strengthen the CFMG, and make minor revisions in the CFMP when deemed necessary. More specifically, the FEO encourages the CFMG to organise meetings and participates in them, provides technical support and inputs including information, helps settle disputes, helps or trains committee members in record keeping and accounting, provides monitoring information (regarding inputs and impacts) to the DzFO and DFO and enhances the management capabilities of the CFMG.

The main actors in the implementation stage are the CFMG members with a facilitating and monitoring role for the FEO and the SFEC staff.

Review involves the evaluation and revision of the CFMP, at least every five years. The ongoing plan will be evaluated with the whole CFMG to assess the effectiveness against goals, and identify opportunities and problems. Revisions are discussed and the revised plan is put up for approval the same way as the original plan.

It becomes clear that the extension staff, both at dzongkhag as well as project level, have a crucial role in the whole process as the 'glue' between the local community and the government/project. Their task is to create a workable common problem perception at the government-local community interface. If they fail to include the objectives of the local people, the local people can correct this in the CFMP drafting discussion meetings. If they fail to include the government objectives, the DF and in last situation the Director will not recommend/approve of the plan. Thanks to the step-wise process of writing and approving the CFMP, there are many stages at which the local community as well as the government can influence the decision-making process before the actual implementation phase. This in turn prevents a situation in which the implementation phase becomes the main arena of interaction between the government and the community (through the extension agent). It also prevents the extension agent from becoming excessively involved in conflicts between the government and the local people thus severely complicating his position, having to deal with a vast array of contradicting interests as has been documented from other countries, e.g. by Wiersum and Lekanne Dit Deprez (1995). This fact is also recognised in the description of the purpose and mandate of the FED: "Studies carried out in Bhutan have shown that successful extension creates a common problem perception between government and the community. When extension is taken as a one-way approach, the programmes are regarded as for the government alone and failure rates are high. Thus, forestry extension in Bhutan should be taken as a two-way exchange of ideas and concerns that leads to common perceptions of forestry problems and common solutions" (Ministry of Agriculture, 2001).

A critical note has to be placed here. It was the aim of the research to evaluate social forestry interventions in eastern Bhutan from the point of view of the local community that participates in it. As part of the problem statement the external objectives also become involved. Within the limited time frame of this research they were considered as endogenous. In the sense that, the objectives as they appeared from the policy documents of the government and the TFDP were considered as the objectives at all levels. Although these objectives were discussed with the local staff, especially the extension staff, no attempt was made to make an in-depth examination of whether the theoretical objectives were the objectives that the staff put into practice as well.

Chapter 6 Local Objectives

"During our grandparents' time, the motorable road was only till Samdrup Jongkhar. Our ancestors said: 'it will never reach our village'. But then the road reached Trashigang, then Mongar, and now it is even here, in Tangmachhu. It's the same with our plantation. Before, there were no trees. But now there are small ones. And in the future, our children will see a forest. Although we might not be able to reap the benefits in the near future, we put in effort now for the coming generations. They will have to walk less far for their firewood and timber. Still, at the time of our death, we hope at least one darshing (pole for erecting prayer flag erected after death) will come from our own community plantation". - Paraphrased from Mr. Karmala and Mrs. Norbu Choeden, Tshokpektang CP, Tangmachhu, Lhuentse (30/03/2002).

6.1 Introduction

The results of the key-informant, group and individual interviews taken in the four sites in eastern Bhutan are presented in more detail in the Annexes D to H. In the following paragraphs this information has been synthesised in order to present the separate site-wise information as a coherent chapter. To do so the opinions, perspectives and objectives of the community members have been linked up with the objectives regarding forest functions, technical and organisational aspects of management, and external inputs that appeared from the CFMPs. In this way it was possible to retrieve the initial objectives of the local community and compare those to the objectives in the CFMPs, but also get an idea of their current objectives and ideas.

6.2 Objectives Regarding Forest Functions

The functions of the forest can be divided in production functions, ecological, regulatory or service functions, and cultural or religious functions (Wiersum, 1996). For a local community these functions can relate to direct household needs, inputs to the agricultural and livestock production processes, as a source of income, and to provide religious and cultural values. Information on the objectives regarding the functions of the forest as the community had them at the moment of starting the CF/CP was obtained from PRAs and RRAs that were conducted before. However these were only available for Drametse and Tangmachhu. Whereas the TFDP mentioned that partial RRAs had been conducted in Pam and Manam as well, these documents were not available. Therefore for these sites, and to crosscheck the information from the RRAs, the people were asked to state their main objectives again during the group meetings. The following main priorities appeared:

Table 1: Objective Priorities

Forest Product	Dozam CF Drametse	Yezorongpek CP Pam	Tshurgangpek CP Manam	Tshokpektang CP Tangmachhu
Fuel/firewood	(1)	(1)	(2)	(1)
Timber	(2)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Fodder	(5)	-	(4)	(3)
Shingles	(3)	-	(3)	-
Posts and poles	(4)	-	-	-
Bamboo	(6)	-	-	-
Landslide control	-	(3)	-	-
Site improvement	-	(4)	-	-

Non-convergence of Objectives in Social Forestry in Eastern Bhutan

In all sites all the forest products have seen a decrease in availability due to population increase and the subsequent increase in cattle, construction, demand for forest products, outsider extraction and forest fires. Thus among the local participants in the four sites there is a strong general consensus that increasing the availability of fuelwood and timber are the main objectives. The additional two objectives in Pam (control of landslides and making the site look more 'beautiful') can be explained by the fact that the site is located very close to the village and the main road. Thus landslides cause a lot of problems and many people pass the site when travelling on the road. Fodder also occupies an important role in three of the four sites. Since the villagers of Pam have alternative grazing land nearby they did not mention increasing the availability of fodder as an objective. Lastly shingles are a priority in two of the sites, and posts and poles and bamboo only in Drametse.

In Drametse and Pam, lemon grass harvesting was not mentioned as one of the general objectives, but in the plan rules regarding its' utilisation were nonetheless included. To what extent this was done at the communities' request (since lemon grass extraction is an important source of additional income for some farmers) or out of governments' concern (since lemon grass harvesting can have negative side impacts) is unfortunately unclear.

The emphasis of the local community thus mainly lies on the production functions of the forest for household needs (fuel, timber, shingles, post and poles and bamboo) and as input for the livestock production process (fodder). The service function is only an objective in Pam (landslide control and site improvement). The production function of lemon grass extraction for cash income is only of limited importance in Drametse and Pam. The cultural and religious functions are not represented in the visited sites (unless the use of poles for erecting 'darshing' is considered as a religious function). This is mainly due to the fact that no standing forest was present since all the sites were degraded. In other sites where well-stocked forest is included, such as Masang Daza in Mongar (see Box 1), these functions and values are of importance though.

In Drametse, Pam and Tangmachhu an interesting change in objectives became apparent during the discussions. Whereas at the onset of the CF/CP the people had hopes for an increase in a whole range of forest produce, this had by now been reduced. The main reason they mentioned for this was the fact that their experience learnt that species other than chir pine did not thrive well, partly due to the site conditions, partly due to destruction by cattle, and partly due to poor planting techniques. Stating that chir pine would fulfil their most immediate needs of fuelwood and timber, the local people had focussed on plantation of this species. However with more (technical) government assistance they were interested to plant other species as well. It seems that villagers are well aware of the fact that chir pine thrives best under the local site conditions, and since the trees provide them with their most immediate needs, they do not have interest to plant other species. The question remains how chir pine monocultures can provide fodder, a main objective in three of the sites.

6.3 Management Objectives

In contrast to the benefits, which are short term and local, the management responsibility and control over the resource must necessarily be long term for the local participants to be actively involved (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). These management responsibilities can be divided in technical aspects of management and organisational aspects of management (Wiersum, 1996). The technical aspects pertain to a set of deliberate activities for conservation and possible enhancement of resources and controlled utilisation of available benefits, protection and maintenance of the site, and purposeful regeneration. In the visited CF/CPs the people expressed their general satisfaction with the increased responsibility they received over their forest resources, and the fact that they could decide themselves on how to

manage them. Some fears were expressed though that the government might reduce these responsibilities in the future. The people expressed full trust in the activities of the CFMCs.

6.3.1 Technical Aspects

The first technical aspect of management is the *controlling of access to, and harvesting of, the forest resources*. This includes access of the members of the CFMG as well as restricting access to non-members. Benefits accruing from SF projects consist mainly of forest biomass, which in Messerschmidt et al. (2000) is defined as all the resources of a forest, including woody and non-woody materials, of importance to local people and their subsistence livelihoods. In Bhutan this is a key component in the subsistence economy and an integral part of the rural lifestyle, to meet the daily needs of family and household, agriculture and livestock management. An important aspect when considering the benefits is the harvesting and distribution of the forest biomass among the local people. As such rules are necessary governing both the production cycle (which products will become available in which time periods) and the allocation of these products among the legitimate users within the CFMG. Control practices may include harvesting of only selected products and species, harvesting according to condition of the product, limiting the amount of product to be harvested (for example by time, quantity, area or payment), and social means of protecting areas.

All the CFMPs state that in the first plan period there will not be any benefits accruing to the members since the trees will be too small. Therefore there are no utilisation rules specified (except for Dozam CF). In the review of the plans these will be added. The CPMP of Tangmachhu (Forestry Services Division, 1997b) thus states that "*products harvested from the forest will be distributed according to the priorities at the time of harvesting, upon which will be decided during group meetings. This arrangement will be applicable for following management plans*". Similar arrangements are also present in the other CFMPs. Still the people hope to receive at least some benefits in the near future. This research showed a remarkable difference between Drametse, where the people expect benefits to accrue very soon, Pam and Tangmachhu, where the people expressed that the main expectation was for the future, but that they did expect at least some benefits during their own lifetime, and Manam, where there was clearly a long-term vision. As Vergera (1984) had already mentioned, one of the characteristics of SF is that it should focus on the short term and local benefits rather than to be long term and extensive in scale. The preferred species are typically early maturing and multi-purpose, to provide a wide variety of products mainly for local consumption. Most CFMPs mention that the community members prefer fast-growing species to fulfil immediate needs. Wangchuk (1995) recommends that community woodlots should not be established on degraded lands, as the benefits can only be reaped after relatively long time. However there seem to be some undetermined variables that affect people's expectations in SF projects. For Drametse, it seems clear that being located at a site with some mature standing trees, as opposed to the degraded sites elsewhere, the people will be expecting more forest products to become available and at an earlier point in time. Already the site is being used, for example for collecting firewood and lemon grass harvesting. Therefore the rules had to be updated and a complex negotiation process started. For Manam, Tangmachhu and Pam this does not hold however, as the sites are newly planted. The result from Manam seems to directly contradict the theory as mentioned by Vergera (1984) and others. A few Drametse households signed out from the CFMG, due to a lack of immediate benefits, thus supporting the theory.

The Tangmachhu community expressed an important concern regarding the benefits. They feared that, although according to the CFMP and current rules and regulations they would have full control over the utilisation of the products from the CP, the government might change the rules. There is a lack of trust and fear of inconsistency in government policies. In Drametse similar concern was expressed relating to the fines for illegal extraction for members. They did not want to increase these, as they feared the government might not allow a decrease again in the future when they wanted it.

Inter-community heterogeneity was only observed in Drametse, where the people of the internal villages of Bikhari and Thramlu expressed their problems in getting firewood and wanted increased access without having to pay a fee from within the CFMU. Whether the other villages agreed to that is not known.

Lemon grass (*Cymbopogon flexuosus*) distillation is a major source of supplementary cash income generation for many farmer-entrepreneurs and labourers in eastern Bhutan. The grass is a dominant component of chir pine forests. Cattle graze the young growth, but oil extraction is the main use. Through distillation the citrus oil is obtained which is used in the production of Vitamin A and in the flavour, cosmetics and perfumery industries (Wee et al., 1991, Food and Agriculture Organisation, 1996). The oil is exported to Kerala in India and the higher quality oil to Europe. The extraction has largely been in the hands of Tashi Commercial Corporation with a central distillery in Kurizampa and a number of smaller cottage units in different parts of eastern Bhutan. The fuelwood consumption related to the production is estimated at around 4,000 tonnes yearly. Individuals not owning distillation units are often involved in the cutting and transporting of grass to the units. Lemon grass harvesting is only of importance in Drametse and Pam. In Drametse, strict rules have been implemented, including the prohibition of burning the grass, fees for establishing extraction units and fuelwood consumption. The new rules on who can harvest the lemon grass in the CFMU are questionable in fairness, as they seem to favour the larger operators. In Pam there are only fees applied to harvesting for household (Nu. 10/- per bundle) and commercial (Nu. 30/- per bundle) purposes.

All the communities seem determined to keep outsiders out, and rules and fines regarding illegal extraction by non-members have been included in all the CFMPs. In Drametse the fines for illegal extraction have been considerably increased. Even for legal extraction by CFMG members they increased the fees, probably since they realise demand will be exceed supply. Whether this is fair and equitable is questionable however, since poorer households become disadvantaged.

The second technical aspect of management is the *purposeful protection and maintenance of forest stands of desirable quality*. In the visited sites this is the protection of all the existing vegetation within the boundaries of the degraded sites. This mainly boils down to protecting the sites from damage by damaging agents, namely cattle and forest fires. In the CFMP of Manam (Forestry Services Division 1998) it is stated that "*the pilot community plantation success will depend entirely on the interest and commitment of the member households. Forest fire and cattle grazing are the two risks in developing the area. It requires a great deal of effort by the communities to protect seedlings planted until they are well established and future damage is minimised*".

Forest fires are one of the main protection hazards in the chir pine forests of eastern Bhutan (viz. Appendix I). As such all the CFMPs have strict rules prohibiting the setting of forest fire in the plantation and adjacent areas. A yearly returning activity is the cutting of a fire line around the whole plantation site, varying from 2 to 10 meters in width. There are

finer implemented on people getting caught causing a fire, in some cases dependant on whether it was done intentionally (for example for grass rejuvenation) or incidental, whether caused by a member or an outsider, and whether it was inside a planted area or a non-planted area. The fines range from replanting the damaged area to Nu. 5000/- per hectare. In case of fire outbreak all the members are responsible to be present during suppression. There are fines for absentees. In Manam, Pam and Tangmachhu the community members have appointed watchmen/women (shingsumpa) on a turn-wise basis and against a cash or in-kind payment. Their duties are to guard the site against cattle grazing and inform the other members in case a fire is spotted. However the CFMP's also state that *all* members have a responsibility towards this end. In Drametse the discussion was ongoing as to whether, where and how many watchmen to appoint.

Drametse and Tangmachhu have been successful in preventing forest fires from damaging the site. Manam and Pam however have not been that lucky. Although they tried their best to prevent the fire from spreading the nature of the fire made it impossible to do anything (see also Annex J). Due to negligence from project and government side after the fire destroyed their plantation, the people of Manam are unwilling to continue. In Pam the destruction of the plantation by the fire is seen as a great loss, but if the guardian of the culprit who started the fire replants the site they are willing to continue. The success of preventing a site from forest fire seems to depend much more on the location, accessibility, visibility and vegetative condition of the site as well as a large dose of luck rather than community commitment. Even when a community is committed to keeping away the fire, if a fire is started accidentally, in the late afternoon or evening, after a few months of hardly any rain, on a completely dry site with a lot of undergrowth and with a strong wind blowing in a single direction, the ingredients for an all-destructive fire which can not be stopped are available.

Within the traditional subsistence agricultural systems in Bhutan there is little on-farm forage. Thus *cattle grazing* in forests is very intense in some areas, providing the major food source. The productivity of forest grazing land is however very low, and the importance is derived from the large area available (Wee et al., 1991). Forest grazing is especially problematic where it interferes with the regeneration of high-value species (like oak) after logging and where it conflicts with the conservation of biodiversity in unlogged forest through selective grazing of seedlings of palatable tree species (Davidson and Incoll, 1998). Wee et al. (1991) however point out that it is a generalisation to say that the grazing is the primary cause of forest degradation. It is mainly cool broad-leaf forest that is affected by uncontrolled grazing, whereas chir and blue pine forests are less affected as these species are unpalatable to cattle. Whatever may be, unrestrained grazing is a long-standing tradition in Bhutan, and it is difficult to encourage farmers to change their habits.

Fig. 11: Young mithun (bamin) bull. This cattle species is a domesticated form of the gaur (*Bos gaurus*, Dz. rilang, Sh. yeba) and is often crossbred with local cattle to increase meat production and hardiness. The mithun is always left free to browse in the forest. Government mithun breeding farms are located in Erong (Samdrup Jongkhar) and Wangkha (Chukha). In Northeastern India (mainly Arunachal Pradesh) the mithun is called gayal, and has a similar economic as well as a ceremonial role.

Although providing an area for cattle to graze is one of the functions that the forest has for the local community, grazing has been included here under management objectives. The reason for this is that officially, under the rules governing all the CFMPs, cattle grazing is strictly prohibited in order to protect the seedlings from destruction. As such, the forest no longer functions as a grazing area.

To prevent cattle from destroying the saplings in a CP or CF site, there are various methods that can be applied. The first one is barbed wire fencing, in which barbed wire is nailed to poles or sometimes to live trees all round the plantation. The second option is social fencing, the practice of protecting a site by common understanding among local people to control animal and human access without physical restraint. The last option is live fencing, the establishment of a boundary of live plant material thick enough to prevent cattle from passing through. Due to the size of most CP and CF sites, the last option has not been implemented. It is mainly used to protect agricultural fields and small plantations near the house. The size of the CP and CF sites also means that the first option has not been implemented. The CFMG itself can not buy the barbed wire, and the government and project have thus far been unwilling to provide it. Strikingly though, in afforestation and reforestation sites in western Bhutan with a similar size barbed wire and poles have been provided.

In all the CFMPs it is clearly stated that grazing of cattle within the plantation is not permitted until the seedlings have grown above the browsing height of the cattle (a minimum time span varying from 2 years in Drametse to 8 years in Manam and Pam). In the absence of other options, all CFMPs have provisions for social fencing agreements. Cattle herders are urged to restrain their cattle from entering the plantation area. Fines are imposed on both member and non-member households whose cattle is found in the plantation area. These fines vary from Nu. 25/- per cattle plus Nu. 50/- per destroyed sapling and replantation, to the confiscation of cattle and subsequent surrender to the dzongkhag authorities for further action.

The success of social fencing has been mixed and seems dependent on the number of cattle using the area and the distance from the site to the village. Manam is facing most problems due to the large number of cattle (up to 600 heads) using the area and the fact that the site is located out of sight of the village. They thus can't control the grazing and moreover feel it is socially problematic to keep fining perpetrators since it will lead to bad relations and conflicts. Most of the cattle come from adjoining villages, especially during wintertime, and they do no longer wish to worsen the relations with their neighbours. Therefore they have many times requested barbed wire fencing but they didn't receive it. Now they want to stop with the plantation. Many CFMGs have indicated willingness to transport barbed wire and poles from the road head to the site, and then construct a fence along the site combining the poles with live trees. But in eastern Bhutan it has not been government nor project policy to provide this. In Drametse the grazing problem is less serious, although it is one of the reasons that mainly chir pine seedlings have been planted. The site is very big and difficult to oversee, and the number of cattle is high as well. Now they are thinking of imposing permanent watchmen in the area. In Tangmachhu and Pam the number of cattle is limited, the site is closely located to and well visible from the village, alternative grazing land is available, and the fines are considered very high. Thus the social fencing is successful there.

The third technical aspect of management encompasses the *purposeful propagation of valuable species*. This may consist of assisted natural regeneration, seeding, vegetative propagation by cuttings and nursery-raised seedlings, and optimisation of the micro-climate and soil (Wiersum, 1996). The natural regeneration of tree species at all sites is supposed to be protected from damage. Broadcast seeding of chir pine seeds has only been done in

Drametse. The main focus has been on plantation of seedlings, both from government and private nurseries as well as from community nurseries. The micro-climatic and soil conditions for these seedlings were improved as well, for example by adding manure in the dug holes and by removing undergrowth around the seedlings. The plantation activities form the major part of the propagation of valuable species (most commonly chir pine). They are governed by rules explained in the CFMPs. These have a detailed 'plan of activities', which states the kind of activity, the month in which this is due to take place, who has to participate and for how long, and fines on absenteeism of Nu. 50/- per day. The activity schedule for all sites looks similar (viz. table 3), and all members are expected to be present. The number of seedlings each household has to plant is decided during the annual meetings and depends on the availability of seedlings. During the spacing and stacking, plantation and fire line cutting activities the FEO is often present to give technical advice and oversee the activities.

Fig. 13: In Social Forestry activities the management becomes mainly the responsibility of the local participants in the project. Here the inhabitants of Waichur, Bikhur and Thramlu villages gather for a group photo after a day of discussion on the new CFMP (05/04/2002).

Table 2: Plan of Activities

Activity	Months (Western)	Responsibility
Spacing and stacking	April, May	All CFMG members
Site cleaning	April, May	All CFMG members
Pit digging and manuring	June	All CFMG members
Seedling collection from roadhead	May, June	All CFMG members
Plantation	June, July	All CFMG members
Weeding and cleaning (twice to thrice)	August, September, October	All CFMG members
Refilling of pits (in case seedlings died)	June, July of following year	All CFMG members
Fire line cutting	October	All CFMG members
Fire and grazing control	Whole year round, but mainly October to April	All CFMG members, main duty for watchmen/women

In Manam and Tangmaehhu there was no problem with the labour inputs for the various activities. All the households including those with limited manpower were able to participate in all the activities. In Pam a few problems occurred but these were internally settled. All CPs have made special consideration rules for households with domestic problems and special cases. In Drametse a few households did not provide labour due to absenteeism

from the village and their names would be deleted from the CFMG. A few households that signed out stated lack of manpower as the reason. The review of the CFMP will also see an updating of the rules and fines.

Every CFMP has the provision that community nurseries should be established to provide the plantation site with seedlings. The government would pay for the seedlings raised, both in private and community nurseries, and these would be planted in their own plantation or elsewhere. Although the private nurseries at Drametse, Tangmachhu and Manam have been successful, the community nurseries have been a failure in Tangmachhu. The members lost interest as the government did not have budget to buy the seedlings, and they shifted responsibilities for the care of the seedlings. In Pam the people voiced the opinion that they did not see the need for a community nursery, since the rate the government provided for the seedlings is too low and the government provides them for free anyway. In Drametse the discussion on whether to establish a community nursery or not is currently ongoing.

6.3.2 Organisational Aspects

The organisational aspects of management include the process of decision making on objectives of forest management (see 6.1), the kinds of activities carried out by certain people at certain times (see 6.2.1), the equitable distribution of benefits (see 6.2.1), and the control over proper execution of the plans (Wiersum, 1996). In many ways the organisational aspects coincide with the technical aspects of management. The remaining organisational aspects are presented in the CFMPs under the 'constitution and by-laws'. These state the following:

- The member households of the CFMG;
- If and how other households can become a member of the CFMG. In all cases this new membership is restricted to households that have formed after separation from existing households, for example when children start an own household;
- How members who withdraw are treated. They lose all the rights they had to the CF/CP and its products and have no permission to rejoin;
- The rights and responsibilities of the members. These include equal access to resources as the main right, and attendance and contribution to meetings and discussions, participation in activities, reporting the violation of rules, and monitoring and controlling the activities of the management committee as the main duties;
- When the community meetings will be held, with both annual and ad-hoc meetings. Fines are levied for non-presence of a household;
- The composition, selection, tenure and functions of the executive committee;
- The sources of money for the community funds, mainly the collection of fees and fines, and how it would be managed;
- Conflict resolution by the management committee, and if necessary forward to the DzFO and gup/chimi or dzongkhag court;
- The monitoring and evaluation process both internal by the CFMG as well as external by the DzFO and DFO.

All the community members were satisfied with the existing organisational rules that were written in and approved by them when the CFMP was composed. In the meantime, during the implementation phase, they were not disappointed with the rules. In Tangmachhu, some problems occurred due to the fact that the CFMP did not contain a fully elaborated constitution and by-laws. During subsequent meetings the community adjusted this themselves and by consensus introduced new rules that would be included in the updated CFMP (this also shows the increased institutional and decision-making capacity that has

formed among the CFMG). The rules on the executive (management) committee were not always strictly followed. In most cases, the chairman and secretary of the CFMG had remained the same. When the members were asked about why the duties had not been transferred to other elected members, they replied that, if the CFMG was satisfied with the execution of duties by the executive committee, they could be reinstalled for another term. Till date there have been no new members to any of the CFMGs. In Drametse, there were six households that did not provide the required labour and would be deleted from the CFMG, loosing all the rights to the forest and its products. The compulsory attendance to CFMG meetings by at least one member from each household has led to situations when, if the meeting is held during busy times, unqualified people are sent to the meetings. This is described in more detail in Annex L. Any conflicts have been internally solved in all the cases. In Manam the money from the community fund was given as loan to a member upon mutual agreement by all the members. In Tangmachhu no fund had been established. In Pam and Drametse the decision over the money in the fund would only be made in the future.

6.4 External Inputs

The provision of external inputs can consist of technical assistance, financial incentives, extension services, marketing co-operation, and provision of access to land (Wiersum, 1996). As per the CFMPs the government provided the access to land (government reserved forestland), free seedlings for plantation and guaranteed demand for seedlings grown in community and private nurseries as financial incentives, and technical assistance (through extension). The DzFO and DFO also have a duty in monitoring and controlling of the proper implementation of the CFMP according to the rules mentioned in them. To this extent they or their deputies (FEO and forest guards) are required to pay regular visits to the site and see whether this has happened. In case of non-compliance to the rules they have the right to take corrective measures. The DzFO is also required to write a progress report at least on annual basis and if and when it is required. This report is to be submitted to the Department of Forestry Services. If the community repeatedly or severely fails to comply with the rules and duties as set out in the CFMP, and refuses or fails to correct the failure, the Department of Forestry Services has the right to revoke the certificate.

The people of Pam, Drametse and Tangmachhu were satisfied with the government inputs and control. Only in Manam did the people express severe dissatisfaction with both the government and project assistance. Not only did they not receive any help after the plantation was destroyed by fire; the government didn't mediate between the nursery owner and a private organisation, which didn't pay for seedlings. They had also requested fencing materials on several occasions, but never got it. The blame for this all seem to lie mainly with the former DzFO, who was not dedicated to his work, and didn't convey the grievances of the community to the higher government and project authorities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 [Non-] Convergence in Objectives

This research was originally aimed at evaluating SF interventions in eastern Bhutan from the point of view of the local participants. This aim was later specified and a more workable problem statement and research objectives were written. The focus of the research moved towards the non-convergence of local and external (government/project) objectives. This non-convergence has been observed in many SF projects around the world.

During the course of this research a general non-convergence in objectives was not observed in social forestry in eastern Bhutan. Referring back to the origins of different perspectives of sustainable forest management in general and social forestry interventions in particular (see chapter 2.3) a number of remarks can be made. According to Wiersum (1999b), there are three causes or origins of different perspectives that in turn lead to the normative pluriformity in perceptions, ideas, objectives and expectations towards social forestry interventions.

Firstly Wiersum mentions the *different perspectives on forest resources and different values attached to forest functions*. Not only government and project on the one hand and the local community on the other may have different perspectives, even within these actor groups there are differences. As can be concluded from chapter 5, the perspectives the government and the TFDP project have on the forest resources and the values they attach to the forest functions are rather congruent. As mentioned in chapter 5.2, considering that the role of the project has been *facilitating* the national social forestry programme in eastern Bhutan, rather than having its own set of objectives regarding social forestry, the government and project objectives have been taken as a single entity. This is confounded by the fact that the objectives they have towards the social forestry interventions they support are similar. As was assumed in chapter 3.1, the common perception of the problem will result in such similar objectives. Similarly, with minor variations, which are caused by a difference in location rather than a difference in perspectives, the local communities of all four sites have the common objective of increasing the availability of firewood and timber. As is reported in the previous paragraphs, the objectives regarding forest functions, management responsibility and external inputs are all rather similar and thus based upon a common understanding of the situation and the problem that social forestry intends to address.

So the perspectives *within* the two broad actor groups, namely within the government and the project and within the local communities, do not differ to the extent that this seems to reflect normative pluriformity. However *between* these two groups there are some differences. In a superficial comparison of local and external objectives there seems to be little similarity. The local people strongly stress increasing the availability of timber and fuelwood as their overriding objective. By contrast the government and the project have expressed other objectives besides increasing the availability of forest products for the local people as well, such as rehabilitation of degraded areas and the empowerment of, and institutional capacity building among, the population of rural areas. Although these are not direct and specific objectives of the local community, indirectly they are of importance. Without rehabilitation of the degraded forestlands near the village the availability of timber and fuelwood will not increase. And without their true participation in the management, their access to and control of the forest resources will not improve either. On the other hand, without the government

allowing the local community to harvest and use the forest products they are in greatest need of, they will not participate in the project and no rehabilitation will take place either. Thus external and local objectives are intricately linked and dependent upon each other, and are made to reconcile in the CFMPs.

This becomes obvious when looking at the individual CFMPs. The objectives mentioned in them are a combination of the objectives of the national SF program (and as a consequence the SF component of the TFDP) and the objectives of the local community. It is probably thanks to the late introduction of SF in eastern Bhutan that the objectives are so closely related. Obviously lessons were learnt from the rest of the world and the woodlot programme in western Bhutan. The TFDP project provided experienced and dedicated SF staff consultants who assisted and trained the local extension staff from both the project and the government side in participatory techniques. By making use of RRA and PRA right from the planning phase it has been possible to retrieve the local people's objectives and incorporate them in the CFMPs. In this way the experience of the Sahel, India and Nepal, where the implementation phase of the projects became the principal arena of interaction, was avoided. As Wiersum and Lekanne Dit Deprez (1995) describe, this led to a situation in which the policies of the project were adjusted by the local people to suit their own needs, leading to a failure of the program through conscious withdrawal from or ritual acceptance of the project. This was due to the fact that the local people did not have access to decision-making right from the start.

The only non-convergence exists in the accrual of benefits. Whereas in SF programmes the benefits should preferably occur on the short term, the chosen form of all the CP projects and Dozam CF (on degraded forestland) results in benefits on the long term only. However, the local people realise this and therefore it has not led to many problems. The third objective from the national SF programme, developing forest based home and cottage industries to improve income and the social-economic position of the rural people, is hardly an objective of the local people. Only in Drametse the harvest and sale or own extraction of lemon grass oil is of some economic importance to a limited number of participants. In the other sites the collection of phinshing and chorgenshing fruits is of negligible importance. The main reason for this seems to be that no natural forest is available. More importantly, the people stress the fact that they participated in the CF/CP project only to increase the availability of fuelwood and timber for their own domestic needs, and not for commercial sale.

To summarise, the objectives in the CFMPs seem partly externally derived, such as the objective of rehabilitation of degraded sites and assuring a sustainable production in the future and the objective of improving the socio-economic condition of the community and income generation. One of the key features of SF that Vergera (1984) mentions is that it is also mainly concerned with the non-monetary local economy. This seems to be supported by this research, as the local community has as overriding objective to increase the availability of forest products for their own household use. They do not focus on sale of the products (except for lemon grass in Drametse and Pam, which has limited household use). Only Pam community has additional objectives (control of landslides and beautification of the site).

However in general it can be stated that due to the participatory nature of the social forestry interventions in eastern Bhutan from the planning phase onwards the objectives of the local community have been sufficiently included in both the objectives regarding forest functions as well as the management and external input objectives of the CFMPs. This is a remarkable change since the research by Wangchuk (1995) who observed that the external objectives have been overriding any objectives of the local community in community plantations in western Bhutan. It seems that in the visited sites the management plans have absorbed and thus expressed what the local participants have wanted. This is also clear from

the fact that during the Drametse review there were no changes to the objectives, and only changes to the things that should naturally be updated now that the site evolves. In general the local people are very satisfied with the CPs and CF. Much of the credit for this should go to the extension agents and their dedicated works. The only exception is Manam, a site that can be labelled as a failure. This case however strengthens the notion that forestry extension is of paramount importance to social forestry programs.

Secondly Wiersum refers to the *broad variety of forest types under community management*. In Eastern Bhutan the sites are all similar, degraded forestlands whose natural vegetation would consist of chir pine with lemon grass and shrub undergrowth. The sites all have the character of a plantation with little natural forest cover. Only in Manam and Drametse did some natural vegetation still occur in the gorges of inaccessible perennial streams. With regard to trees in other landscape niches within the village boundaries, such as in house compounds, on the fields, along farm boundaries and in orchards, these are the subject of the national and TFDP private forestry/agroforestry programme, and therefore lie beyond the scope of this research.

Lastly he mentions the *wide variety of indigenous and professional management practices*. In the CPs and CFs in eastern Bhutan, on sites which have been degraded for a long period of time and where forest management has not been practised, traditional and indigenous knowledge on how to manage the forest have been largely eroded. Moreover the sites are all new plantations and thus there is little 'forest' to be managed. Only in a few cases did indigenous knowledge appear present, namely the recognition of the local people that chir pine is one of the few species (if not the only) that will grow well on these sites and the dual effect of lemon grass harvesting on seedling survival observed by the people of Shaphangma (see Annex D). In regard to professional forest management practices, the forest guards and forest rangers (divisional and dzongkhag) have all had a similar training. Therefore the practices they apply and pass on to the local people are not much different.

Thus out of the three origins of normative pluriformity only the first one, different perspectives on forest resources and different values to forest functions, seems to be partially of importance in eastern Bhutan.

7.2 Reasons for Success and Failure

The virtual absence of significant problems as a result of conflicting objectives caused by normative pluriformity does not mean that the SF projects have been successful in all aspects. There have been minor problems in all the sites, and Manam has been most unsuccessful (to the extent of being a complete failure). When it can not be attributed to a non-convergence in external and local objectives, what are the main reasons for this?

Wangchuk (1995) mentioned already that the most important factors influencing the success of community woodlots in western Bhutan were a common problem perception within the local community, a common problem perception between the local community and the government (assisted by forest extension), the size of the planting area, and the distance from the woodlot to the village. Other factors that affect the woodlot were local leadership and community organisation, the availability of and perceived need for tree products, the economic benefits, and supervision during planting. He attributed the failure of the Walakha and Gubji community woodlots to a lack of forestry extension, a lack of inter-community homogeneity, the absence of local leadership, and the large size of the site and distance to the

village. The lack of forestry extension in the Walakha woodlot had resulted in a situation where the farmers were completely unaware of the government objectives, policy and rules. Thus they considered the woodlot as a government plantation and this resulted in a lack of enthusiasm and commitment. During this research in eastern Bhutan the importance of most of these factors was acknowledged and confirmed. Two 'new' factors have been distinguished, namely the outside threat and the site conditions.

The table below shows that out of the four visited sites, three can be called a success to a more or lesser degree. A ++ means that the factor for the site is very important (or a very strong influence), a + important, a +/- neutral, and - unimportant. The factors are discussed separately below.

Table 3: Factors for Success and Failure

Factor/Site	Dozam CF Drametse	Yezorongpek CP Pam	Tshurgangpek CP Manam	Tshokpektang CP Tangmachhu
Success/failure	S	S	F	S
Community homogeneity and co-operation	+	++	+	++
Site accessibility and visibility	+/-	++	-	+
-Fire control	+/-	+	-	+
-Grazing control	+/-	++	-	+
Site conditions	+/-	-	-	+
Site size	-	+	+	+
Dedication DzFO/FEO	+	++	-	+
Perceived need	+	+	++	+
Benefits	+	+/-	-	+/-
Outside threat/extraction	+	-	+/-	-

Community characteristics/homogeneity: At community level a surprising homogeneity of objectives at community level was observed in all sites. Traditionally, farming households in eastern Bhutan are individualistic in nature. But villagers are also very much reliant on each other. Due to the small and transparent society there are close-knit socio-economic, cultural, religious and ancestral ties between the households in a village and between villages as well. In order to survive in the harsh conditions, a farmer household can not be too individualistic lest it be excluded from the community it relies on. This reliance shows itself in for example indigenous systems of labour sharing, irrigation water sharing, performance of religious ceremonies and cattle herding. The socio-economic situation of most households is also rather homogenous. There are no 'rich' and 'poor' households, just 'richer' and 'poorer' ones, based on the land holdings and the number of cattle owned and, increasingly, on the money received from family members employed away from the village. With respect to social forestry interventions, homogeneity clearly shows for example in the provision of labour, the attendance of meetings, the development of own initiative, the level of co-operation during activities, and the prevention of forest fires and grazing. Only in Drametse did heterogeneity of objectives come to the surface, due to the large user group and the fact that three villages were located inside the CFMU itself. However this did not have considerable effect on the success of the site. Only in the case of community nurseries did shifting of responsibilities take place. The lack of success of community nurseries however can also be attributed to the government policy of providing free seedlings, and paying for

them if they are grown by private or community nurseries (Thinley et al., 1998; Wangdi et al., 1998).

Site accessibility/visibility/size: These three factors are important determinants for success with regard to forest fire and grazing prevention. The further away the site is from the village and/or the less visible and/or the larger the size, the more difficult it is to detect and fight forest fires and prevent grazing. Another important factor is the availability of alternative grazing land. The presence of grazing land at not too much distance from the old grazing land at the CF/CP site, such as in Tangmachhu and Pam, considerably reduces the number of cattle grazing within the plantation. Manam is located on a steep and difficult to access site out of sight from the village, decreasing the chance of sighting cattle and fire and the opportunities to fight it. Messerschmidt et al. (2000:167, 168) mention as one of the greatest measures of success of the SF program in eastern Bhutan the fact that during the forest fire season of early 2000 none of the CF or CP sites had been destroyed by forest fire. This is said to reflect villager dedication to manage and protect the forest resource under their protection. Whereas forest fires are often very difficult to stop once out of control, the report states that the CF and CP members manage to protect their own forest from fire. To take absence of forest fire at the site as a criterion of success however seems a bit blunt, as the fires are often uncontrollable. Especially in case of small communities such as Pam and Manam it is difficult to do anything. Even Manam could be termed 'successful' until its destruction by fire. It seems mainly the physical factors such as these that affect that success of CF/CP in eastern Bhutan.

A long-term constraint faced by the Tshokpektang CP in Tangmachhu is the lack of sufficient land to plant for forestry. Much of the available degraded land suitable for forestry development is private sokshing owned by an absentee landowner. This is observed in other sites as well. Although it seems there is a lot of 'empty' land surrounding villages, this is actually referred to as 'chamsai sago' (Dz.) or 'changme ga sa' (Sh.), 'playing grounds' for both children and cattle.

Site condition: The conditions at the sites are all almost similar and characterised by a natural vegetation of chir pine and grass undergrowth. They are to a large extent, if not fully, degraded with only sparse trees. The main vegetation consists of grasses, mainly lemon grass, and small bushes and shrubs. The sites are dry especially in winter and prone to forest fires, fuelled by strong winds. Soils are often rocky and little fertile. The main difference between the sites is the slope. Whereas Tshokpektang CP is located on a very gentle slope, Dozam CF has very variable slope conditions, and Tshurgangpek CP and Yezorongpek CP are on steep and difficultly accessible slopes. These conditions greatly affect the success of the sites. Tree species other than chir pine do not grow well due to these conditions. Moreover species other than chir pine are very easily destroyed by fire and cattle. The soil condition makes planting saplings difficult and the soil rockiness and dryness reduce the sapling survival rate. The planting of different species was attempted but failed, and as a result the objective of increasing the availability of a wider range of forest products was changed to a focus on products that chir pine could provide (i.e. mainly timber and fuelwood). This was observed in Tangmachhu, Pam and Drametse. However, if the survival rate of other species could be improved, the people were willing to plant these as well.

Fig. 13: The plantation at Tangmachhu (Tshokpektang): one of the Social Forestry success stories in Eastern Bhutan.

Forestry extension: It has become clear that after the initial phase of failure in community plantations in western Bhutan and the recommendations by Wangchuk (1995) in this respect a lot has improved in regard to the forestry extension in Bhutan. As described in chapter 5.3, the process of planning and implementation of CF/CP sites in eastern Bhutan has from the start been participatory. Thus a common problem perception between the government and the local community was established and maintained by the extension agents from the government and the project. The technical backstopping (as also described in all the CFMPs) is one of the main responsibilities of the government towards the CF/CPs. In turn the government and project heavily rely on the extension agents (DzFO and FEO) who form the main vital link between local people and government/project. Where the extension agent is dedicated, the technical backstopping is good, and the chances of success increase. This is the case in Drametse, Pam and Tangmachhu. In both Pam, Tangmachhu and Drametse the DzFO/FEOs had long experience in the field and a good professional and individual relationship with the people. That way they were an effective and vital link between the local people and the government as well as between the local people themselves. Where the extension agent has failed in his role, such as the previous extension staff in Yangtse, the project also fails. The much-needed technical advice after the destruction of Manam CP was never received, because the higher authorities never became aware of the problem. Another factor here might be the remoteness of the site, which might not have encouraged any of the staff to visit it.

Although the organisation of forestry extension in Bhutan is still hierarchical, it provides definite options for a participatory approach. It comes close to the linear and two-way communication model that has often been described as the 'ideal' forestry extension model (viz. chapter 2.2; Wiersum, 1999b; Messerschmidt et al., 2000). In this model the extension agent is seen as the final implementer of the forest policy with local co-operation. Although this model has been challenged (in for example Wiersum and Lekanne Dit Deprez (1995) and Wiersum (1999b) where forestry is seen as a conglomeration of parties putting the forestry agent in a delicate position rather than as a coherent organisational system) it seems to be functioning rather well in Bhutan. Although the strategy of the forestry extension agent

is still conservative, risk-minimising and one of arming himself against uncertainty, there are no incentives for this strategy to develop into corruption and making him the 'primary target' of the local people.

Fig. 14: The Yezorongpek Community Plantation in Pam after destruction by fire. The occurrence of forest fires is one of the greatest threats to the success of Social Forestry activities in Eastern Bhutan.

Benefits: The benefits have been discussed in detail in 6.2 and 6.3.1. A problem occurs when the local people expect them at the short term, whereas due to the nature of plantations these will only occur in the longer term. Even though they seem aware of this fact, most people are still expecting benefits in the near future. Only in a few cases in Drametse did the lack of immediate benefits lead to withdrawal. As discussed in chapter 7.1 this is the only reason for success and failure related to the normative plurality of objectives. The project and government in most cases stress short-term objectives but the choice of sites can only result in long-term benefits, and the local communities have very variable time spans of expectations of benefits.

Perceived need: As the objectives of the local communities show, the acute shortages of forest-related products are the main reasons for the local people to request for establishment of a CF/CP. This perceived need and the hope for a solution is also the impetus that keeps them interested and committed.

Threat: The threat of outside extraction has been discussed in Chapter 2.2. A real threat was observed in Drametse, where people from outside would come to extract lemon grass from the CFMU, and sometimes also other forest products. In Manam the threat came mainly from cattle from other villages and cross-border intruders from India.

Government policy: One of the biggest constraints to CF development has been the perceived risk and controversy attached to CF development as a result of the experiences in Gongthung, Trashigang (viz. Messerschmidt et al., 2000:127). The delay in the authorisation of the reviewed Social Forestry Rules 1996 also hampered the developments and brought concern to both TFDP staff as well as fieldworkers. No one wished to risk embarrassment in front of villagers by their inability to deliver on promises. These two reasons brought a virtual halt to CF development from 1997 till 2000 (Kcill et al., 1998; Evans et al., 1996; Messerschmidt et

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aL, 2000; Namgyel and Chopel, 2001). Sometimes it seems as if the trust and support from the higher authorities is insufficiently present. Therefore the national level institutional structures require clarification on roles, authority and responsibilities of the territorial, dzongkhag and RNR sector staff. Tenzing et al. (2001) observed the same problem in plantation projects in western Bhutan.

Only when the Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of 2000 were issued did the process pick up again. Primary focus had till then been on establishment of CP sites, as this does not involve handing over of any well-stocked forest. Thus the government, also in the absence of clear-cut rules, appeared less weary to approve of these plans. The main reason however is that the CF rules and regulations have been under constant discussion in the past years and only the approval of the FNCR in 2000 has made clear what exactly is possible in this field within the government rules. Now that the rules are firmly established, it can be expected that more CF and CP sites whose approval has been kept pending will be approved, since it is clear to which rules and regulations they have to comply.

Relating to that, another main reason for failure has been the lack of firm guarantees about the future of the local communities' investments in tree resource development. The only guarantee as yet is that there is no guarantee- this situation inevitably weakens farmer incentives to pursue SF. Their participation seems therefore based on their sense of justice and trust rather than legal guarantees from the government side (Messerschmidt et al.; 2000, Namgyel and Chopel, 2001). This has been observed in Yangmacbhu regarding the future utilisation of benefits and in Drametse regarding the level of fines. In both cases the community was worried that the government might change the rules again in the future.

In short, government policy does not directly affect the problem perception and objectives of the local community. However it does affect the success and failure of CF and CP projects through the influence it exerts on the action the government takes in relation to the projects.

In light of all the above, it seems that the research framework of chapter 3.1 ought to be extended with a number of other factors beside the common problem perception and objectives between the local community and the government. There seem to be many more factors affecting the success of social forestry interventions in Bhutan, and probably in general. Figure 15 gives a broad overview of the factors and relations that have been established thus far.

Site characteristics refers here to the physical site conditions such as precipitation and slope, but also to the size, visibility and accessibility of the site as discussed above. Technical characteristics refer here for example to the way of planting and other factors affecting the species survival rate. Community characteristics refer to community size, homogeneity and interest. Accrual of benefits means when and which benefits the community expects to receive. This is closely related to their perceived need such as shortage of forest products. Outside threat can also be an important factor affecting the local problem perception. The central role of forestry extension also becomes apparent. From the discussions with the community members, the site and technical characteristics and the government policy appear to be the most influential factors.

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Fig. 15: Factors affecting success and failure

7.3 Recommendations

Recent developments: Social forestry in Bhutan is still young and continues to evolve and develop. The sector has had a number of major boosts in the recent years, mainly the introduction of clear-cut rules and regulations and the assistance provided by the TFDP. In August 2002 the Kuensel in its online edition reported on the 'Participatory Forest Management Project', funded by the Swiss Development Corporation/Helvetas and aimed at the promotion of participatory forest management by local communities on both private and public land. It will focus on both sustainable forest management as well as income generation for local farmers in seven dzongkhag, including the eastern dzongkhag of Lhuentse, Mongar and Trashigang. The project will be incorporated in the decentralisation process in the 9th Five Year Plan, which means that it will be mainly executed by the govt-level staff of the Ministry of Agriculture. These developments show that Bhutan is serious in its efforts to promote social forestry activities. The following recommendations can hopefully contribute to those efforts.

Upgrading CPs to CFs: The benefits of CPs and a CF like Dozam (consisting mainly of degraded forest) only accrue to the local people after a considerable number of years of hard effort and investment. The people are often more interested to include natural, well-stocked forest into their CF as well (i.e. extend it beyond CP), rather than the sole focus on the

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rehabilitation of degraded forest areas. This will provide them with immediate benefits, rather than having to wait for many years. The long-term sustainability of the CP sites is also questioned in Messerschmidt et al. (2000). The sites are often small, participating groups very large, the sites have a poor resource base, and the community consists of scattered settlements. These difficult institutional conditions can create future problems, for example with regard to division of a few resources among many people. Now that the new FNCR allow inclusion of well-stocked forest under certain rules and regulations, there is more scope for this. Sites such as Yakpugang and Masang Daza in Mongar have already shown this, including larger areas of natural forest. It is recommended that instead of putting human and financial resources in the establishment of new CPs, first and foremost the opportunities and limitations should be examined whether the existing CPs can be enlarged and upgraded to CFs. This especially holds for the site at Tangmachhu, where both funds and scope are available (viz. Appendix H)

Site location and fencing arrangements: The main problems the CP and CF sites face lie with forest fire protection and grazing. Wangchuk (1995: 56) already mentioned that 'local people consider barbed wire as indispensable for success' and since the need was apparently there this should be taken seriously. It is therefore recommended that in sites where social fencing has proven unsuccessful, the government should provide the fencing materials when the people request for it. Thus in Manam the fencing material should be provided in order to encourage the people to continue the plantation. In the first place, however, prevention is better than cure. Thus it is recommended that sites which are prone to grazing by a large number of cattle, and which are located at too much distance (or otherwise out of direct sight) of the residences of the CFMP members.

Improving seedling provision: Shortage of seedlings occasionally occurs and at the same time nursery operators face problems in finding buyers for their seedlings, especially when the government has run out of budget. Messerschmidt et al. (2000) mention that private nurseries until now have only worked because of artificial subsidies (the guaranteed purchase of seedlings by government agencies). However the creation of good commercial markets would be a better way to encourage farmers and CFMGs to start private nurseries (Thinley et al., 1998, Wangdi et al., 1998). This would also provide an incentive for community nurseries to work more efficiently than they have done till date. The provision of free seedlings however is a very important feature, and if it would be withdrawn, the interest would disappear. If CFMGs have to purchase seedlings on a commercial market, the government should pay them for those seedlings.

Institutional capacity at national and district level: Field staff members are in some respects not well prepared to live up to their duties as 'modern' foresters, and additional training, especially in participatory techniques, is deemed necessary (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). The current curriculum at the NRTI however includes these techniques, and the latest batches of foresters passing out from the Institute all seem reasonable aware and experienced.

The staff also faces equipment and transportation shortages, which makes it difficult for them to execute their work properly. In the dzongkhag headquarters computers have been provided only recently, but in the geog the situation is often very basic, with no electricity, many days of walking, and lack of materials (for example big sheets and markers for participatory planning). For the past few years, the TFDP has been providing these materials. It is questionable how the FSD will now continue to provide these materials now that the TFDP is closed down.

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The linkages between the dzongkhag and geog and the FED in Thimphu are also weak and unclear and lacking in adequate conceptual support to the field (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). This was observed in the field as well, with CFMPs taking a very long time to get approval. This often resulted in uncertainty and loss of interest by the local community. As the government policy has been well established, it is expected (and observed) that the process will be much faster now.

Institutional capacity at local level: Messerschmidt et al. (2000) remark that CFMGs still need considerable guidance in creating and maintaining workable management systems and structures. This is not per definition a failure, as the approach is still rather new. It has to be expected however that after some time the local people should be enabled to work together in similar management systems without outside intervention. The Mongar DzFO and FEO noticed some remarkable changes in the community. These changes, including increased sense of responsibility for the management of the forest resources under their care, were observed in the field as well. The members noted lapses in their CFMPs themselves and solved them, and most meetings were organised by themselves. Continued practice and exposure to community-level planning and implementation will increase the skills of the local people, which will be useful to them in other activities as well.

Future research: The 9th FYP of Bhutan will focus very strongly on the decentralisation process onwards from the dzongkhag to the geog level. Thus, the 202 geog in Bhutan will receive more responsibilities, including development budget allocation. One of the components will be the enhanced development of local institutions for management, utilisation and conservation of natural resources (Kinga, 2002). It would be interesting to see whether community-level management of natural resources in Bhutan as part of the decentralisation policies in the 9th FYP could mean a more effective and efficient means to conserve and utilise the natural resources as compared to government intervention. At the same time, the lessons learnt in SF projects and the experience the people have gained in managing their own resources can be applied to ensure smooth and effective local governance.

The lack of knowledge on traditional/indigenous forest management systems in Bhutan is another field that urgently requires further research. It can not be assumed that the past 30 years of centralised forest management have completely wiped out all the knowledge that existed before. As the practice of *riadam* and the example in Masang Daza show there is still a lot of practice and knowledge present. Without proper documentation it might go lost before efficient use of it can be made, not only in SF projects but in other fields as well.

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Annex C: Community Forestry Development in Eastern Bhutan

Status as per April 2001 (TFDP, Khangma)

Dzong-khag	Geog	Site name	CF/CP	Total area (ha)	Legal tenure	CFMG members	Mgt. Plan prep.	Mgt. Plan approved	Certificate issued
Lhuentee	Menbi	Tshokpek-tang	CP	3.24	GRF	19	Completed	June 3 rd , 1998	May 27 th , 1999
	Jaray	Nganey	CP	9	GRF	33	Completed	March 2002: not approved	-
Mongar	Drametse	Dozam	CF	200	GRF	103	Completed	April 1997	September 17 th , 1997
	Mongar	Yakpugang	CF	260	GRF	42 + 61	Completed	May 2001	October 24 th , 2001
	Saleng	Masang Daza	CF	100	GRF	31	Completed	-	-
Yangtse	Toe-tsho	Tshurgang-pek	CP	5.26	GRF	27	Completed	December 11 th , 1998	October 27 th , 1999
	Kham-dang	Shangshang Phola	CP	4.05	Sok-shing	68	Completed	October 5 th , 1999	October 27 th , 1999
Trashigang	Yang-nyer	Gochadrang	CF	337	GRF	161	Completed	Cancelled 1999	-
	Yang-nyer	Tholong Pangthang	CP	10	Tsam-dro	210	Completed	June 11 th , 1999	June 15 th , 1999
	Khaling	Joensham Lamdroksa	CP	329.9	Tsam-dro	139	Completed	April 16 th , 2002	-
	Sam-khar	Yezorong-pek	CP	9.32	GRF	47	Completed	March 2000	June 11 th , 2000
Pema Gatsel	Zobel	Resinang	CF	20.09	GRF	29	Completed	September 20 th , 2001	December 28 th , 2001
	Shumar	Shali	CP	8.2	GRF	56	Completed	-	-
Samdrup Jongkhar	Dechen-ling	Peling Tsho	CP	8	GRF	38	Kept pending	-	-

Annex D: Dozam CF, Drametse

Mongar dzongkhag, Drametse Tsho 'Om geog, Waichur, Zangkhar, Bikhar, Thramlu, Phantshomo, Wungkhar and Shaphangma villages:
Dozam Community Forest (DCF).

General community objectives: From the RRA conducted in 1995 the following forest-related problems appeared in the village problem ranking matrix: (1) firewood, (2) shingles, (3) post and poles, (4) fodder, (5) bamboo, (6) timber. Due to increase in population and settlements and extraction by outsiders all these products showed a decreasing availability. The community expressed willingness to plant useful tree species on private and government land if the seedlings were provided for free.

The PRA conducted in 1996 in the villages of Zangkhar, Gop and Waichur resulted in shortages of construction timber and firewood as the priority forest-related problems. Furthermore the availability of firewood, timber and shingles (as result of population increase, forest fires, resin tapping and outside extraction), bamboo (as result of increased requirement for agricultural fencing), flag posts (as result of increased demand due to improved economic conditions), forest fuel, cane, stone and boulders, drinking water and torch light (as result of population increase) and grazing land (as result of increase in the number of cattle) had considerably decreased.

In the CFMP (Forest Services Division, 1997a) this was translated into the following objectives:

- Improve the availability of fuelwood, timber and fodder within the CF,
- Rehabilitate degraded sites and protect the local environment for long-term productivity,
- Promote other forestry-related activities, in order to further improve the socio-economic situation of the community.

The main objective was "to increase and diversify the availability of forest products within the area i.e. to improve productivity through reforestation and protection measures with preference for fast growing species to fulfill immediate needs (expecting harvest of fuelwood and small timber from 2000 onwards)".

The community agreed on all the above mentioned objectives and they wanted to keep them as it is. They expect the benefits to start accruing within the coming years and more than for the future they expect them in the present. When faced with the question how they are planning to diversify the availability of forest products whilst planting only chir pine seedlings, the CFMG members from Shaphangma and Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar commented that they had tried other species as well which died due to the site characteristics, mainly the drought. Also they were more prone to be destroyed by the cattle. Moreover, according to them chir pine delivers most of the products they needed. Therefore, they did not want to include 'and other forest-related products' in the first objective either, although previously they did have this as objective in the back of their mind. The people of Shaphangma expressed interest to plant other species as well but only with increased government assistance to increase the survival rate. The Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar community, led by the CFMG chairman, proposed a multiculture as well, based on altitude difference, with Phokchir and below mainly chir pine, and above Phokchir blue pine, cypresses and other species. Since the fodder production in the CFMU had remained behind expectation (due to unsuccessfulness of the pasture development and the fact that the cattle ate fodder species seedlings), they wanted to delete this objective from the list and instead focus fodder production under AF activities at private land. For another example of establishment of common pasture within a CF plantation viz. Tenzing et al., 2001. Here it is mentioned that unlike forestry activities, the establishment of a community pasture will bring immediate benefits to the community. Obviously, the Dozam experience proves a different thing. As additional species, they wanted to plant phumhungshing (?) for commercial use.

Objectives regarding utilisation of benefits: Despite the fact that the old CFMG states that there are limited possibilities of utilisation in the near future due to the degraded nature of the site, several utilisation rules have been included. These rules have as aim to prevent overexploitation of the available resources and promote the development of a favourable environment and conditions for rehabilitation of the site (Forest Services Division, 1997a).

During the review meetings the CFMG members expressed their expectation that in the coming 5 to 10 years the availability of forest resources would increase as a result of the plantation. Therefore, adjustment of these rules was considered necessary.

With respect to timber, the three meetings resulted in different conclusions as to what rules to apply. The Shaphangma villagers decided to revise the existing rules by increasing the fees for legal extraction of timber. For non-members illegally extracting timber from the CF they increased the fines they could impose by fivefold. However for the members they kept the fines same, instead of increasing it as well, stating that if they would increase this the government might keep this high fine in place in the future also even when they wanted to lower it again and thus they might be in future loss. This is an example of the uncertainty that villagers feel regarding government policies on CF and the possibility of changes that limit the CFMG's management responsibilities. During the Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar meeting the community, led by the chairman and secretary of the CFMG, decided to delete the existing rules in the CFMP and replace them by the FNCR (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000). They said the existing fines and fees were too low. Volume II Section 101 of the FNCR states the rules for royalty fees on timber for rural house construction. For timber with a size girth of less than 1' the fee is Nu. 4/-, with size girth between 1' and 2' Nu. 12/-, irrespective of whether it is coniferous or broad-leaved timber. For coniferous timber with a size girth of 2' to 4' the fee is Nu. 30/-, and for timber larger than 4' 1" the fee is Nu. 40/-. For broad-leaved timber with size girth 2' to 4' the fee is Nu. 40/-, and for timber larger than 4' 1" the fee is Nu. 120/-. Regarding the fines, these are stated in FNCR Volume I Section 51(5). Without registration mark but with a permit the fine is Nu. 3,000/-. However in absence of or with an invalid permit the fine is Nu. 50,000/- or six months imprisonment plus seizure of the timber. In other words, the people have decreased the fees for small-sized trees, only nominally increasing the fees for larger sized trees, but considerably increasing the fine on illegal harvest. Finally, the Waichur/Bikhar/Thramlu community agreed to introduce the FNCR royalty fees, but keep the fine for members as it is and increase the fine for non-members.

As for fuelwood collection, the Shaphangma community agreed to impose the FNCR, which in Volume II Section 106 (regarding the supply of firewood in rural areas) states that no royalty fee will be imposed on collection of dry firewood and lops which can be collected and transported by men or animals. When collection and/or transportation by mechanical devices takes place the royalty will be levied at commercial rates. When sound trees are to be marked for firewood purposes, to a maximum of one truckload (8 m³) per household per year, a royalty of 50% the fee for rural household construction timber is applicable. In excess of 8 m³ royalty at commercial rates shall be charged. The first part in effect means no change in comparison to the rules set out in the CFMP, but the second part increases their access to firewood from sound trees, which was not permitted at all under the CFMP. The people of Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar decided to keep the rules in the CFMP, and make the FNCR only apply for firewood collection by lemon grass distillers. In case of wind-uprooted trees, anyone could make an application to the executive committee to issue a permit to take the tree. During the Waichur/Bikhar/Thramlu meeting the people of Bikhar and Thramlu expressed the difficulties they faced in obtaining firewood. Their hamlets are located within the CFMU and this means that for collection of firewood they have to walk a long distance to the nearest GRF. Therefore they proposed that for them debranching and lopping of sound trees should be allowed after verification by the executive committee and without having to pay a fee. The Waichur people agreed to this. For the rest they imposed the FNCR. For lemon grass distillers they prohibited the collection of firewood and imposed fines equal to the fines for timber harvesting by non-members.

The use of torch light in the area had ceased to exist now that kerosene lamps and battery-operated torches had become available. Therefore the utilisation rules on torchlight could be deleted.

The rules on collection of forest foods were left as it is. In addition to the existing utilisation rules, the Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar meeting added the prohibition of stone quarrying within the CFMU by outsiders, with fines as per FNCR.

Special utilisation rule: lemon grass harvesting: Traditionally the CF area has been used for lemon grass harvesting. Being a major source of cash income for the community, in the CFMP this practice was continued under certain rules and regulations. Due to the nature of lemon grass harvesting in eastern Bhutan, which consist of burning the grass during the winter in order to stimulate the growth of new fresh shoots that result in a higher output, every year many hectares of forest are lost to the fire. Therefore, strict rules had to be implemented. The burning of lemon grass has been completely banned within the CF (as within GRFs).

The Shaphangma community observed a duality in the result of lemon grass harvesting on the growth of seedlings. Where the grass is cut, more space is left for seedlings to grow as well as an increase in the amount of sunlight, water and nutrients that becomes available to them. However the new shoots that

appear after cutting attract cattle which grazes on it and in the meantime destroys the seedling. Therefore the community decided that lemon grass cutting should be allowed, but cattle should then be prevented from grazing in the area. This is another example of indigenous knowledge, if not traditional as well.

The Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar community led by the chairman of the CFMG expressed their concern over the fact that the lemon grass collection for animal bedding was being threatened by the lemon grass harvesting for oil extraction as well as by the fact that people who previously thought they held the sole right on collection when the area was still a GRF continued to see themselves as the owners of the lemon grass. Another reason for decreased availability was the collection by non-members. However they said that lemon grass extraction for animal bedding should be a benefit for all the members. Finally they agreed not to amend the rules and in case conflicts arose they would settle among themselves.

All the communities agreed that lemon grass harvesting should be continued as it is important for income generation and moreover if the grass was not cut it would become the dominant vegetation and increase the chance of forest fires. During a previous meeting, the fee for lemon grass distillers was decreased upon their own request. However some had not paid that fee and they proposed new rules to be imposed as to what to do in this case.

The Shaphangma community decreased the seasonal permit fee for lemon grass distillation units for both the small (Nu. 700/-) and large (Nu. 1,500/-) plants. The payment for sale of excess to outsiders was kept same at Nu. 800/-. The Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar community, from where a considerable number of lemon grass distillers origin, decided to impose completely new rules, namely an auction of all the lemon grass within the CFMU to the highest bidder from the CFMG. The executive committee would set a minimum bid, and if no one made a bid higher than that minimum, they would auction the lemon grass to outsiders, and in case no bidder turned up at all they would sell at the rate of Nu. 500/- per truckload. If the minimum bid will be set low, this would benefit the lemon grass distiller who wins the auction. However, the other lemon grass distillers within the CFMG would loose out, since they would have to harvest their lemon grass from outside the CFMU i.e. from GRF against normal royalty fee. The people of Waichur/Bikhar/Thramlu decreased the permit fee as well, to Nu. 2000/- for large plants and Nu. 500/- for small plants, to be paid before installation. They also adopted rules in case the distiller was unwilling or unable to pay the fee. If the amount was not paid, and the unit was operating, the executive committee would visit the distiller and request the double amount of the original fee. In case this amount was not paid either, the whole CFMG would go to the unit and demolish it.

Objectives regarding input and management responsibility: The community expected to provide the labour for site preparation and maintenance, transportation of seedlings from the road head, manure and financial contribution. From the government/project side they expected land on GRF, technical assistance and free seedlings in return. Regarding management, they expected full responsibility according to the rules in the CFMP. During the group discussions the community expressed their full satisfaction with how the practice worked. They were happy with the increased responsibility they received and well as with the executive committee and the participatory nature of the CFMG meetings and decision-making process. The people of Shaphangma had a request for the government to provide technical assistance to plant tree seedlings other than chir pine and increase their survival rate.

The seedlings were provided for free by the government. After the establishment of 3 private nurseries the government compensated them and the seedlings were then planted in the CF. Only in the 2000 planting season there was a lack of seedlings and the number planted per household was reduced to 150. Although in the original CFMP the community was supposed to establish two community nurseries, this had not happened. Three private nurseries were established however, providing the seedlings for the CF against compensation by the government. The villages were divided as to whether to establish a community nursery or not, one being in favour, one being against, and one wanting to establish only after their demand could not be met by the government or private nurseries.

The members of the executive committee expressed the communities' concern over the absence of certain rules and regulations in the old CFMP to Mr. Tshering Choeda and the Mongar Dzif also became aware of this. These lacks referred mainly to the absence of clear fines for labour absence during fire line cutting, fire suppression and plantation, the joining of new members, the absence of rules on a watchman and on how to deal with permanent absentees. Thus during the review meetings per village these issues were also raised and in the general meeting they would be incorporated into the new CFMP.

The CFMG members also pointed out that some issues in the old CFMP had become obsolete. The initial management activity of developing and improving pastureland within the CF was unsuccessful as

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there was no proper fencing and protection thus resulting in continuous grazing by cattle before it could be well developed.

When asked why they imposed the FNCR, effectively reducing their own decision-making power and management responsibility, they said that since the fees and fines would be deposited in their own fund and not go to the government they had no problem with that.

Grazing: The Drametse area has a peculiar grazing practice (personal communication with Mr. Tshering Choeda, 01/04/02). After the local Tshed in end of October/early November all cattle except milking cows is left to graze freely in the adjacent forest till March. The around 680 number of cattle (180 from Zangkhar, 270 from Waichur and 230 from Shaphangma) also grazes within the CF site where they browse on fodder grasses, lemon grass and, especially when the grass is dry, on seedlings of fodder species. The social fencing agreement has not been followed very strictly and after seeing most species other than the non-palatable chir pine seedlings disappear the community decided to plant only chir pine seedlings.

The Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar people stated that since the people of Gop village took their cattle down to Yayung in winter and back to Gop in summer, crossing the CF area, they should be made to pay Nu. 50/- per household per year for trespassing and grazing in the CF. They did not want to restrict this activity, as there was no other way.

Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar and Waichur/Bikhar/Thramlu people expressed their need for a watchman/guard to control the cattle grazing. However they disagreed over how many where to appoint them, i.e. one in the upper part and one in the lower part or one at the four corners of the CF.

The people of Thramlu and Bikhar have no other grazing land available outside the CF except for GRF far away in Yayung and therefore wanted to be allowed to graze their cattle in the CF. However under strong opposition from the Waichur people present during the meeting they gave up their demand.

Labour contribution: At the initial stage 109 households joined but after some time a number of them never turned up for the works that had to be executed nor for the CFMG meetings. The absence of labour absenteeism rules and fines was a serious hamper to the means the community had to deal with these cases. Some households, which did not turn up for the plantation in 1999, did the double amount in 2000. But regarding the others the review of the CFMP will take the necessary action by deleting them from the member list (see below). The new CFMP will also see more clear-cut rules and fines on how to deal with labour absenteeism, although the villages were still divided on the exact rules.

The small households having 2 or 3 members said that no matter what they have to manage their labour contribution and as such are doing it.

All the villages expressed their interest to reduce the number of seedlings to be planted yearly in order to make plantation more efficient and reduce the workload. As arguments they gave that the 250 seedlings to be planted according to the old CFMP was too much considering that the area was slowly reaching full plantation. Moreover, the members observed that some people would take seedlings in bulk and plant them inefficiently or even throw them. To control the results, the Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar community expressed their interest to delineate the CF and let every hamlet take care of plantation and other activities in a certain area.

Non-membership: From Gop village located in-between Walchur and Zangkhar along the feeder road no households have joined the CFMG. This is due to the fact that they have a reasonably well-stocked GRF close to the village from where they extract their forest products. As such they did not feel the need to join.

The current 103 member households that attend the meetings say they have no intention of withdrawing from the CFMG, as they are hopeful for the future. One member, Mr. Wangchuk from Wungkhar Jiwa had withdrawn from the CFMG but later regretted and joined again upon retribution of missed plantations.

However from the original 109 households there are 6 which do not participate in any of the activities. Mrs. Yangchen from Zangkhar Mantshanglu has resettled in Gelephu (Southern Bhutan). Mr. Kinzang Dorji from Thramlu, Mrs. Sanjay from Thramlu Laishingri, Mrs. Soam Zanguo from Walchur Saitshangag, Mr. Dorji from Waichur Thungthari and Mrs. Kencho Oema from Waichur Zhingri gave various reasons for not attending. These reasons were, a lack of immediate benefits (caused by unawareness and a lack of long-term view), a lack of manpower, and/or too much distance from the CF. The Mongar DzFO Mr. Rinchen Wangdi (personal communication, 23/02/02) and the other community members confirmed that these were the main reasons for their disinterest. During the review of the CFMP they will

Annex D: Dozam CF, Drametse

all be made to sign a very strong genja (agreement) that they will never join again the future nor make any claims on the CF.

With respect to new members the community has decided that people who do not belong to any of the original member households would not be allowed to enter. However, when the children of a member leave the household and start a household of themselves they would be allowed to join the CFMG against a payment of Nu. 500/-.

Forest fire: Since the inception of the CF in 1997 forest fires have not affected the area. The community has cut a fireline around the whole plantation to prevent fires from outside the CF from spreading. However the CFMP had no rule regarding this and during the review this will be incorporated. Similarly, the rules on causing a forest fire in the CF or outside the CF resulting in destruction of the CF will be further specified with higher fines and distinction between fires caused by outsiders and by members. Also there will be new rules introduced on the introduction of watchmen for forest fires and cattle grazing. The villages had different positions and rules, the final outcome of which will be decided in the general meeting.

Success: The Mongar DzFO (personal communication, 23/02/02) and the Drametse FEO (personal communication, 02/04/02) observed some notable changes in the community. They mentioned that the feeling of responsibility for their CF had increased. This resulted for example in the complete absence of forest fires in the area. Moreover, the meetings were all organised by the community itself with the FEO a mere observer and guide during the discussions. The CFMG revolving fund stands currently at Nu. 11,612/-, mainly from the lemon grass harvesting fees. The money they want to use for future development of the village and in emergencies.

According to Messerschmidt et al. (2000), the success of Dozam CF can be attributed to keen village interest, participation and a dedicated FEO and local RNR Extension Centre. In that way it is an outstanding example of increased community management of a natural resource. At the same time it is noted however, that Dozam CF is a poor example of 'community forestry' by definition and in respect to setting standards, due to its location in a largely degraded as opposed to natural forest area. If it was established at a later point in time, it might have been designated as CP rather than CF.

The CFMG itself observed during the implementation of the CFMP that there were certain rules missing and unclear and they reported this to the DzFO. They will include this in the review of the CFMP, and in the meantime they have introduced their own rules. Except for the 6 households that will be deleted from the CFMG, all the households had been providing the labour requirements as per rule. This also shows the commitment the community has developed for the CFMU.

Failure: One failure is the communities' disability to control the grazing of cattle in the area and to prevent the destruction of planted saplings (mainly of species other than chir pine). This is due to the cultural practice of free grazing the cattle in winter time, and as such it is difficult to prevent or change it. The introduction of stricter enforcement and the appointment of watchmen should decrease this problem and it is commendable that the community has taken these initiatives.

Another failure is the fact that the plantation target was not fully met. However this is not due to unwillingness or inefficiency of the community, but due to the lack of seedlings. This however could have been prevented if the CFMG had taken the initiative to introduce the two community nurseries as mentioned in the CFMP or to increase the number of private nurseries (which would be advisable seeing the record of community nurseries elsewhere).

Another point noted is the difficulty the CFMG finds in making special rules for the people of Bikhar and Thramlu. Their villages are located within the CFMU, and as such they are, more than any of the other villages, dependent on the CFMU for their forest-related products. It would not be unrealistic for the CFMG to introduce special exception rules for them. Regarding firewood, the Waichur/Bikhar/Thramlu meeting had agreed on this. Whether in the general meeting this exception will be approved as well has to be seen. Regarding grazing of cattle, no exception rules have been introduced, although during the meetings all the members expressed their concern over the situation of the people of these villages.

Another hot issue during the meetings was the harvest of lemon grass. During previous meetings the lemon grass extractors had requested for a decrease in the fees for establishing and operating a lemon grass extraction unit. However in some cases the extractors had failed to pay even that subsidised fee. As such the CFMG decided to keep the lower fee but make stricter rules on how to act in case the fee was not paid. The proposal by the Zangkhar/Phantshomo/Wungkhar community, mainly led by Zangkhar members

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who were operating an extraction unit, to establish an auction for the whole harvest is probably driven by self-interest only and can hardly be considered fair towards the other extractors. Whether during the general meeting this proposal will be approved remains therefore to be seen.

A major problem pertained to the CFMG members who did not contribute any labour nor attended the meetings. The CFMG will simply solve this problem by deleting these members from the list.

Recommendations: The review of the CFMP will most probably incorporate many new rules and regulations that will make the functioning of the CFMP more effective and efficient and thus improve on many of the shortcomings that have been observed in the old CFMP. Most recommendations will be related to those shortcomings, i.e., the establishment of more nurseries, the introduction and enforcement of new and fair lemon grass harvesting rules, the introduction of watchmen to enforce rules on cattle grazing, and the deletion of non-contributing members from the list. Otherwise, the CF is a very successful one, and thus few other recommendations can be made.

Annex E: Community-Issue Matrix, Dozam CF, Drametse

Issue from CFMP	Shaphangma	Zangkhar/ Phantshom/ Wungkhar	Waichur/Bikhar/Thramiu
2.2 Objectives	As it is	As it is	As it is
2.3.1 Management activities			
2.3.1-1 Woodlots	From 250 to 100	From 250 to 100	From 250 to 50
2.3.1-2 Natural stand and regeneration protection	As it is	As it is	As it is
2.3.1-3 Grazing land development	Cancel, develop into plantation	Cancel	Cancel, develop into chir pine plantation
2.3.1-4 Lemon grass harvesting	As it is	As it is	As it is but no chir pine felling by lemon grass extractors
2.3.1-5 Agroforestry	As it is	As it is	As it is
2.3.1-6 Seedling production	Only PN no need for CN	Establish CN besides PN	Only when government stops supplying seedlings: establish CN
2.4 Protection rules			
2.4.1 Grazing and movement of cattle	Stricter enforcement	As it is but with guards	Stricter enforcement and guards
2.4.2 Fire control	Annual creation of fireline. If culprit not found: Nu. 20/- per hh plus replanting, if culprit found and fire inside CF plantation: Nu. 1,500/- per acre (deliberate), Nu. 1,000/- per acre (accidental) plus replanting	Annual creation of fireline. If culprit not found: replanting by whole CFMG, if culprit is found and in natural forest: Nu. 500/- per acre (accidental), Nu. 1,000/- (deliberate), if in plantation: Nu. 1,000/- (accidental), Nu. 2,000/- (deliberate), if not paid: apply FNCR 2000, if culprit is outsider: apply FNCR 2000	Yearly creation of fireline. If culprit not found: replanting by whole CFMG, if culprit is found and member: as it is, if culprit is found and non-member: Nu. 3000/- per acre plus replanting
2.5 Utilisation rules			
2.5.1 Timber	Rates revised: fee Nu. 50/- (class 4 and 3 tree), Nu. 30/- (class 2 tree), Nu. 25/- (class 1 tree), fines for non-members: Nu. 1,500/-, Nu. 1,000/-, Nu. 500/-, fines for members as it is.	As per FNCR (2000)	Fees as per FNCR (2000), fine for members as it is, for non-members: Nu. 1,000/- (class 4 and 3 tree), Nu. 700/- (class 2 tree), Nu. 500/- (class 1 tree).
2.5.2 Fuelwood	As per FNCR (2000)	As it is for shrubs and dead branches, for lemon grass distillers: FNCR (2000) apply	Fees and fines as per FNCR (2000), for Bikhar and Thramiu: de-branching and lopping of trees including chir pine allowed after verification by Exec. Comm. For lemon grass distillers: not allowed, fines Nu.

2.5.3 Wood torch	Delete	Delete	1,000/-, Nu. 700/-, Nu. 500/- Delete
2.5.4 Lemon grass	Permit fee decreased: Nu. 1,500/- per season for large plants, Nu. 700/- for small plants	Auction of all lemon grass within CFMU to highest bidder within CFMG, otherwise: auction to outsiders, lastly: sale at Nu. 500/- per truckload	Permit fee decreased: for large plants Nu. 2,000/- per season, Nu. 500/- for small plants, to be paid before installation, if paid: double amount, if not: demolishing of unit
2.5.5 Forest foods	As it is	As it is	As it is
Additional issues			
Labour absenteeism during fire line creation and fire suppression	Fine Nu. 50/- per day general absence, critical circumstances born by all	Fine Nu. 100/- when not reported, no fine when reported to CFMG	Fine Nu. 100/-
Labour absenteeism during plantation	Fine Nu. 50/- per day plus planting at later time, hh should provide double labour	Compulsory but can be done at any time	Compulsory
New membership	Outsiders not allowed, insiders upon payment of Nu. 500/-	Outsiders not allowed, insiders upon payment of Nu. 500/-, no rejoining after leaving	Outsiders not allowed, insiders upon payment of Nu. 500/-
Permanent absentees during labour and meetings	-	Delete from the list	-
Stone quarrying	-	Prohibited for outsiders, fine as per FPCR 2000	-
Movement of cattle from Gop-Yayung through CF	-	Nu. 50/- per hh per year	-
Establishment cottage industries	-	Market survey and funding for omla and phrumchungshing (?) export	-
Division of CF activities	-	Hamlet-wise division	-
Guard	-	Introduce one in upper and one in lower part	Yearly shifting guard at four corners of the CF
Office	-	Establishment of CFMG office, building materials provided by government, labour by CFMG	-
Protection of water sources	-	Planting of trees and prohibition on felling near source	-

Annex F: Yezorongpek CP, Pam

Trashigang dzongkhag, Samkhar geog, village Pam:
Yezorongpek Community Plantation.

General community objectives: In the CFMP the following objectives for establishment of the CP are mentioned (Forest Services Division, 1999):

- to supplement the local needs of fuelwood and timber
- to rehabilitate degraded land and protect the environment for sustainable production
- to generate income and improve the socio-economic condition of the community through sale of commercial species.

However as noted before these objectives appear in practically all the CFMPs. Since no other data were available as to what were the trends in forest product availability or village problems, the community was asked to state again their prior objectives. During this discussion, following objectives became apparent:

- improve the availability of fuelwood and timber
- control the occurrence of landslides affecting agricultural lands and the road
- make the barren site look more nice since it is close to the village.

The main objective mentioned in the CFMP missing from the objectives that the community mentioned is the last one, regarding income generation and improvement of the socio-economic condition. It became clear that more than that the community wanted to use the products that would become available from the CP for their own use rather than for sale. Although initially in the CFMP six tree species were selected for plantation the community planted mainly chir pine since the site was not suitable for other species and the chir pine would provide the community with fuelwood and timber, being the main objective for plantation.

Objectives regarding utilisation of benefits: The CFMP clearly mentions that in the first plan period there would be little benefits as the planted trees would still be small. In the group discussion the members confirmed this by stating that they did not join with the aim of reaping benefits in their own lifetime, but mainly for the benefit of their children who would stay in the village. A CP near the village would make it easier for them to get the tree products they would need. After some more questioning however the community expressed their hope and expectation that within 5 years they would be able to use lopped and topped chir pine trees and fallen branches etc. as fuelwood, and within 15 years they expect to extract the first timber. Although the benefits are negligible at the moment, they expressed their willingness to continue providing inputs and face a "loss" for the moment in order to gain in the future. In that way they have a clear long-term planning and view.

Objectives regarding input and management responsibility: Regarding these objectives the community stated that they had no problems and misconceptions. The rules as set out in the CFMP were satisfactorily to them and everything was executed according to the CFMP. The government provided all they wanted and even more. In the CFMP it was mentioned that the community should start their own community nursery in order to grow the seedlings for planting in the CFMP. The main aim of this was to reduce the transportation costs and reliance on other nurseries (Forestry Services Division, 1999). The government would then pay the community for the seedlings provided. However the community nursery had not been established and the government had continued to deliver the seedlings as demanded by the CFMG free of cost. The reason the community mentioned was that the rate offered by the government for provided seedlings was too less considering the work involved in raising them. Only in 2001 there were no chir pine seedlings available and the set plantation target could not be achieved. The community now expected to take one more year to fill up the whole site.

Grazing: Previously the area had been in use as grazing area for Pam community. However after the CP was established grazing cattle became punishable during the first five years and as a result the approximately 200 number of cattle are being grazed in other areas (mainly towards Rangzhikdar village). The system of social fencing in other words is very effective here, mainly due to the limited number of households and cattle originally using of the area for grazing. Furthermore the community mentioned that the fine of Nu. 25/- per cattle entering the CP and Nu. 50/- per damaged plant is very high for them. Lastly the close location of the village to the CP, the high degree of social cohesion and control and the availability of alternative grazing areas were mentioned by the people as reasons for success.

Labour contribution: one of the few problems faced by the CFMG is the labour absenteeism. During cutting of the fire-line in 2001 two households did not send their representatives. Their membership was consequently kept pending until they pay the fine fixed by the CFMP. According to the CFMP per day the household is absent a fine of Nu. 50/- has to be paid, with a Nu. 100/- fine for those who purposely went for contract work in other places. However the CFMG changed the rule that in case of domestic problems they will have to replace the labour next time.

Non-membership: Out of total of 51 households 47 households are member. The remaining four households have not joined since their household has too few members to provide the necessary labour or because they are working outside the village. Of the original members, none have signed out and all are satisfied with the proceedings thus far.

Forest fire: During the group discussion the community did not show much fear of the CP being destroyed by fire. They have cut an over 2.5 metre fire-line along the whole border of the CP. Moreover the CP is within visible distance of the village so any fire would be detected fast and action could be taken accordingly. Beside this they have also been provided with forest fire fighting equipment by the TFDP. According to the CFMP, a person apprehended for starting a forest fire will be dealt with according to the FNCA, 1995 (i.e. replanting by the offender, replaced by FNCR, 2000).

Unfortunately, on April 1st 2002 a youth from Rongthung village passed the CP site along the footpath from Tmshigang to Pam and threw a biri (Indian cigarette) bud without putting it off properly. Within no time the strong winds spread the fire from the footpath upwards across the site and despite swift notice and action by the Pam community they could not prevent the CP from being completely destroyed, as well as adjacent GRF, before the fire could be put off. During consequent discussion with some CFMG members they expressed their disappointment over what happened. However they also stated they hoped for some number of seedlings to have survived and their willingness to replant the whole site in 2002 itself only if the required number of seedlings could be provided by the government. The culprit's guardian has agreed to abide by the law and take care of the replanting himself.

Success: The site has been a rather successful CP with full community participation and a high rate of plantation. Moreover the social fencing has been successful compared to other sites. This high degree of success seems to be attributed to a largely homogeneous and dedicated community as well as the support and dedication of the FEO Mr. Dorji Drukpa. His continued assistance was lauded by the community as well as being recognised by the dzongkhag authorities. Another factor contributing to the success might be the close location of Pam to the Trashigang dzongkhag headquarters facilitating the extension work.

Failure: There are no main failures or faults with respect to the CFMG or the dzongkhag authorities themselves. The destruction of the CP by forest fire was an accident that could only have been prevented by increased awareness among the people of eastern Bhutan regarding the causes of forest fire. Once the fire was started, the local conditions including the lemon grass undergrowth, the dryness of the vegetation and the strong winds made it extremely difficult to combat it.

Recommendations: In order to support the community in re-establishing the CP site it is recommended that the government provides the required number of seedlings for replanting to the culprit's guardian or the community at the earliest, so that the replanting can be done soon.

Furthermore it is advised that a community or private nursery (private nursery preferable, as examples show that community nurseries are not successful, see Tangmachhu) be established to reduce dependency on government nurseries for seedlings.

Annex G: Tshurgangpek CP, Manam

Yangtse dzongkhag, Toetsbo geog, village Manam:
Tshurgangpek Community Plantation.

General community objectives: as objectives for establishment of the CP the CFMP mentions the following reasons:

- to restore tree cover and improve the site productivity,
- to supplement the supply of forest products (mainly fuelwood, fodder, construction timber, leaf litter and flag posts),
- to improve the socio-economic position of the community,
- to demonstrate the success of CP and community involvement in forest management.

During the discussion with the chairman the following priorities of products that the expected to obtain was expressed: (1) timber for house construction, (2) firewood, (3) wood for shingles and (4) leaf-litter and grass for the cattle. Due to the fact that the adjacent areas are in the same condition the community faced a severe fuelwood and construction timber shortage. Fuelwood is still extracted from the GRF in the upper part of the ridge above the villages and in the gorge of the Budgirong stream. Timber however is being extracted from the opposite side of Nyamnyang river, i.e. Melongkhar village under Yang geog. After marking by the Forest Department and obtaining the permit from Tshenkharla (under Doksum Forest Office) the trees are felled. From there the logs are floated in the river where they end up on the Indian side of the river. The local people have to transport the logs from there to Manam village. Although there is co-operation with the Indian people they have to transport the logs fast otherwise confiscation or theft takes place. It is a very complicated and time-consuming procedure.

Objectives regarding utilisation of benefits: The chairman and other members insisted that they do not expect the benefits in their own lifetime, but rather they have the aspiration that at least for the future generations the establishment of the CP will relieve the difficult times they face themselves.

Objectives regarding input and management responsibility: The community expressed their preference for construction timber species and commercial species for long run benefits rather than fast growing species. Therefore they chose mainly conifer and broadleaf species (Forest Services Division, 1998). The fines from cattle grazing were deposited in a community revolving fund and that money had been given to one of the CFMG members as loan with interest. The whole committee made this decision. Regarding the input from government/TFDP side the CFMG is not satisfied. After the fire in 2000 they received no technical backstopping or assistance and advice on how to continue. The DzFO nor the TFDP staff visited the CP, although they met with the executive committee on the way. The previous DzFO had also ordered seedlings at the rate of Nu. 4/- each from the private nursery owned by Mr. Sonam Jamsho but never paid for them. Right now around 3,000 overgrown chir pine, cypresses and eucalypt saplings are available. If fencing material becomes available they want to plant them in the CP.

Grazing: The social fencing system in Manam has never worked properly. Although the cattle is grazed under supervision of wadipa (cowherders) they can't control all the cattle. The site has been used as winter grazing area for around 600 heads of cattle not only from Manam and Thangdrang but also from Chemkhar and Maidung villages. Therefore the grazing and browsing of cattle resulting in destruction of seedlings is not uncommon. Earlier the CFMG used to fine the cattle owners, but after sometime they considered it unfair as there is no fence to keep out the cattle. They had therefor requested barb wire and fence posts to make a fence but this was refused. However without fencing arrangement they are unwilling to continue the plantation.

Labour contribution: All the households till date have been able to provide the required labour, even the households consisting of widows and their children only. Despite the fact that within the village community they are somewhat less well off and have labour shortage they manage to do the work.

Non-membership: All the households in the villages of Manam and Thangdrang are members of the CFMG. Till date no one has shown interest to sign out. However when their demands for fencing are not being met they are planning to dissolve the CFMG.

Tshokpektang CP, Tangmachhu

Lhuentse dzongkhag, Menbi geog, village Tangmachhu:
Tshokpektang Community Plantation (TCP).

Forest fire: In April 2000 the whole CP and surrounding areas was destroyed by a forest fire. People from the Indian side of the border had encroached upon Bhutanese territory in the late afternoon, to hunt for game (gasha or barking deer, *Muntiacus muntjak*, basha or goral, *Neomothedus goral*, and riphag or wild boar, *Sus scrofa*). They had lit the vegetation near the river side to drive the animals out of their cover but due to the strong winds blowing from the river side upwards the fire climbed up. Despite the fact that they had cut a fire-line 10 meters wide from below and 5 meters wide from above and the sides the fire spread very fast. The whole community turned up to control the fire but they were unable to do so, also due to darkness. Being from the Indian side of the border, the community has no power to sue them under the FNCR. Moreover this would endanger the relationship they have with those people and still they are dependent on them.

During the field visit (02/03/02), surprisingly, a considerable number of seedlings turned out to have survived the fire. Probably due to the speed with which the fire spread and the absence of leaf mould on the soil (only lemon grass and rocks) the rootstock of the seedlings was not damaged and especially the chir pine and chilauney seedlings had resprouted. Most eucalypt, hawla, cypresses and walnut saplings had not survived. However, if there is no fencing materials provided to protect the CP from grazing cattle they are unwilling to continue with the CP.

Success: The main successes lie in the field of the fast plantation of the complete area by the community and the strong commitment of all the members to provide the labour as per the CFMP.

Failure: The main failures are outside of the control of the CFMG. Only the fact that the social fencing system didn't work is partly attributable to them, although the large number of cattle makes it extremely difficult to control. The unwillingness of government and TFDP to provide fencing materials is a major reason for the community to complain. The fire was not started from within the community and no means of suing the culprits is possible.

Fig. 16: One of the few resprouted Eucalypt saplings in the CP.

Also the conditions during the fire made it difficult to fight it. The lack of technical backstopping and assistance by the government and the TFDP is one of the major reasons that the people have lost interest. When asked why the TFDP did not provide assistance they replied that they had not received information from the DzFO regarding the condition of the CP and therefore did not undertake any action. The main fault thus seems to lie with the former DzFO. A major reason might be the remote location of the CP, which makes it difficult to reach and extend support.

Recommendations: It is recommended that the new DzFO, with or without assistance from the TFDP, discusses with the CFMG whether they want to continue with the CP or not. In case the government does not provide fencing materials, there seems to be little scope for continuation of the CP. Instead the development of agro-forestry practices in the village should be promoted. Furthermore it is recommended that for future CF/CP locations the distance to the dzongkhag headquarters/nearest road point should not be too much, in order to facilitate the provision of extension services.

General community objectives: During the RRA conducted in 1995 (Basuet et al., 1995) the availability of firewood and the availability of grazing land and fodder occupied the 1st and 2nd position in the village problem ranking matrix. Moreover the availability of almost all forest-derived products except for fodder and forest foods has decreased. The community stated that due to population increase and subsequent increase in housing construction the availability of timber, bamboo, sand, boulders, water and firewood had decreased. Rampant tree cutting was mentioned as the main reason for decrease in availability in leafmould, shingles, fencing materials and wood for agricultural tools.

The CFMP 1997 mentions as communities' objective to increase the availability of firewood and timber products in the village through plantation, protection of existing vegetation and promotion of natural regeneration (Forest Services Division, 1997h).

During the group meeting this single most important objective was confirmed by the CFMG members stating that they have to travel long distances to fetch their fuelwood and timber and they are hoping that the CP will increase that availability for the future generations. They did not stress as much on increasing the availability of other forest-related products, hence the emphasis on chir pine plantation.

Objectives regarding utilisation of benefits: At the moment no benefits are accruing since just now the trees are too small (3 to 4 feet) and only after 10 years i.e. by the end of the 9th FYP (2007) benefits are expected (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29/03/02). The CFMG members also expressed the hope that at least within their own lifetime they would be able to get some of the benefits, as one lady expressed at least one darshing (flagpole for prayer flags to be erected after a person has died).

The main concern they expressed is that although the CFMP gives them full power to harvest from the CP without government restrictions they doubt whether in the future when the trees reach harvesting age these rules will remain the same. They are afraid that inconsistency in government policies might affect their decision making power over the utilisation of products from their own CP.

Objectives regarding inputs and management responsibility: The community expected to provide the labour for site preparation and maintenance, transportation of seedlings from the road head, manure and financial contribution. From the government/project side they expected land on GRF, technical assistance and free seedlings in return. Regarding management, they expected full responsibility according to the rules in the CFMP.

The local people did the species choice themselves with assistance from the FEO. Originally they had chosen eucalypt, *Aesandra butyracea*, chir pine, and cypressus, but after noticing that the pine seedlings were growing better and had a higher survival rate they preferably planted those only.

Previously the seedlings were provided by the government but a community nursery was established in October 1999 for plantation at the CP and supply to others (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29/03/02). In 2000 all 19 households were contributing labour to the community nursery but by 2001 this decreased to only 7.

The CFMG members are satisfied with the government assistance they have received and everything has been implemented according to the CFMP. Only they had requested for fencing materials which was not provided and that they are expecting some more training and technical backstopping in the future. They expressed full trust in the managing abilities of their elected executive committee members as well.

Grazing: The social fencing arrangement in Tangmachhu is successful. A watchman has been appointed under mutual agreement to control grazing which works well. He/she changes yearly and received a compensation of Nu. 1,800/- per year (instead of the 36 man-days labour in retribution as in the CFMP). The fine of Nu. 50/- per destroyed seedling is quite high for the people. Moreover the total number of cattle in the summer does not exceed 20, whereas during wintertime the cattle grazes in the barren paddy fields. The cattle is mostly from the members, with no cattle from outsiders grazing near the CP. When occasionally cattle of members browsed within the CP a warning to the owner was given and no fines have

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been issued till date. Although the CFMG requested for fencing materials they were not provided with it due to lack of budget, and thus they gave it up.

Labour contribution: There have been no problems with labour absenteeism. In some cases exemption has been granted to households when there were domestic problems. One household consists only of a mother and daughter but still they were able to provide the necessary labour contribution.

Non-membership: No members of the hamlet wanted to leave neither did anyone want to join.

Forest fire: Before the fire season starts the community cuts a 12 feet wide fire line, with all the bushes and grass completely removed. Due to this no forest fire has occurred in the CP (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29/03/02). In 1998 a forest fire during plantation time destroyed the complete area around the CP. Despite the fact that that time no fire-line had been made, the swift action of the whole community resulted in the protection of the CP. Now the CFMG has been provided with fire fighting equipment by the TFDP.

Success: The social fencing arrangement and the protection from forest fire have been very successful. There have been no problems with labour absence or members leaving the CFMG. This can all be attributed to a large social cohesion and control and the appointment of a watchman. Also the CP itself is now fully planted and the trees, especially the chir pine trees are growing well.

Failure: Main problem observed is that there is no budget available for review of the CFMP now that the first 5 years have passed. Moreover the community is ready to provide the necessary labour and other inputs for a possible extension with natural well-stocked forest to meet 2.5 ha per household criteria and upgrade to CF (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29/03/02). They are even willing to give up sokshing registered in their own thram, since it will benefit the whole community. However, the tenure status of the surrounding forest is still to be established, as it appears to be a combination of GRF and sokshing registered in the name of absentee landholders.

Box 3: Shifting of budget to TCP review. Under the TFDP budget is available for planning of another CP or CF under Lhuentse dzongkhag. Initially this was concentrated at Ngency village, Jaray geog for establishment of Ladung CP. This proposed CP of 9 ba on GRF with a total number of 33 out of 37 participating households had a CPMP prepared in September 2001. A PRA was conducted in 1997 and the site was found very steep, remote and severely degraded with only small bushes. The population is dependent on share cropping of dryland and off-farm labour due to the limited availability of arable land. The dependency on the forest for fuelwood and other forest products is also very high (Department of Forest Services, 2001b). In March 2002 the Director of Forest has not approved the CPMP since the area was too small to qualify for CF under the FNCR 2000. The area has no chance for extension with degraded or well-stocked forest either due to the terrain. Moreover the procedure took so much time and was so unclear that the community has lost their interest to continue. After surveying other sites at Budur and Autsho villages it was concluded that these sites are still well-stocked or 50% degraded and 50% well-stocked respectively with expectation of future degradation. Till date no application has been written although the community is very enthusiastic. The fear of the Dzongkhag Forest Department is that the establishment of a CF in a well-stocked forest near the roadhead will create incentives for illegal local sale of timber and that therefore these sites are not that much suitable (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29/03/02). Instead, it is proposed to shift the available budget to the review and possible extension and upgradation of TCP.

Another failure was the establishment of the community nursery. After abolishment of the government nursery the FEO initiated the community nursery with as aim to provide the necessary seedlings for plantation at the site and refilling of pits after seedlings died as well as provision to other government or community plantations. In 2000-2001 10,000 seedlings were raised and in 2001-2002 8,000 seedlings. However during the winter of 2001-2002 the responsible households did not provide sufficient water to the seedlings nor any other care and over 80% of the seedlings died. Since the Dzongkhag Forest Department had no budget to pay for the seedlings the nursery operators lost their interest. However even when money would be provided the care would be far less than in a private nursery. The land is owned by

Annex H: Tshokpektang CP, Tangmachhu

one household whilst the remaining 6 households provide the labour or an equivalent in grains. However they tend to shift the responsibilities to each other as they can't reach consensus and as such the seedlings die due to lack of care (personal communication with Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, 29-30/03/02). This is clearly demonstrated by the nearby private nursery operated by the CFMG chairman, Mr. Karmala, whose seedlings are all in good condition.

Recommendations: Tangmachhu is a success-story in SF interventions in Eastern Bhutan, with a good plantation record and a fast improving site condition. The community is enthusiastic regarding the development of the CP and prospects of further extension into a CF. It is therefore recommended that budget is made available to look into the possibilities of upgradation into a CF under the FNCR (2000).

Due to the inefficiency of the community nursery operations, it is recommended that this be converted into a private nursery. The CFMP lacks a constitution and by-laws (including conflict resolution and management of the community revolving fund) and thus it is recommended that during the plan review attention to this is paid. Other rules that have been omitted in the CFMP, or are not mentioned detailed enough, include labour contribution rules and utilisation rules. These should be included as well.

Annex I: Community Meetings in Eastern Bhutan

Here will be presented a number of general observations regarding community meetings as they are being conducted in eastern Bhutan, and especially the socio-cultural and religious factors that influence them. The observations are grouped under the headers gender, community leaders, the agricultural and religious calendars, specific circumstances, CFMP rules, and social diversity. The Annex ends with some recommendations.

Gender: To conduct a community meeting in eastern Bhutan needs a specific approach dictated by a specific culture. One main feature of Bhutanese households is that inside the house the women make most of the decisions in matters directly and indirectly relating to the household. But outdoors it is the men who are most active and speak out most openly, making many decisions. This doesn't mean that the women have no influence on these decisions. Often, the matter will have been discussed indoors, and the men often function as mere messengers for decisions made under mutual consensus (Pema et al., 1995). Despite some traditional gender biases and differences extreme inequalities and discrimination do not prevail (Kinga, 1999). Bhutanese society is largely egalitarian, with non-existent or very weak social distinctions based on gender (Messerschmidt et al., 2000).

In eastern Bhutan most land is registered in the name of the female head of the family. The family system is predominantly matriarchal, with ownership rights of land and assets in female hands. Similarly, of all the member households in the CFMGs an average 56% is registered under the name of the female head of the household (Drametse: 62%, Manam: 40%, Pam: 34%, Tangmachhu: 95%). In most CFMGs there is a rule that at least one female should be member of the executive committee. In most executive committees, it remains by that one lady. Moreover, when female household members who are not aware of the issues attend meetings, for example, the members' mother, sisters or daughters, they do not contribute much to the discussion. Even when specifically asked, they do not know what to answer as the subject is unfamiliar to them. Female household representatives who are also CFMG members however are often very talkative and provide good input to the discussion. During the group meetings conducted as part of this research an average of 65% was female (Tangmachhu: 40%, Manam: 67%, Pam: 38%, Drametse Shaphangma: 56%, Drametse Zaughkar/Phantshomo/Wungkar: 76%, Drametse Bikhar/Thramlu/Waichur: 75%, with the Tangmachhu and Manam meetings due to low number of representatives not really qualifying as 'group' meetings). Kinga (1999) also mentions that public meetings are mostly attended by women, not only because the men are often away, but also because they are considered more articulate and decisive. Women can voice their opinions and make suggestions. However they themselves feel that important decision can better be made by men, which the men agree to. Extension workers often encourage women to attend meetings. There are no cultural or educational barriers that prevent women interacting with men (Pema et al., 1995). It is also noted that in relation to forestry, men's and women's roles are almost equal. Many ladies will bring their young (grand) children to the meeting who can not be left home alone. Many of them are still babies and this sometimes creates disturbances, with crying babies who need breast-feeding or need to be cleaned (Bhutanese mothers do not feel ashamed to breast-feed or change diapers in public).

Community leaders: Furthermore, the influence of community leaders is also very strong. Often they act as the ears, eyes, and mouth of the whole community. People will express their wants, grievances, problems and hopes to the community leader, who then acts as a spokesperson to the outside world. Even when people do not openly express something, the community leader will often observe and discuss potential issues. From the official administrative point of view, there are the chhimi (elected people's representative to the national assembly), gap (elected political head of goog, paid by the government), mangi-ap ('father of the community', appointed community representative to the GYT, and 'peace maker'), chupoen (Sh. chipon, appointed village level co-ordinator, head of cheog) and shokpa (committee members or representatives). Other people with special functions and corresponding influence include gomchen (lay monks), midwives, school teachers, menpa (Sh. manpa, traditional healers), watchmen, and the executive committee members of for example irrigation channel construction and maintenance groups, CFMGs etc. Lastly, the elderly and economically successful have a considerable influence as well. These people, and then especially the gap, are held in high esteem and are usually paid great respect and homage. The relation between them and the villagers is based on long-standing tradition and are even somewhat feudal. They are seldom challenged by the villagers.

To what extent these people are really representative of the whole village is questionable, and depends on the local circumstances. In many smaller villages, under exceptional circumstances, they are reasonable proxies of the whole village. Such was the case in Manam, where the death of a village prevented a group meeting, and except for two ladies, only the mangi-ap cum secretary of the CFMG was interviewed. However in general it is better not to rely on their information alone. During many meetings in which the community/CFMG executive committee was present, these people would often control the discussions. It was then necessary to specifically ask questions to people who did not actively participate in order to cross-check the information given by the executive members. Also, the presence of village leaders and even other community members

Annex I: Community Meetings in eastern Bhutan

creates an unwillingness for some people to speak out, since they don't want to create conflict or make themselves look foolish.

The agricultural calendar: The agricultural calendar and the weather circumstances often heavily influence the attendance during meetings. During field preparation, sowing, transplanting, harvesting and other agricultural activities most males will be in the fields and therefore the number of female attendants will be higher. These agricultural activities are often dictated by the weather circumstances. For example, during the Drametse meetings the first rain after the dry winter made the soil more easily ploughable. Being traditionally a man's job, this resulted in the over-representation of women during the meeting. Some households, weary of the fine for non-attendance, even send children below the age of 15. Similarly, during other meetings conducted in the winter when there is little agricultural activity, the number of male representatives will increase.

The religious calendar: There is also the influence of the religious calendar. During certain auspicious days, called duezang, such as the 10th, 15th and 30th day of the Bhutanese month, as well as on religious and national holidays, the villagers will not do any work and so meetings during these days will be attended by all. In total there are around 45 to 50 such days per year, depending on the locality. Other religious days, such as Losar (the Bhutanese New Year) as well as local new years and the annual tshochu (festival) are used solely for religious purposes and on these days no meetings will be conducted.

Fig. 17: Final community meeting for Joensham Lamdroesa CP plan preparation meeting, Khating, Trashigang (20/03/2002).

Specific circumstances: Then, there is the influence of specific circumstances that influence the meetings. Such circumstances include death in the village, the religious ceremonies for which last for the days following the death case and will be repeated with 7-days intervals till 49 days after the death. The whole village often attends these religious rites. In Manam, the death of a villager resulted in the impossibility to conduct a group meeting with the CFMG members, as all had gone to the house where the death had taken place. In Drametse, during the Waichur/Bikhar/Thramlu meeting, a child had died in Thramlu village, and therefore all members from that village had requested permission to be absent.

CFMP rules: All CFMGs have the rule that for CFMG meetings that are according to the fixed calendar, each member household is obliged to send a representative. There are also fines imposed for absent households, mostly of Nu. 50/- per time absent. This sometimes results in households sending elderly people or children for the meeting when no other household members are available. For incidental meetings however, the executive committee members will call anyone who is available.

Social diversity: Social diversity is especially manifest in economic and social relationship and in various lifestyles. It exists at all levels, and can also manifest within itself. It is also seen in the variety of ways people perceive, value and relate to public life, such as at meetings. A person or group of people within a society with an investment, share or interest in an activity, who values that activity or it results or outputs, or who has a concern about it is called a stakeholder. It is important during meetings to identify these stakeholder (groups).

and make sure that all groups are being heard. The fact that no community is homogenous and as a result there are many different views and opinions on all issues. This makes reaching a consensus sometimes a very difficult and time-taking affair. It is therefore important to take enough time for the meeting. Moreover it often takes time to make villagers understand certain issues which are obvious to the (educated) conductor of the meeting. It doesn't mean they are backward or stupid, they just have their own way of thinking and reasoning and their own ways of expressing themselves. It is important to use simple language which they can comprehend and to take time in expressing things that are seemingly unclear to them, with continued asking whether the issue is clear to them or not.

Tips for conducting community meetings in Bhutan: Based upon the previous, there are some tips that can increase the participation during community meetings conducted in villages in eastern Bhutan. Firstly, meetings held during the winter (agricultural slack season) or on religious days will see an increased participation of people. Secondly, if information from females or otherwise less talkative community members is required it is better to interview them separately instead of in front of other members (especially the village leaders). Thirdly, it is important to take account of the inter-community differences and make sure that all are equally involved in the discussions, not least of all the females present. Fourthly, there should be enough time available and one should be patient enough to explain everything clearly in simple language and make sure all is understood correctly. Fifthly, it is obvious that it is important to listen to the views expressed by all community members and take them duly into account.

Forest fires in Eastern Bhutan

The winter season in eastern Bhutan lasts from November to March and is usually very dry with little or no rainfall. Moreover the soil is rocky with little water retention and temperatures at the lower altitudes (1,200 to 2,000 meters) are relatively high (average daytime temperature of 20 to 25 degrees Celsius). The vegetation in these areas consists mainly of (degraded) chir pine forest with shrubs and bushes and lemon grass undergrowth. During the winter season this vegetation is very prone to forest fires. More accurate it would be to call 'wildfire' as in most cases the areas are too degraded to be labeled as 'forest'.

Fig. 18: Forest fire blazing between Chazam and Rolong, Trashigang (22/03/2002).

Causes of forest fires: there are four main causes of forest fires in eastern Bhutan, namely:

- 1) Intentional burning to stimulate fresh lemon grass growth harvested in the summer months for oil extraction as means of cash income generation. The harvest of lemon grass after burning the old dried-up shoots is considerably higher.
- 2) Intentional burning to stimulate fresh fodder grass growth for cattle grazing during summer.
- 3) Intentional burning to reduce the incidence of wildlife pests such as wild boar, deer and various insect species that attack crops on neighbouring agricultural land, as well as to reduce occurrence of ticks attacking the cattle browsing in the area. Scientifically this has not been studied, it is merely a farmer's belief. However in the winter of 2000-2001, at Mongar Pankhang and Dongshu (Drancise goog) a wild fire set for this reason destroyed a large area of chir pine and mixed broadleaf forest. The following summer season the food availability for locusts was so low that they attacked the maize crop, destroying the whole area. Not a single vegetation remained spared, and the farmers' strategy severely backfired on them.
- 4) Accidental burning e.g.:
 - a) fires lit for cooking and to keep warm by cowherders left unattended and not put off properly. During the winter months cowherders (mostly teenage boys) often spend weeks in the forest taking the cattle to places where grazing grass is available.
 - b) Kitchen fires at temporary huts/shelters not put off properly before departing for work.
 - c) Burning garbage or agricultural waste (for soil enrichment) left unattended or burning out of control.
 - d) Discarding of match sticks or cigarette buds, which have not been put off properly, by locals or vehicles passing on the highway.

It is often difficult to point a finger at the actual culprit. Even when this can be done, it seems hard to punish a farmer for carelessness. In most cases, no culprit is found. When the culprit is apprehended, they are often sent away after a warning and after promising to replant the destroyed area or pay a fine per acre. Only when this is refused does the case go to court (Gyeltshen, 2002).

Damage of wild fires: Wild fires do not only destroy existing vegetation. It rejuvenates it as well. Within days of the first rains the grass will start reshooting. The year following the fire, the chir pines above a certain height (generally 3 to 4 feet) will profusely regenerate. Although smaller trees and saplings generally do not survive, when the fire covers a large distance in a short time (i.e. under conditions of fierce wind, dry material and little leafmould on the soil) there are certain tree and shrub species whose rootstocks remains unaffected, and these

species will also resprout. The burnt remains of vegetation are a good soil fertiliser bringing nutrients back into the soil for the new sprouts to use. So, in pine forests, the damage is just temporary, and when the fires do not occur on yearly basis, it is beneficial in fact. Forest fires have been occurring for ages, and this has led to the specific 'degraded' pine forests common in eastern Bhutan. Wee et al. (2000:39-40) thus state that it is a popular misconception that these pine forests have been degraded due to fires started by local people. However they are more likely the result of the harshness of the site and the low precipitation. In broadleaf and mixed forests the damage is much bigger, as most of these trees can not survive the intense heat of the fires.

Another cause of concern however is the loss of animal life. Visibly, esp. basha (*Naemorhedus goral*), shangsha (*Capreomys sumatraensis*) and gasha (*Muntiacus muntjak*) are the main victims. When trying to escape from the fire, they often jump right into it (free barbecue for villagers!). But the millions of insects that instantly expire are not that much visible. However the new grass provides a new source of food to all these animals, and the surviving individuals thrive well. It's a kind of natural selection. In occasional circumstances, there is also loss to property and sometimes even human life.

Fires that occurred during winter of 2001-2002:

Lhuentse Dzongkhag:

- Gorgau Tshangkhar and Karmazhangshong, (12/01), 70 ha,
- Jarey Zangkhur, (01/02), 80 ha,
- Gangzur Tsangkam above Jangchubling Lhakhang, 5 ha,
- Tangmachhu, (03/02), 5 ha,
- Menji, March (03/02), 4 acres

Mongar dzongkhag:

- Duyang and Wangling
- Shericchhu and Drametse
- Pakhadangchhu
- Yadi

Trashigang dzongkhag:

- Buyang
- Lichen
- Ranjar
- Jamkhar (spreading from Trashigang Rimalu)
- Tongmljangsa shortcut

Trashigang dzongkhag:

- Bartsam and Rijsu
- Udzorong and Kanglung
- Pam
- Ritsalu, Yangnyer, Gongthung, Rolong
- Below Kheri petrol pump
- Pam (including CP)

Fig. 19: Author participating in forest fire control. Yangnyer, Trashigang (21/03/2002).

Prevention and control: The forest department- both divisional as well as dzongkhag- does everything in its power to educate people on the risks and dangers of forests fires. According to Lhamu (2000) this approach has been effective, with the number of forest fires in the 1999-2000 winter season considerably less than in previous years. It was largely contributed to the increased education of local people. However, if this approach was really so successful, it remains doubtful why the number of fires increased again in 2001, with a very significant increase in the winter of 2001-2002. It seems that not education, but favourable weather circumstances (not too dry, occasional rainfall, not too strong winds) play a much larger role in preventing the fires.

When fires do occur, the forest department staff together with local villagers try their best to control them, often even at the risk of losing their own life. But often it is a lost cause, as the situation at that time is not conducive to take any action. Sometimes united power of the department and the local people can put off the fire, or by means of backfiring it can be prevented from spreading. But in general, there is not much that human beings can do. The winds are often too strong and the vegetation too dry to put the fire off or even prevent spreading.

Annex K:

List of Important Tree Species

Local, common and botanical name of important tree and shrub species¹²

Tshangla	Dzongkha	Bramilo	English/ common	Botanical	Main uses
Chorgengshing	Churushing	Chorgengshing	Amala, omla	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> (syn. <i>Embllica officinalis</i>)	Food, firewood, timber, tannin, fodder
Tsendenshing	Tsendenshing	Tsendenshing	Cypress	<i>Cyperus corneyana, himalayensis</i>	Timber, incense
Solo bang		Solo bang	Lemon grass	<i>Cymbopogon flexuosus</i>	Fodder/ manure, essential oil extraction
Balingmoshing, thobdashing, nyerashing, jashing (Drametse only)	Thobdashing	Thobdashing	Eucalypt	<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp. (mainly <i>E. robusta</i>)	Fuelwood, timber, flagpoles, fence posts
Gulishing	Machushing ?	Gulishing	Kawla	<i>Persea fructifera</i>	Timber
Kheyshing	Tashing	Tarkashing	Walnut	<i>Juglans regia</i>	Timber, food, dye, medicine
Roinangshing	Teytongshing	Teytongphushing	Chir pine	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	Timber, flag poles, fence posts, fuelwood, leaf litter (bedding/ manure), resin tapping
Zalushing	Puyamshing	Puyamshing	Chitaune	<i>Schima wallichii</i>	Manure, fuelwood, timber
Tshaishing	Sokeyshing	Nangshalu-shing	Chestnut	<i>Castanopsis tribuloides</i> (sokar), <i>hystrix</i> (sonak)	Timber, fruit
Khirtangshing	Khirtangshing	-	Kokko, Albizia	<i>Albizia lebbeck</i>	Timber, fuelwood, fodder, medicine
Phinshing	Yikashing	-	-	<i>Aesandra butyracea</i>	Essential oil extraction, fruits ³

¹ Information from own observation Forest Services Division, 1997a, b, 1998, 1999, Department of Forest Services, 2001a, b, Shah, 1996, Messerschmidt et al, 2000, Grlerson and Long, 1983.

² The local nomenclature in Dzongkha, Tshangla and Bramilo is extremely difficult and names differ even within languages from village to village. E.g., whereas Tshangla speakers from Drametse call *Melia* 'thobdashing' and *Eucalyptus* 'jashing', this is exactly the opposite for all other Tshangla speakers. Therefore other sources might mention different names for the same species.

Non-convergence of Objectives in Social Forestry in Eastern Bhutan

Kharabtang-shing, Shajulashing	-	-	-	<i>Lyonia ovalifolia</i>	Fuelwood
Bainangshing	Sisishing	Sisishing	Oak	<i>Quercus griffithii</i>	Timber, leaf litter (bedding/manure), fuelwood
Dongkoshing, dhongkalashing	Dongashing	-	-	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Ornamental, fruit pulp
Karshing, champay-shing	Khashing	Khashing	Champ	<i>Michelia champaca</i>	Timber, fuelwood
Changshing	Tongphushing	-	Blue pine	<i>Pinus bhutanica</i> , <i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	Timber
Pagalashing	-	-	-	<i>Duabanga grandiflora</i>	Timber
Tsishing	-	-	Ipi-ipi	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Fodder, firewood, timber
Sushing, soshing, shishing	Bashing	-	Bamboo spp.	<i>Bambusa</i> spp.	Construction poles, food
Nyerashing, jashing, thobdashing (Drametse only)	Jashing	-	Bakaina, persian lilac	<i>Melja azaderach</i>	Fodder, timber, fuelwood
Jatsenshing (Drametse only), bashing	Jatsenshing	-	Cryptomeria	<i>Cryptomeria japonica</i>	Religious purposes, fuelwood, flag poles
Lishing	Patsha	-	Cane spp.	<i>Dendrocalamus</i> spp.	Poles, fencing, mats
Phrogpalagashing	-	Phrogpalagashing	Pajash	<i>Butea buteiformis</i>	Oil from seeds
Phrumchungshing ⁴	-	-	Imli (titiri), bhuta badam, neem, mahua?	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> , <i>Corylus colurna</i> , <i>Azadirachta indica</i> , <i>Madhuca latifolia?</i>	Fruits as export

³ Penjore, 2001.

⁴ This species was suggested by CFMG members from Drametse Zangkhar as additional species to be planted in the CF. They had heard that the fruits/seeds fetch a considerable price when exported to India. However, the exact species could not be established in absence of trees, and a few likely species are mentioned.

Annex L: List of consulted individuals

Thimphu:

Mr. Mani Sangye, Head, FED,

Khangma:

Mr. Karma Drukpa, PM, PFO,
Mr. B.B. Chhetri, APM, TFDP,
Mr. Dechen Dorji,
Mr. K.J. Tempel,
Mr. Dhono, SF section, TFDP

Lhuentse:

Mr. Nakphel Drukpa, FEO,
Mr. Tshering Dorji, FEO,

Mr. Karma, chairman, CFMC,
Mr. Tshewangja, member, CFMC,
Mrs. Tshering Dolma, watcher, CFMC,

Mrs. Norbu Choeden, member, CFMG,
Mr. Dorji, member, CFMG.

Trashigang:

Mr. Sonam Gyaltsen, DzFO,

Mr. Sonam Jamtsho, chairman, CFMC,

Mrs. Yeshey Choeden,
member representative, CFMG,
Ms. Kesang Dechen, member, CFMG.

Trashigang:

Mr. Sithar Dorji, DzFO,
Mr. Dorji Drukpa, FEO,

Mr. Wangchuk, chairman, CPEC,
Mr. Kunzang, secretary, CPEC,

(members)
Mr. Ngotong,
Mr. Bendo,

Mr. Wangchuk Namgay,
Ms. Yangki,
Mrs. Tashi,
Mrs. Tshewang Choden,
Mrs. Peldon,
Ms. Yangchen,
Mrs. Sanjay,

Mr. Kunzang Wangchuk,
Mr. Jangchuk,
Mr. Monang,
Mr. Chaynga,
Mrs. Kozang,
Mrs. Sherub Tshomo,
Mrs. Tshogayme,
Mrs. Tshering Zangmo,

Mongar:

Mr. Rinchen Wangdi, DzFO,
Mr. Tshering Choeda, FEO,
Mr. Tashi Wangchuk, AHEO,

Mr. Ugyen Penjor, chairman, CFEC,
Mr. Karma Wangchuk, secretary, CFEC,
Mr. Dawa, member, CFEC,
Mrs. Karjai, member, CFEC,
Mr. Lungjey, member, CFEC,

(Zangkhar/Wangkhar/Phantshomo)
(members)

Mr. Yeshey,
Mrs. Tsokey,
Mrs. Tshewang,
Mrs. Tshomo,
Mrs. Ugyen Lhamo,
Mrs. Dorji Udon,
Mrs. Pema Chezoni,
Mr. Dorji,
Mrs. Sangay Choden,
(member representatives)

Ms. Jaymo,
Ms. Pema Dechen,
Mrs. Penden Tshomo,
Mr. Karma,
Mrs. Sonam Choden,
Mrs. Danzhi,
Mrs. Yangay Lhamo,
Mrs. Yangdon,
Ms. Zangmo,
Mrs. Chening,
Mrs. Tshewang,

(Shangpa)

(members)

Mrs. Yeshey Dema,
Mrs. Sangay Pema,
Mrs. Chador,
Mr. Rinzin,
Mr. Sangay Phuntsho,
Mrs. Pema Chozom,
Mr. Tenzin,
Mr. Dukpula,
(member representatives)
Mrs. Dolma,
Ms. Sonam Wangmo,
Mrs. Kunzang,
Mrs. Pem Choden,
Mrs. Ugyen Choden,
Mrs. Peldon,
Ms. Yangzom,
Mr. Chenga,
Mr. Tashi,
Mrs. Zhiden,
Mrs. Peldon,
Mr. Ugyen Nangay,
Mrs. Tshering,
Mrs. Dolma,
Ms. Tshewang Zangmo,
Mrs. Ugyen Lhamo,
Mr. Tshering Wangdi,

(Thramlu/Bikhar/Waichu)

(members)

Mr. Daza,
Mrs. Dorji Tshomo,
Mrs. Sonam Choeden,
Mrs. Wangmo,
Mrs. Choden,
Mrs. Kinzang Wangmo,
Mrs. Ugyen Lhamo,

Mrs. Choezang,
Mrs. Pema Zangmo,
Mrs. Sonam Choden,
Mrs. Rinzang,
(member representatives)
Mr. Nidup,
Ms. Chocki,
Ms. Norbu,
Mr. Dendup Yeshey,
Mrs. Peldon,
Mr. Sanjay,
Mrs. Chengamo,
Mrs. Pelmo,
Mrs. Duchen Zangmo,
Mrs. Tshochi Lhamo,
Mrs. Pema Choden,
Mr. Norbu,
Mr. Tshewang.